

Health effects associated with consumption of processed meat, sugar-sweetened beverages, and trans fatty acids: a Burden of Proof study

Authors:

Demewoz Haile¹, Kassandra L. Harding¹, Susan A. McLaughlin¹, Charlie Ashbaugh¹, Vanessa Garcia¹, Nora M. Gilbertson^{1,2}, Hewan Kifle¹, Marie C. Parent^{1,2}, Reed J.D. Sorensen¹, Simon I. Hay^{1,2}, Aleksandr Y. Aravkin^{1,3}, Peng Zheng^{1,2}, Jeffrey D. Stanaway^{1,2}, Christopher J. L. Murray^{1,2} & Michael Brauer^{1,4}

Affiliations

¹Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, University of Washington, Seattle, WA, USA

²Department of Health Metrics Sciences, School of Medicine, University of Washington, Seattle, WA, USA

³ Department of Applied Mathematics, University of Washington, Seattle, WA, USA

⁴School of Population and Public Health, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada

Corresponding author:

Demewoz Haile, MSc, PhD

Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195 USA

dhwolde@uw.edu

Abstract

Previous research suggests detrimental health effects associated with consuming processed foods, including processed meats, sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs), and trans fatty acids (TFAs). However, systematic characterization of the dose-response relationships between these foods and health outcomes is limited. Using burden of proof meta-regression methods, we evaluated the associations between processed meat, SSBs, and TFAs and three chronic diseases: type 2 diabetes, ischemic heart disease (IHD), and colorectal cancer. We conservatively estimated that – relative to zero consumption – consuming processed meat (at 0.6–57 g/day) was associated with at least an 11% average increase in type 2 diabetes risk and a 7% (at 0.78–55 g/day) increase in colorectal cancer risk. SSB intake (at 1.5–390 g/day) was associated with at least an 8% average increase in type 2 diabetes risk and a 2% (at 0–365 g/day) increase in IHD risk. TFA consumption (at 0.25–2.56% of daily energy intake) was associated with at least a 3% average increase in IHD risk. These associations each received two-star ratings reflecting weak relationships or inconsistent input evidence, highlighting both the need for further research and – given the high burden of these chronic diseases – the merit of continuing to recommend limiting consumption of these foods.

Introduction

Ultra-processed foods high in calories, sugars, unhealthy fats, and salt have been linked to a variety of adverse health outcomes^{1,2}. Processed meat, sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs), and trans fatty acids (TFAs) are widely-consumed ultra-processed foods that are consistently associated with increased chronic disease risk^{3,4}. The Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study (GBD) 2021 estimated that diet high in processed meat contributed to nearly 300,000 deaths globally in 2021 and over 10 million disability-adjusted life years (DALYs, which combine years of life lost plus years lived with disability); diets high in SSBs and TFAs were estimated to contribute to approximately 3.6 and 2.5 million DALYs, respectively⁵.

Processed meats, preserved by smoking, curing, salting, or the addition of chemical preservatives, can contain harmful compounds, such as N-nitroso compounds³⁶, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)⁷, and heterocyclic amines⁸. High consumption of processed meats has been linked to chronic diseases such as heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and colorectal cancer. It is hypothesized that this is due to increased visceral fat index⁹, inflammation^{10–12}, and the potential for factors such as N-nitroso compounds, PAHs, and heterocyclic amines to induce tumors^{13–16}. SSBs encompass a wide range of beverages including sodas, fruit drinks, sports drinks, energy drinks, and sweetened teas and coffees, and they compose the primary source of added sugars in many people's diets¹⁷. High consumption of added sugars, particularly in liquid form, is associated with weight gain and increased risk of obesity, type 2 diabetes, and ischemic heart disease (IHD)¹⁸. SSB consumption has risen globally during the last three decades, with the steepest increases in low- and middle-income countries¹⁹. TFAs are a type of unsaturated fat occurring naturally in small amounts in some meat and dairy products, but also produced artificially to convert vegetable oil from a liquid to a solid via hydrogenation. Artificial TFAs, inexpensive and shelf-stable fats used in many processed foods and baked goods,²⁰ have been associated with increased risk of systemic inflammation²¹ and cardiovascular diseases^{22–24}.

Because processed meat, SSBs, and TFAs are widely available and their consumption is commonplace, it is important to rigorously characterize the dose-response relationships between intake of these foods and the risk of prevalent chronic diseases, and to systematically evaluate the strength and consistency of evidence supporting these associations. Here, we performed updated systematic reviews and meta-analyses using burden of proof methods to characterize relationships for dietary risk factors – specifically processed foods – and related health outcomes. Our present analysis examines the associations between processed meat consumption and three health outcomes (type 2 diabetes, IHD, and colorectal cancer), between SSB intake and two outcomes (type 2 diabetes and IHD), and between TFA consumption and one outcome (IHD). These risk-outcome pairs were selected based on their inclusion – initially predicated on World Cancer Research Fund grades of convincing or probably evidence (5) – in

GBD 2021. To accurately and reliably capture disease risk across the full intake range observed in input studies, we used burden of proof meta-regression methods²⁵ designed to 1) flexibly model risk-outcome associations that may not be linearly related across the entire relative risk function and 2) conservatively estimate relationships, accounting for consistency/inconsistency across input study findings. Results and policy implications of this study are summarized in **Table 1**.

Results

Overview: In this study, we conducted systematic reviews and meta-analyses to evaluate the dose-response associations between processed meat consumption and three chronic disease outcomes (type 2 diabetes, IHD, colorectal cancer); between SSB consumption and type 2 diabetes and IHD; and between TFAs consumption and IHD based on Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines²⁶. The PRISMA workflow diagrams for processed meat are described in **Extended Data Figures 1-3**. The PRISMA flow diagrams for the SSB and TFA systematic reviews are described in **Extended Data Figures 4-5 and Extended Data Figure 6**, respectively. Further details on our search strategy and inclusionary and exclusionary criteria are detailed in the **Methods** and the **Supplementary Appendix, sections 1-3**, including **Supplementary Tables 1-4**. The characteristics of the studies included in these systematic reviews are presented in **Supplementary Table 5**. The definitions of bias covariates (**in Supplementary Table 6**) and the bias covariate scores of each study were reported in **Supplementary Tables 7- 9**. Most of the studies adjusted their effect size for age, sex, body mass index (BMI), and energy intake (**Supplementary Table 8-9**).

Processed meat consumption and type 2 diabetes

Our analysis of processed meat consumption and type 2 diabetes included 96 observations from 15 prospective cohort studies²⁷⁻⁴¹ and one nested case control study⁴², which included a total of 1,115,885 participants and 64,607 type 2 diabetes events. The follow-up period ranged from 4.6 years to 40 years. Most of the studies (n=12)^{28,30-35,37,38,40-42} used type 2 diabetes incidence as the endpoint to estimate effect sizes, while four studies^{27,29,36,39} considered both diabetes incidence and mortality as endpoints. Six studies^{29,35,37,38,41} determined outcomes using administrative medical records, disease registries, or death certificates; five studies used self-reported incidence^{30,34,38,41,42}; three cohort studies used biomarkers^{28,29,32}; and two cohorts used physician diagnosis^{37,40}. All studies adjusted their effect size measure for age and sex. All studies except one adjusted for smoking. Other common adjustment variables included energy intake (n=13)^{28,30-35,37,38,40-42}, alcohol consumption (n=12)^{27-30,32,33,36-38,40-42} and BMI (n=14)^{27-30,32-36,38-42}.

We observed a statistically significant, non-linear, monotonic increase in type 2 diabetes risk associated with higher processed meat consumption; that is, disease risk increased with

increased intake at all intake levels but, for a given unit increase in consumption risk increased most steeply at lower intake levels (**Fig. 1, Panel A**). The mean relative risk (RR) of developing type 2 diabetes was 1.30 (1.12–1.52) at a daily intake of 50 g of processed meat compared to the theoretical minimum risk exposure level (TMREL; equal here to 0 g/day or no consumption).

As a complement to the main RR function, we generated a conservatively derived burden of proof risk function (BPRF), which – averaged across the central part of the exposure range – yielded an estimate of 1.11, indicating that consuming processed meat in the range of the 15th to 85th percentiles of exposure (0.6 to 57 g/day), compared to consuming no processed meat, was associated on average with at least an 11% higher risk of type 2 diabetes.. This BPRF equated to a risk-outcome score (i.e., the signed value of the average log BPRF) of 0.10, corresponding to a two-star rating within the burden of proof framework. We observed asymmetry in the funnel plot (**Fig. 1, Panel A**), and the result of the Egger’s regression suggested statistically significant evidence of publication or reporting bias (Egger’s regression p-value 0.0001) (**Table 2**). We found that trimming had a significant effect on the risk-outcome score: without trimming, the risk-outcome score increased to 0.14 suggesting that the conservatively estimated association between processed consumption and type 2 diabetes is relatively sensitive to outliers (**Extended data Fig. 7, Panel A and Supplementary Table 17**).

Processed meat consumption and IHD

In the processed meat consumption and IHD systematic review, we included 11 prospective cohort studies^{36,43–52} representing a total of 1,173,821 participants and 31,549 IHD events. The median (range) follow-up period was 14 (8 to 30) years. Most of the studies used incidence and mortality as the endpoints^{36,43–46,48,49}, based on administrative medical records, disease registries, or death certificates^{36,43–46,48–52}. All of the studies adjusted their effect size measure for age and sex. Most of the studies adjusted for physical activity (n= 9)^{36,43,44,46–51}, BMI (n=9)^{36,43–46,48–51}, smoking (n= 10)^{36,43,44,46–52} and energy intake (n= 8)^{43,44,46–51}.

We observed a weak, non-linear, monotonic increase in IHD risk associated with processed meat consumption when accounting for between-study heterogeneity (**Fig. 1, Panel B**). We estimated the RR to be 1.15 (0.97–1.36) at 50 g/day consumption of processed meat compared to no consumption (**Fig. 1, Panel B and Supplementary Table 14**). Our conservative analysis yielded a risk-outcome score of -0.001, corresponding to a one-star rating, indicating a weak association after accounting for between-study heterogeneity. We did not find significant evidence of publication or reporting bias, and visual inspection of the funnel plot provided no evidence of substantial bias. The risk-outcome score calculated without trimming was consistent with the model using trimming (risk-outcome score = -0.01), which indicates that the model is insensitive to outliers (**Extended data Fig. 7, Panel B and Supplementary Table 17**).

Processed meat consumption and colorectal cancer

In the meta-analysis that examined the association between processed meat consumption and colorectal cancer, we included 18 prospective cohort studies^{53–70} with a total of 2,678,052 participants and 30,259 colorectal cancer events. The median (range) of follow-up was 9 (5 to 27) years. Most of the studies (n= 15)^{53–58,60–63,65,66,68–70} used incidence of colorectal cancer as an endpoint and the remaining three studies used both incidence and mortality. Most of the studies (n= 14)^{53,54,56–58,60–63,65–67,69,70} used administrative medical records or disease registries to determine the occurrence of colorectal cancer. All studies adjusted their effect size measures for age and sex. Most of the studies adjusted for BMI (n= 14)^{53,55,56,58,59,61–66,68–70}, smoking (n= 14)^{53,55,56,58–62,64,66–70}, education (n = 11)^{53,55,56,58–60,63,65,66,69,70}, energy intake (n= 15)^{53–61,63–68}, physical activity (n= 13),^{53,55,59–62,64–70} and alcohol intake (n=14)^{53,55,58–64,66–70}.

We observed a statistically significant non-linear monotonic increase in colorectal cancer risk associated with higher processed meat consumption (**Fig. 1, Panel C**). The mean RR of developing colorectal cancer risk was 1.26 (1.08–1.47) at a daily intake of 50 g of processed meat compared to the TMREL (i.e., no consumption). We estimated the exposure-averaged BPRF to be 1.07, indicating that consuming processed meat in the range of the 15th to 85th percentiles of exposure (0.78 to 55 g) – compared to consuming no processed meat – was associated with at least a 7% higher risk, on average, of colorectal cancer. The risk-outcome score (0.07) equates to a two-star rating, indicating a weak association between processed meat and colorectal cancer when accounting for between study heterogeneity. We did not find significant evidence of publication bias. We found that using untrimmed data impacted between-study heterogeneity and notably influenced the risk-outcome score (0.02) but did not change the star rating of the strength of the evidence (**Extended Data Fig. 7, Panel C and Supplementary Table 17**).

SSB consumption and type 2 diabetes

Our analysis of SSB consumption and type 2 diabetes included 92 observations from 18 prospective cohort studies^{71–88} and one nested case control study⁸⁹, representing a total of 563,444 participants and 39,505 type 2 diabetes events. All studies used type 2 diabetes incidence as the endpoint to estimate effect sizes. Fourteen studies used self-reported incidence^{71,73–77,79–84,87,89}; two^{72,78} studies used administrative medical records, disease registries, or death certificates; and one study⁸⁸ used physician diagnosis to determine the outcome. All studies adjusted their effect size measure for age, sex, BMI, and physical activity. All studies^{71–87,89} except one adjusted for smoking. Other common adjustment variables included energy intake (n=14)^{71–76,78–80,84–87,89}, alcohol consumption (n=14)^{71,73–75,77,79,80,82–87,89}, education level (n=14)^{71–74,76,77,79–84,87,89} and hypertension (n=8)^{10,71,73–75,83–85}.

We observed a statistically significant, non-linear, monotonic increase in type 2 diabetes risk associated with higher SSB consumption (**Fig. 2, Panel A**). The mean RR of type 2 diabetes at a

consumption level of 250 g/day (~8 oz) was 1.20 (1.07–1.34) compared to the TMREL (0 g/day) (**Supplementary Table 15**).

We estimated the exposure averaged BPRF to be 1.08, indicating that consuming SSB in the range of 15th to 85th percentiles of exposure (1.5 to 390 g/day) was associated, on average, with at least a 8% higher risk of type 2 diabetes. This BPRF equated to a risk-outcome score of 0.07, corresponding to a two-star rating (**Table 2**). We did not observe statistically significant evidence of publication or reporting bias (Egger's regression p-value 0.25) (**Fig. 2, Panel A**). We found that trimming had a minimal impact on the risk-outcome score, and without trimming, the risk-outcome score was 0.07 (**Extended Data Fig. 8, Panel A, Supplementary Table 17**).

SSB consumption and IHD

Our analysis of SSB consumption and IHD included 27 observations from eight studies^{90–97}, representing a total of 961,176 participants and 24,542 IHD events. Three studies estimated effect size using IHD mortality^{93,95,96} as the endpoint, six studies evaluated both IHD incidence and mortality as endpoints^{90–92,94,96,97,97}. All studies determined outcomes using administrative medical records, disease registries, or death certificates^{90–97}. All studies adjusted their effect size measure for age, sex, smoking, physical activity, BMI, and alcohol intake.

We observed a statistically significant, non-linear, monotonic increase in IHD risk associated with higher SSB consumption (**Fig. 2, Panel B**). Compared to no consumption, the mean RR of IHD at a consumption level of 250 g/day (~8 oz) was 1.07 (1.03–1.12). We estimated the exposure-averaged BPRF to be 1.03, indicating that consuming SSB in the range of the 15th to 85th percentiles of exposure (0 g to 365 g/day) was associated, on average, with at least a 2% higher risk of IHD. The BPRF equated to a risk-outcome score of 0.02, corresponding to a two-star rating. The Egger's regression did not show statistically significant evidence of publication or reporting bias (Egger's regression p-value 0.36) (**Table 2 and Fig. 2, Panel B**). We found that trimming had no effect on the risk-outcome score (**Extended Data Fig. 8, Panel B, Supplementary Table 17**).

Fig. 2: Relative risk of sugar-sweetened beverages on type 2 diabetes (Panel A) and ischemic heart diseases (Panel B). The panels show the log(relative risk) function, the relative risk function, and a modified funnel plot showing the residuals (relative to 0) on the x-axis and the estimated standard error that includes the reported standard error and between-study heterogeneity on the y-axis. RR relative risk, UI uncertainty interval.

TFA consumption and IHD

We identified six prospective cohort studies to evaluate the relationship between TFA consumption^{98–103} and IHD, representing 226,509 individuals and 12,548 IHD events. The median follow-up was 24 years (follow-up range: 6 to 30 years). All studies determined outcomes using administrative medical records or disease registries. In all studies, the effect size measures were adjusted for sex, BMI, energy intake, and smoking. All studies adjusted the effect size for age except one^{98,100–103}. Most of the studies adjusted their effect size for alcohol intake^{99–103}. Four of the six studies adjusted their effect size for education^{98,99,101,102} or hypertension^{99,101–103}. Three studies adjusted their effect size measures for physical activity^{99,101,102}.

We observed a non-linear, monotonic increase in risk of IHD with increasing consumption of TFAs (**Fig. 3**). The mean RR of IHD at 1% of daily energy intake from TFA compared to no TFA intake was 1.11 (1.00–1.24). Consumption of TFAs at higher levels (2% of daily energy intake) was associated with a 1.20 (1.00–1.44) increased risk of IHD. We observed considerable between-study heterogeneity (**Fig. 3 and Supplementary Table 16**).

Fig. 3: Relative risk of trans-fat consumption and ischemic heart diseases. The panels show the log(relative risk) function, the relative risk function, and a modified funnel plot showing the residuals (relative to 0) on the x-axis and the estimated standard error that includes the reported standard error and between-study heterogeneity on the y-axis. RR relative risk, UI uncertainty interval.

When between-study heterogeneity was accounted for, our conservative interpretation of the evidence suggested that consuming TFA in the range of the 15th to 85th percentiles of exposure (0.25 to 2.56 % of daily energy intake) increases the risk of IHD, on average, by at least 3%. This corresponded to a risk-outcome score of 0.03 (**Table 2**). This risk-outcome score equates to a two-star rating, indicating the association between TFA and IHD is weak but significant when accounting for between-study heterogeneity. There was no statistically significant evidence of publication or reporting bias (Egger’s regression p-value 0.44). We found that trimming had a significant effect on the risk-outcome score; without trimming, the risk-outcome score decreased to -0.12, which equates to a one-star rating, suggesting that the risk-outcome score for TFA consumption and IHD is sensitive to outliers (**Extended Data Fig. 9**).

Discussion

This meta-analysis evaluated the dose-response relationships between processed meat consumption and three chronic disease outcomes – type 2 diabetes, IHD, colorectal cancer; between SSB intake and type 2 diabetes and IHD; and between TFA consumption and IHD. For all six risk-outcome pairs assessed, even our intentionally conservative BPRF summary measures showed that higher intake of the processed food under evaluation was associated with significantly increased risk of the specified health outcome. Higher consumption of processed meats was associated with increased risk of type 2 diabetes, colorectal cancer, and IHD; higher intake of SSBs was associated with increased type 2 diabetes and IHD risk; and increased consumption of TFAs was associated with increased IHD risk. Except for the association between processed meat consumption and IHD – which received a one-star rating

suggesting a weaker association and/or less consistent evidence base – all of the risk-outcome relationships received two-star ratings, also defined as weak within the burden of proof framework. However, these low star-ratings serve to indicate the need for further research to resolve inconsistencies across input study findings and clarify the level of health threat posed by increased consumption of the processed food in question. Moreover, the policy relevance of a risk factor must depend both on the magnitude of the association and strength of underlying evidence along with the prevalence of the risk factor and associated diseases outcomes.

Because burden of proof meta-regression methods allowed us to capture the shape of the risk-outcome association from the data rather than enforcing prior assumptions such as log-linearity, our findings more accurately reflect the dose-response relationship at specific levels of consumption than do results from traditional meta-analyses. For all six of the RR curves generated by our analysis, health risk increased monotonically; that is, across the full range of exposure, risk increased as consumption increased. Notably, however, the steepest slopes of the risk curves occurred at exposure levels approximately equivalent to one serving or less for each of the dietary risk factors. This indicates that the health risks associated with consuming processed meats, SSBs, and TFAs increased the fastest at low levels of consumption, i.e., one serving size a day. This information provides critical data for public health specialists and policy makers responsible for dietary guidelines and potential initiatives aimed at reducing consumption of these processed foods.

With respect to specific risk-outcome pairs, our analyses yielded two-star ratings for the association of processed meat consumption with type 2 diabetes and with colorectal cancer, and – even based on our conservatively derived summary estimates – showed that consumption at commonly observed levels (compared to zero consumption) was associated with at least an 11% average increase in type 2 diabetes risk and 7% average increase in colorectal cancer risk. Our RR curves showed that regularly consuming 50 g/day of processed meat, roughly equivalent to eating a standard-sized hot dog, was associated with a 30% increase in type 2 diabetes risk and a 26% increase in colorectal cancer risk. The monotonic increases in health risk with increased consumption of processed meat suggest there is not a "safe" amount of processed meat consumption with respect to diabetes or colorectal cancer risk. Our findings are consistent with the World Health Organization (WHO) designation of processed meat as carcinogenic to humans¹⁰⁴ and designations by the World Cancer Research Fund and the American Institute for Cancer Research of processed meat consumption as a risk factor for colon cancer. The majority of the existing dietary guidelines provide qualitative recommendations to limit or avoid the consumption of processed meat without specifying intake levels, although a few do provide quantitative recommendations. Based on our findings, dietary guidelines should note the potential health risks of consuming even small amounts of processed meat.

Regarding the relationship between processed meat and IHD, our conservative interpretation indicates that the evidence for an association is weak, yielding a one-star rating due to a negative risk-outcome score value. One-star ratings reflect risk-outcome relationships that are statistically significant using conventional analytic methods but do not achieve significance based on conservative BPRF methods incorporating between-study heterogeneity. For all of our analyses of processed meat consumption, we found considerable heterogeneity among input study findings, which contributed to low star ratings reflecting a combination of low effect size and/or inconsistent input evidence. This heterogeneity likely resulted from variations in input study characteristics that we were unable to fully account for with our covariate selection and adjustment methods, in addition to the impact of potential effect modifiers such as genetic factors¹⁰⁵ and confounders. Further research is needed to untangle confounding effects and ultimately coalesce on a more consistent body of evidence.

With respect to SSBs, they are a significant source of added sugars in the diet, with consumption increasing globally^{5,19}. Our conservative interpretation of the available evidence, based on BPRF metrics, showed that commonly observed SSB consumption levels were associated with at least an 8% average increase in type 2 diabetes risk and at least a 2% increase in IHD risk, equating to two-star ratings. As with processed meat consumption, the RR curves we derived showed monotonic increases in type 2 diabetes and IHD risk with increased SSB consumption; that is, across the entire intake range, any increase in SSB consumption was associated with increased disease risk, with the steepest increases in risk observed at intake levels below 250 g/day, roughly equivalent to 9 ounces of soda or $\frac{3}{4}$ of a typical soda drink. Our findings support the need for initiatives to avoid/reduce the consumption of SSBs^{106,107}. WHO recommends limiting the intake of added sugar, including SSBs, to 10% of total caloric intake and a further reduction below 5% total caloric intake for additional health benefits¹⁰⁸. The Dietary Guidelines for Americans recommend limiting the intake of added sugar, including SSBs, to below 10%¹⁰⁹.

The relatively low two-star ratings for the disease outcomes tested in association with SSB intake were likely due in large part to high between-study heterogeneity, potentially resulting from variable health effects of particular SSBs depending on the amount of sugar content. Our SSB–type 2 diabetes model did test and include as a bias covariate whether input studies provided a clear definition of SSB (i.e., whether sugar was explicitly mentioned as a sweetener). However, this covariate could not be used as a proxy measure for the sugar content of SSBs, meaning it could not fully account for the heterogeneity associated with variation in the sugar content of SSBs. It is also noteworthy that all the SSB studies included in our analysis adjusted their effect size measures for BMI and for physical activity, and the majority accounted for energy intake. These adjustments reduced the likelihood that our estimates of increased type 2 diabetes and IHD risk associated with SSB consumption were mediated through effects of SSBs on BMI, energy intake, or physical activity.

Based on our meta-analysis examining the relationship between TFAs and IHD, our conservative BPRF estimate showed that commonly observed TFA consumption primarily from industrially produced trans-fat sources (0.24% to 2.5% of daily energy intake) was associated with at least 3% average increased risk of IHD, equating to a two-star association. The RR curve indicated a monotonic increase in IHD risk associated with increased TFAs consumption, with no safe level of exposure observed for industrially produced trans-fats. The relatively low star rating is again due in large part to high between-study heterogeneity, likely resulting from residual confounding and measurement error. In the input studies included in our meta-analysis, only a single study adjusted its effect size measurement for saturated fat intake, and none adjusted for other potential diet-related confounders including sodium, SSBs, and processed meat intake. Our findings support the need for initiatives such as the best practice policies recommended by WHO aimed at eliminating industrially produced TFAs from the food supply¹¹⁰. One policy is to establish mandatory national limits of 2 grams of industrial trans-fat per 100 grams of total fat in all foods. WHO additionally recommends instituting mandatory bans on the production and/or use of partially hydrogenated oil as an ingredient in all foods. The “REPLACE” action package, developed by WHO, supports the design and implementation of policies to eliminate industrially produced TFAs from the food supply.

All observational nutritional cohort analyses based on self-report and recall to quantify intake levels are subject to measurement error and residual confounding^{111–113}. The present risk-outcome analyses are likewise susceptible to such errors; to the extent we were unable to account for them, they were likely primary contributors to the high between-study heterogeneity that resulted in the relatively low star ratings. To account for confounding, burden of proof methods systematically test and adjust for bias covariates that might influence the estimated risk-outcome relationship. An important bias covariate that we tested for was whether input studies adjusted their effect size for energy intake, a well-known approach in nutritional epidemiology studies^{114,115}. Most of the studies included in our analyses made this adjustment, and it therefore was not identified by our algorithm as a significant bias covariate in our models. In addition to energy intake, we also accounted for whether studies adjusted for other dietary factors (e.g., consumption of fruits and vegetables, unprocessed meat, and alcohol) that could potentially confound the association between the dietary risk factors under investigation here and each outcome of interest. Relatively few input studies adjusted their effect size for these dietary factors, except for alcohol intake. Importantly, our bias covariate selection and adjustment methods were not able to eliminate all residual confounding, and did not address the measurement error intrinsic in dietary assessment tools^{111,112,116}.

Although the primarily two-star (and one one-star) ratings we obtained for the risk-outcome associations evaluated in this study are considered relatively weak, this is in large part due to high between-study heterogeneity leading to wide uncertainty intervals, as estimated in the

burden of proof framework, and the balance of evidence still points to adverse health outcomes associated with these foods. Policy makers should continue advocating for measures that reduce intake of processed meat, SSBs, and TFAs as these food items are consumed widely and are associated with diseases that are highly prevalent¹¹⁷. Additionally, nutritional epidemiology studies must incorporate advances in technology and new analytical techniques to address existing methodological challenges. For example, nutritional epidemiology studies can benefit considerably from recent developments in artificial intelligence and “omics” technologies. Artificial intelligence-assisted dietary assessment has significantly reduced measurement error associated with dietary recall^{118–120}, a major challenge in nutritional epidemiology studies. The use of Mendelian randomization techniques, which use study participants’ genetic profiles to predict their intake levels rather than relying on self-report and recall, show promise as a way to reduce the effects of residual confounding in analyses estimating associations between dietary intake factors and health outcomes^{121,122}.

The results of our meta-analysis are subject to a number of limitations. In our analysis, we investigated a small set of health outcomes for each dietary risk factor – limited to the relevant risk-outcome pairs included in GBD 2021 – which did not encompass all possible health outcomes associated with these risk factors. Expanding the pool of potential health outcomes associated with these dietary risks could allow for a more complete accounting of the evidence and associated burden in the future. Additionally, we focused on three dietary risk factors that are components of ultra-processed foods, but we did not investigate the health effects of other potentially harmful ultra-processed foods such as sweetened breakfast cereals and processed cheese products. We included prospective cohort and case-cohort studies, which inherently introduce residual confounding that our methods cannot completely eliminate. As noted previously, a considerable number of the studies included in this meta-analysis did not account for dietary confounding factors beyond energy intake. Additionally, the primary exposure assessment tool in almost all studies included was the food frequency questionnaire (FFQ). The FFQ can introduce measurement errors arising primarily from difficulties experienced by respondents recalling long-term intake, along with instrument-specific limitations such as the finite inventory of foods listed and lack of detailed information about the foods. Several of the studies included assessed dietary exposure only at baseline, which might not accurately reflect future dietary habits. Furthermore, even though investigations of diet-gene interactions are becoming more common, we could not include genetic predisposition as a bias covariate in our analysis due to the absence of genetic information in the studies included. When studies reported effect sizes for total TFA consumption without stratifying by TFA source (ruminant vs. industrial), we elected to assume that the majority of the TFA was industrially produced. The risk model we use is based on effect sizes derived from incidence and/or mortality data, and we were unable to run separate models for incidence and mortality due to data scarcity, except in

the case of SSB–type 2 diabetes. Finally, although many of the studies included reported serving sizes in grams, some did not define serving size. In these cases, we applied a constant conversion factor to translate serving size into grams, which might not be consistent with the definition of/perception of serving size within the given study’s context.

In conclusion, our conservative BPRF metrics support recommendations to avoid or limit the consumption of processed meat, SSBs, and TFAs due to their associations with prevalent chronic diseases. However, our analyses of the currently available evidence yielded associations with one- to two-star ratings, due in large part to significant heterogeneity between studies – likely attributable to differences in study-level characteristics, residual confounding, and measurement error that we were unable to control for. To the extent these star ratings – particularly the one-star rating for the association between processed meat and IHD – reflect a lack of consistent data, they highlight the need for stronger, more diverse evidence beyond conventional observational epidemiological studies.

Acknowledgements

Research reported in this publication was supported by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (OPP1152504). The funders of the study had no role in study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, writing of the final report, or the decision to publish.

Author contributions

D.H., S.I.H., M.B., C.A., and J.D.S. managed the estimation or publications process. D.H., K.L.H. and C.J.L.M. wrote the first draft of the manuscript. D.H. had primary responsibility for applying analytical methods to produce estimates. D.H. and H.K. had primary responsibility for seeking, cataloguing, extracting, or cleaning data; designing or coding figures and tables. D.H., V.G., M.C.P, R.J.D.S., J.D.S. and C.J.L.M. provided data or critical feedback on data sources. D.H., R.J.D.S., P.Z., N.M.G., and A.Y.A. developed methods or computational machinery. D.H., K.L.H., V.G., A.Y.A., J.D.S., M.B. and S.I.H. provided critical feedback on methods or results. D.H., K.L.H., S.A.M. C.J.L.M., and M.B. drafted the work or revised it critically for important intellectual content. D.H., C.A. and S.I.H. managed the overall research enterprise.

Competing interests

The authors of this manuscript declare no competing interests

Tables

Table 1: Policy summary

Background	Previous research has indicated adverse effects of processed meat, sugar-sweetened beverage (SSB), and trans fatty acid (TFA) consumption on chronic disease outcomes. However, confidence in these findings has been limited by heterogeneous findings across research studies. In this meta-regression, we examined the relationships between processed meat and risk of type 2 diabetes, ischemic heart disease [IHD], and colorectal cancer; between SSBs and type 2 diabetes and IHD; and between TFAs and IHD. Using burden of proof methods that flexibly model non-linear relationships and quantify and incorporate between-study heterogeneity, we generated measures that capture the strength of the input evidence and provide conservative estimates of association to more accurately and reliably identify adverse risk-outcome relationships.
Main findings and limitations	Based on our conservative interpretation of available data, we found that consuming processed meat at levels between the 15 th to 85 th percentiles of exposure observed in the data analyzed was associated, on average, with at least an 11% increased risk (at consumption levels between 0.6 and 57 g/day) of type 2 diabetes and 7% increased risk (0.78 to 55 g/day) of colorectal cancer. SSB consumption was associated with at least 8% (1.5 to 390 g/day) and 2% (0 to 365 g/day) average increases in risk of type 2 diabetes and IHD, respectively. TFA consumption at 0.25 to 2.56% of daily energy intake was associated with at least a 3% average increase in IHD risk. In the burden of proof framework, these associations are rated as relatively weak two-star relationships, reflecting small effect sizes and/or lack of consistent evidence. We found a weaker one-star association between processed meat and IHD that did not support calculating percent change in IHD risk; this finding may change with the addition of new evidence. Importantly, we observed for all risk-outcome pairs analyzed a monotonic increase in risk of the specified disease outcomes at all levels of consumption, with the steepest increases in risk occurring at exposure levels approximately equivalent to one serving or less for each dietary risk factor. The primary limitations of our meta-analysis was based on observational studies, which are prone to residual confounding, and that the dominant exposure assessment method – the food frequency questionnaire – is susceptible to measurement errors.
Policy implications	This study found evidence – under a conservative interpretation of the available data – to justify robust efforts and policies to promote the reduced consumption of processed meat, SSBs, and TFAs, particularly industrially produced TFAs, to reduce the risk of chronic diseases. Our finding supports the World Health Organization's recent initiative to ban industrially produced trans fats and their call to tax SSBs to reduce diet-related non-communicable diseases. Our observation that the greatest increases in disease risk occurred at low intake levels suggests that even lower levels of habitual consumption of these dietary risk factors is not safe. Policies promoting access to and affordability of healthier food options could help mitigate the risks associated with the consumption of processed meats, SSBs, and TFAs. Therefore, efforts must be intensified to increase public awareness and policy action to reduce the consumption of these dietary risk factors and promotion of healthier food options. Future meta-analysis studies should prioritize

	examining the relationship between processed meat consumption and IHD, as the existing evidence, when interpreted conservatively, is weak.
--	--

Table 2: Strength of the evidence for the relationship between processed meat, SSBs and TFAs consumption and health outcomes

Risk-outcome pair	85 th percentile exposure level	Unit of exposure	RR (95% UI with γ)	RR (95% UI without γ)	BPRF	Risk-outcome score	Star rating	Pub. bias	No. of studies
Processed meat-Type 2 diabetes	56.81	g/day	1.32 (1.12, 1.55)	1.32 (1.24, 1.4)	11%	0.1	★ ★	Yes	16
Processed meat- colorectal cancer	54.88	g/day	1.28 (1.09, 1.5)	1.28 (1.19, 1.38)	7%	0.07	★ ★	No	18
Processed meat-IHD	30.16	g/day	1.12(0.98, 1.28)	1.13 (1.06, 1.18)	N/A	-0.001	★	No	11
SSB-Type 2 diabetes	390	g/day	1.24 (1.09, 1.41)	1.24 (1.19, 1.29)	8%	0.07	★ ★	No	19
SSB-IHD	365	g/day	1.12 (1.04, 1.2)	1.12 (1.08, 1.15)	2%	0.02	★ ★	No	8
Trans-fat -IHD	2.56	Percent of daily energy intake	1.24 (1.01, 1.52)	1.24 (1.15, 1.33)	3%	0.03	★ ★	No	6

The reported relative risk (RR) and its 95% uncertainty interval (UI) reflect the risk an individual who has been exposed to dietary risk factor of interest (i.e. processed meat, SSBs and TFAs consumption) has of developing the outcome of interest relative to that of someone who has not been exposed. We report the 95% UI when not incorporating between-study heterogeneity (γ) – "95% UI without γ " – and when accounting for between-study heterogeneity – "95% UI with γ ." The Burden of Proof Risk Function (BPRF) is calculated for risk-outcome pairs that were found to have significant relationships at an 0.05 level of significance when not incorporating between-study heterogeneity (i.e., the lower bound of the 95% UI without γ does not cross the null RR value of one). The BPRF corresponds to the 5th quantile estimate of relative risk accounting for between-study heterogeneity closest to the null for each risk–outcome pair, and it reflects the most conservative estimate of excess risk associated with dietary risk factors of interest that is consistent with the available data. Negative risk-outcome scores indicate that the evidence of the association is very weak and inconsistent. For ease of interpretation, we have transformed the risk-outcome scores and BPRF into a star rating (0-5) with a higher rating representing a larger effect with stronger evidence. The selected bias covariates were chosen for inclusion in the model using an algorithm that systematically detects bias covariates that correspond to significant sources of bias in the observations included. If selected, the observations were adjusted to better reflect the gold standard values of the covariate. For more information about the definition of candidate bias covariates, see Supplementary Table 6, and for the bias covariates selected for each model, refer to Supplementary Table 12.

Extended data Figures

Extended Data Fig. 1: PRISMA flow diagram of processed meat consumption and type 2 diabetes

Extended Data Fig. 2: PRISMA flow diagram of processed meat consumption and ischemic heart diseases

Extended Data Fig. 3: PRISMA flow diagram of processed meat consumption and colorectal cancer

Extended Data Fig. 4: PRISMA flow diagram of sugar sweetened beverages and type 2 diabetes

Extended Data Fig. 5: PRISMA flow diagram of sugar sweetened beverages and ischemic heart diseases

Extended Data Fig. 6: PRISMA flow diagram of trans-fat consumption and ischemic heart diseases

Extended Data Fig. 7: Relative Risk of Processed Meat Consumption on type 2 diabetes (Panel A), ischemic heart diseases (Panel B), and colorectal cancer (Panel C): Non-trimmed data.

Extended Data Fig. 8: Relative risk of sugar-sweetened beverages on type 2 diabetes (Panel A) and ischemic heart diseases (Panel B): non-trimmed data

Extended Data Fig. 9: Relative risk of trans-fat consumption and ischemic heart diseases: Non-trimmed data.

References

1. Monteiro, C. A. *et al.* Ultra-processed foods: what they are and how to identify them. *Public Health Nutr* **22**, 936–941 (2019).
2. Lane, M. M. *et al.* Ultra-processed food exposure and adverse health outcomes: umbrella review of epidemiological meta-analyses. *BMJ* e077310 (2024) doi:10.1136/bmj-2023-077310.
3. Mendoza, K. *et al.* Ultra-processed foods and cardiovascular disease: analysis of three large US prospective cohorts and a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies. *The Lancet Regional Health - Americas* **37**, 100859 (2024).
4. Srour, B. *et al.* Ultra-processed food intake and risk of cardiovascular disease: prospective cohort study (NutriNet-Santé). *BMJ* l1451 (2019) doi:10.1136/bmj.l1451.
5. Brauer, M. *et al.* Global burden and strength of evidence for 88 risk factors in 204 countries and 811 subnational locations, 1990–2021: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *The Lancet* **403**, 2162–2203 (2024).
6. Deveci, G. & Tek, N. A. -Nitrosamines: a potential hazard in processed meat products. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* **104**, 2551–2560 (2024).
7. Lee, J.-G. *et al.* Effects of grilling procedures on levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in grilled meats. *Food Chemistry* **199**, 632–638 (2016).
8. Zheng, W. & Lee, S.-A. Well-Done Meat Intake, Heterocyclic Amine Exposure, and Cancer Risk. *Nutrition and Cancer* **61**, 437–446 (2009).
9. López-Hernández, L. *et al.* Identifying Predictors of the Visceral Fat Index in the Obese and Overweight Population to Manage Obesity: A Randomized Intervention Study. *Obes Facts* **13**, 403–414 (2020).

10. Huang, Y. *et al.* Associations of Visceral Adipose Tissue, Circulating Protein Biomarkers, and Risk of Cardiovascular Diseases: A Mendelian Randomization Analysis. *Front. Cell Dev. Biol.* **10**, 840866 (2022).
11. Marques, M. D. *et al.* Relation between visceral fat and coronary artery disease evaluated by multidetector computed tomography. *Atherosclerosis* **209**, 481–486 (2010).
12. Oostindjer, M. *et al.* The role of red and processed meat in colorectal cancer development: a perspective. *Meat Science* **97**, 583–596 (2014).
13. Bellamri, M., Walmsley, S. J. & Turesky, R. J. Metabolism and biomarkers of heterocyclic aromatic amines in humans. *Genes and Environ* **43**, 29 (2021).
14. Lala, P. K. & Chakraborty, C. Role of nitric oxide in carcinogenesis and tumour progression. *The Lancet Oncology* **2**, 149–156 (2001).
15. Moorthy, B., Chu, C. & Carlin, D. J. Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons: From Metabolism to Lung Cancer. *Toxicol. Sci.* **145**, 5–15 (2015).
16. Rao, C. V. Nitric oxide signaling in colon cancer chemoprevention. *Mutation Research/Fundamental and Molecular Mechanisms of Mutagenesis* **555**, 107–119 (2004).
17. Sánchez-Pimienta, T. G., Batis, C., Lutter, C. K. & Rivera, J. A. Sugar-Sweetened Beverages Are the Main Sources of Added Sugar Intake in the Mexican Population. *The Journal of Nutrition* **146**, 1888S–1896S (2016).
18. Vartanian, L. R., Schwartz, M. B. & Brownell, K. D. Effects of Soft Drink Consumption on Nutrition and Health: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Am J Public Health* **97**, 667–675 (2007).
19. Lara-Castor, L. *et al.* Sugar-sweetened beverage intakes among adults between 1990 and 2018 in 185 countries. *Nat Commun* **14**, 5957 (2023).

20. Stender, S., Astrup, A. & Dyerberg, J. Ruminant and industrially produced *trans* fatty acids: health aspects. *Food & Nutrition Research* **52**, 1651 (2008).
21. Mozaffarian, D. *et al.* Dietary intake of trans fatty acids and systemic inflammation in women. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **79**, 606–612 (2004).
22. Bendsen, N. T., Christensen, R., Bartels, E. M. & Astrup, A. Consumption of industrial and ruminant trans fatty acids and risk of coronary heart disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies. *Eur J Clin Nutr* **65**, 773–783 (2011).
23. Mozaffarian, D., Katan, M. B., Ascherio, A., Stampfer, M. J. & Willett, W. C. Trans Fatty Acids and Cardiovascular Disease. *N Engl J Med* **354**, 1601–1613 (2006).
24. Naghavi, M. *et al.* Global burden of 288 causes of death and life expectancy decomposition in 204 countries and territories and 811 subnational locations, 1990–2021: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *The Lancet* **403**, 2100–2132 (2024).
25. Zheng, P. *et al.* The Burden of Proof studies: assessing the evidence of risk. *Nat Med* **28**, 2038–2044 (2022).
26. Page, M. J. *et al.* The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* n71 (2021) doi:10.1136/bmj.n71.
27. Ericson, U. *et al.* Food sources of fat may clarify the inconsistent role of dietary fat intake for incidence of type 2 diabetes. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **101**, 1065–1080 (2015).
28. Fretts, A. M. *et al.* Associations of processed meat and unprocessed red meat intake with incident diabetes: the Strong Heart Family Study. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **95**, 752–758 (2012).
29. Gu, X. *et al.* Red meat intake and risk of type 2 diabetes in a prospective cohort study of United States females and males. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **118**, 1153–1163 (2023).

30. Kurotani, K. *et al.* Red meat consumption is associated with the risk of type 2 diabetes in men but not in women: a Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study. *Br J Nutr* **110**, 1910–1918 (2013).
31. Lajous, M. *et al.* Processed and Unprocessed Red Meat Consumption and Incident Type 2 Diabetes Among French Women. *Diabetes Care* **35**, 128–130 (2012).
32. Liu, M. *et al.* Quantity and variety of food groups consumption and the risk of diabetes in adults: A prospective cohort study. *Clinical Nutrition* **40**, 5710–5717 (2021).
33. Männistö, S., Kontto, J., Kataja-Tuomola, M., Albanes, D. & Virtamo, J. High processed meat consumption is a risk factor of type 2 diabetes in the Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention study. *Br J Nutr* **103**, 1817–1822 (2010).
34. Mari-Sanchis, A. *et al.* Meat Consumption and Risk of Developing Type 2 Diabetes in the SUN Project: A Highly Educated Middle-Class Population. *PLoS ONE* **11**, e0157990 (2016).
35. Montonen, J. *et al.* Food consumption and the incidence of type II diabetes mellitus. *Eur J Clin Nutr* **59**, 441–448 (2005).
36. Papier, K. *et al.* Meat consumption and risk of 25 common conditions: outcome-wide analyses in 475,000 men and women in the UK Biobank study. *BMC Med* **19**, 53 (2021).
37. Son, J., Lee, Y. & Park, K. Effects of processed red meat consumption on the risk of type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular diseases among Korean adults: the Korean Genome and Epidemiology Study. *Eur J Nutr* **58**, 2477–2484 (2019).
38. Song, Y., Manson, J. E., Buring, J. E. & Liu, S. A Prospective Study of Red Meat Consumption and Type 2 Diabetes in Middle-Aged and Elderly Women. *Diabetes Care* **27**, 2108–2115 (2004).
39. Steinbrecher, A., Erber, E., Grandinetti, A., Kolonel, L. & Maskarinec, G. Meat consumption and risk of type 2 diabetes: the Multiethnic Cohort. *Public Health Nutr.* **14**, 568–574 (2011).

40. Van Woudenberg, G. J. *et al.* Meat Consumption and Its Association With C-Reactive Protein and Incident Type 2 Diabetes. *Diabetes Care* **35**, 1499–1505 (2012).
41. Villegas, R. *et al.* The association of meat intake and the risk of type 2 diabetes may be modified by body weight. *Int. J. Med. Sci.* 152–159 (2006) doi:10.7150/ijms.3.152.
42. The InterAct Consortium. Association between dietary meat consumption and incident type 2 diabetes: the EPIC-InterAct study. *Diabetologia* **56**, 47–59 (2013).
43. Al-Shaar, L. *et al.* Red meat intake and risk of coronary heart disease among US men: prospective cohort study. *BMJ* m4141 (2020) doi:10.1136/bmj.m4141.
44. Bernstein, A. M. *et al.* Major Dietary Protein Sources and Risk of Coronary Heart Disease in Women. *Circulation* **122**, 876–883 (2010).
45. Burke, V. *et al.* Health-related behaviours as predictors of mortality and morbidity in Australian Aborigines. *Preventive Medicine* **44**, 135–142 (2007).
46. Haring, B. *et al.* Dietary Protein Intake and Coronary Heart Disease in a Large Community Based Cohort: Results from the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities (ARIC) Study. *PLoS ONE* **9**, e109552 (2014).
47. Iqbal, R. *et al.* Associations of unprocessed and processed meat intake with mortality and cardiovascular disease in 21 countries [Prospective Urban Rural Epidemiology (PURE) Study]: a prospective cohort study. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **114**, 1049–1058 (2021).
48. Key, T. J. *et al.* Consumption of Meat, Fish, Dairy Products, and Eggs and Risk of Ischemic Heart Disease: A Prospective Study of 7198 Incident Cases Among 409 885 Participants in the Pan-European EPIC Cohort. *Circulation* **139**, 2835–2845 (2019).
49. Møller, S. P., Mejbørn, H., Christensen, A. I., Biloft-Jensen, A. & Thygesen, L. C. Meat consumption, stratified by dietary quality, and risk of heart disease. *Br J Nutr* **126**, 1881–1887 (2021).

50. Nagao, M. *et al.* Meat consumption in relation to mortality from cardiovascular disease among Japanese men and women. *Eur J Clin Nutr* **66**, 687–693 (2012).
51. Saito, E. *et al.* Association between meat intake and mortality due to all-cause and major causes of death in a Japanese population. *PLoS ONE* **15**, e0244007 (2020).
52. Whiteman, D., Muir, J., Jones, L., Murphy, M. & Key, T. Dietary questions as determinants of mortality: the OXCHECK experience. *Public Health Nutr.* **2**, 477–487 (1999).
53. Bernstein, A. M. *et al.* Processed and Unprocessed Red Meat and Risk of Colorectal Cancer: Analysis by Tumor Location and Modification by Time. *PLoS ONE* **10**, e0135959 (2015).
54. Bostick, R. M. *et al.* Sugar, meat, and fat intake, and non-dietary risk factors for colon cancer incidence in Iowa women (United States). *Cancer Causes Control* **5**, 38–52 (1994).
55. Chao, A. Meat Consumption and Risk of Colorectal Cancer. *JAMA* **293**, 172 (2005).
56. Cross, A. J. *et al.* A Large Prospective Study of Meat Consumption and Colorectal Cancer Risk: An Investigation of Potential Mechanisms Underlying this Association. *Cancer Research* **70**, 2406–2414 (2010).
57. English, D. R. *et al.* Red meat, chicken, and fish consumption and risk of colorectal cancer. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev* **13**, 1509–1514 (2004).
58. Etemadi, A. *et al.* Anatomical subsite can modify the association between meat and meat compounds and risk of colorectal adenocarcinoma: Findings from three large US cohorts. *Intl Journal of Cancer* **143**, 2261–2270 (2018).
59. Flood, A. Meat, Fat, and Their Subtypes as Risk Factors for Colorectal Cancer in a Prospective Cohort of Women. *American Journal of Epidemiology* **158**, 59–68 (2003).
60. Gilsing, A. M. J. *et al.* Vegetarianism, low meat consumption and the risk of colorectal cancer in a population based cohort study. *Sci Rep* **5**, 13484 (2015).

61. Islam, Z. *et al.* Meat subtypes and colorectal cancer risk: A pooled analysis of 6 cohort studies in Japan. *Cancer Science* **110**, 3603–3614 (2019).
62. Knuppel, A. *et al.* Meat intake and cancer risk: prospective analyses in UK Biobank. *International Journal of Epidemiology* **49**, 1540–1552 (2020).
63. Larsson, S. C., Rafter, J., Holmberg, L., Bergkvist, L. & Wolk, A. Red meat consumption and risk of cancers of the proximal colon, distal colon and rectum: The Swedish Mammography Cohort. *Intl Journal of Cancer* **113**, 829–834 (2005).
64. Lin, J. Dietary Fat and Fatty Acids and Risk of Colorectal Cancer in Women. *American Journal of Epidemiology* **160**, 1011–1022 (2004).
65. Mehta, S. S. *et al.* A Prospective Analysis of Red and Processed Meat Consumption and Risk of Colorectal Cancer in Women. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention* **29**, 141–150 (2020).
66. Mejborn, H., Møller, S. P., Thygesen, L. C. & Biloft-Jensen, A. Dietary Intake of Red Meat, Processed Meat, and Poultry and Risk of Colorectal Cancer and All-Cause Mortality in the Context of Dietary Guideline Compliance. *Nutrients* **13**, 32 (2020).
67. Norat, T. *et al.* Meat, Fish, and Colorectal Cancer Risk: The European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute* **97**, 906–916 (2005).
68. Ollberding, N. J., Wilkens, L. R., Henderson, B. E., Kolonel, L. N. & Le Marchand, L. Meat consumption, heterocyclic amines and colorectal cancer risk: The Multiethnic Cohort Study. *Intl Journal of Cancer* **131**, (2012).
69. O’Sullivan, D. E. *et al.* Combinations of modifiable lifestyle behaviours in relation to colorectal cancer risk in Alberta’s Tomorrow Project. *Sci Rep* **10**, 20561 (2020).
70. Pietinen, P. *et al.* Diet and risk of colorectal cancer in a cohort of Finnish men. *Cancer Causes and Control* **10**, 387–396 (1999).

71. Bhupathiraju, S. N. *et al.* Caffeinated and caffeine-free beverages and risk of type 2 diabetes. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **97**, 155–166 (2013).
72. Dhingra, R. *et al.* Soft Drink Consumption and Risk of Developing Cardiometabolic Risk Factors and the Metabolic Syndrome in Middle-Aged Adults in the Community. *Circulation* **116**, 480–488 (2007).
73. Eshak, E. S. *et al.* Soft drink, 100% fruit juice, and vegetable juice intakes and risk of diabetes mellitus. *Clinical Nutrition* **32**, 300–308 (2013).
74. Fagherazzi, G. *et al.* Consumption of artificially and sugar-sweetened beverages and incident type 2 diabetes in the Etude Epidemiologique aupres des femmes de la Mutuelle Generale de l'Education Nationale-European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition cohort. *Am J Clin Nutr* **97**, 517–523 (2013).
75. Gardener, H., Moon, Y. P., Rundek, T., Elkind, M. S. V. & Sacco, R. L. Diet Soda and Sugar-Sweetened Soda Consumption in Relation to Incident Diabetes in the Northern Manhattan Study. *Curr Dev Nutr* **2**, nzy008 (2018).
76. Hirahatake, K. M. *et al.* Cumulative intake of artificially sweetened and sugar-sweetened beverages and risk of incident type 2 diabetes in young adults: the Coronary Artery Risk Development In Young Adults (CARDIA) Study. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **110**, 733–741 (2019).
77. Huang, M. *et al.* Artificially sweetened beverages, sugar-sweetened beverages, plain water, and incident diabetes mellitus in postmenopausal women: the prospective Women's Health Initiative observational study. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **106**, 614–622 (2017).
78. Montonen, J., Järvinen, R., Knekt, P., Heliövaara, M. & Reunanen, A. Consumption of Sweetened Beverages and Intakes of Fructose and Glucose Predict Type 2 Diabetes Occurrence. *The Journal of Nutrition* **137**, 1447–1454 (2007).

79. O'Connor, L. *et al.* Prospective associations and population impact of sweet beverage intake and type 2 diabetes, and effects of substitutions with alternative beverages. *Diabetologia* **58**, 1474–1483 (2015).
80. Odegaard, A. O., Koh, W.-P., Arakawa, K., Yu, M. C. & Pereira, M. A. Soft drink and juice consumption and risk of physician-diagnosed incident type 2 diabetes: the Singapore Chinese Health Study. *Am J Epidemiol* **171**, 701–708 (2010).
81. Palmer, J. R. *et al.* Sugar-sweetened beverages and incidence of type 2 diabetes mellitus in African American women. *Arch Intern Med* **168**, 1487–1492 (2008).
82. Pan, A. *et al.* Plain-water intake and risk of type 2 diabetes in young and middle-aged women. *Am J Clin Nutr* **95**, 1454–1460 (2012).
83. Papier, K. *et al.* Consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages and type 2 diabetes incidence in Thai adults: results from an 8-year prospective study. *Nutr Diabetes* **7**, e283 (2017).
84. Paynter, N. P. *et al.* Coffee and Sweetened Beverage Consumption and the Risk of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: The Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study. *American Journal of Epidemiology* **164**, 1075–1084 (2006).
85. Sakurai, M. *et al.* Sugar-sweetened beverage and diet soda consumption and the 7-year risk for type 2 diabetes mellitus in middle-aged Japanese men. *Eur J Nutr* **53**, 251–258 (2014).
86. Siqueira, J. H. *et al.* Consumption of sugar-sweetened soft drinks and risk of metabolic syndrome and its components: results of the ELSA-Brasil study (2008–2010 and 2012–2014). *J Endocrinol Invest* **46**, 159–171 (2022).
87. Torres-Ibarra, L. *et al.* Regular consumption of soft drinks is associated with type 2 diabetes incidence in Mexican adults: findings from a prospective cohort study. *Nutr J* **19**, 126 (2020).

88. Viana Dias, J. P. *et al.* Consumption of sweetened beverages is associated with the incidence of type 2 diabetes in Brazilian adults (CUME project). *Nutr Metab Cardiovasc Dis* **33**, 789–796 (2023).
89. The InterAct consortium. Consumption of sweet beverages and type 2 diabetes incidence in European adults: results from EPIC-InterAct. *Diabetologia* **56**, 1520–1530 (2013).
90. Eshak, E. S. *et al.* Soft drink intake in relation to incident ischemic heart disease, stroke, and stroke subtypes in Japanese men and women: the Japan Public Health Centre-based study cohort I. *Am J Clin Nutr* **96**, 1390–1397 (2012).
91. Warfa, K., Drake, I., Wallström, P., Engström, G. & Sonestedt, E. Association between sucrose intake and acute coronary event risk and effect modification by lifestyle factors: Malmö Diet and Cancer Cohort Study. *Br J Nutr* **116**, 1611–1620 (2016).
92. Pacheco, L. S. *et al.* Sugar-Sweetened Beverage Intake and Cardiovascular Disease Risk in the California Teachers Study. *J Am Heart Assoc* **9**, e014883 (2020).
93. Collin, L. J., Judd, S., Safford, M., Vaccarino, V. & Welsh, J. A. Association of Sugary Beverage Consumption With Mortality Risk in US Adults: A Secondary Analysis of Data From the REGARDS Study. *JAMA Netw Open* **2**, e193121 (2019).
94. Yang, B. *et al.* Added Sugar, Sugar-Sweetened Beverages, and Artificially Sweetened Beverages and Risk of Cardiovascular Disease: Findings from the Women’s Health Initiative and a Network Meta-Analysis of Prospective Studies. *Nutrients* **14**, 4226 (2022).
95. Mullee, A. *et al.* Association Between Soft Drink Consumption and Mortality in 10 European Countries. *JAMA Intern Med* **179**, 1479–1490 (2019).
96. Keller, A. *et al.* Substitution of sugar-sweetened beverages for other beverages and the risk of developing coronary heart disease: Results from the Harvard Pooling Project of Diet and Coronary Disease. *Prev Med* **131**, 105970 (2020).

97. Pacheco, L. S. *et al.* Sugar- or artificially-sweetened beverage consumption, physical activity, and risk of cardiovascular disease in US adults. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.04.17.23288711> (2023).
98. Laake, I. *et al.* A prospective study of intake of *trans*-fatty acids from ruminant fat, partially hydrogenated vegetable oils, and marine oils and mortality from CVD. *Br J Nutr* **108**, 743–754 (2012).
99. Li, Y. *et al.* Saturated Fats Compared With Unsaturated Fats and Sources of Carbohydrates in Relation to Risk of Coronary Heart Disease. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology* **66**, 1538–1548 (2015).
100. Oomen, C. M. *et al.* Association between trans fatty acid intake and 10-year risk of coronary heart disease in the Zutphen Elderly Study: a prospective population-based study. *The Lancet* **357**, 746–751 (2001).
101. Pietinen, P. *et al.* Intake of Fatty Acids and Risk of Coronary Heart Disease in a Cohort of Finnish Men: The Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study. *American Journal of Epidemiology* **145**, 876–887 (1997).
102. Virtanen, J. K., Mursu, J., Tuomainen, T.-P. & Voutilainen, S. Dietary Fatty Acids and Risk of Coronary Heart Disease in Men: The Kuopio Ischemic Heart Disease Risk Factor Study. *ATVB* **34**, 2679–2687 (2014).
103. Xu, J. *et al.* Dietary fat intake and risk of coronary heart disease: the Strong Heart Study. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* **84**, 894–902 (2006).
104. Bouvard, V. *et al.* Carcinogenicity of consumption of red and processed meat. *Lancet Oncol* **16**, 1599–1600 (2015).

105. Stern, M. C. *et al.* Genome-Wide Gene-Environment Interaction Analyses to Understand the Relationship between Red Meat and Processed Meat Intake and Colorectal Cancer Risk. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev* **33**, 400–410 (2024).
106. WHO. WHO manual on sugar-sweetened beverage taxation policies to promote healthy diets. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2022. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.
107. Andreyeva, T., Marple, K., Marinello, S., Moore, T. E. & Powell, L. M. Outcomes Following Taxation of Sugar-Sweetened Beverages: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *JAMA Netw Open* **5**, e2215276 (2022).
108. World Health Organization. Guideline: Sugar intake for adults and children (WHO Department of Nutrition for Health and Development (NHD)). (2015).
109. U.S. Department of Agriculture and U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. Dietary Guidelines for Americans, 2020-2025. 9th Edition. (2020).
110. *Countdown to 2023: WHO 5-Year Milestone Report on Global Trans Fat Elimination 2023*. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2024. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.
111. Freedman, L. S., Schatzkin, A., Midthune, D. & Kipnis, V. Dealing With Dietary Measurement Error in Nutritional Cohort Studies. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute* **103**, 1086–1092 (2011).
112. Kipnis, V. *et al.* Effect of measurement error on energy-adjustment models in nutritional epidemiology. *Am J Epidemiol* **146**, 842–855 (1997).
113. Dahm, C. C. Correcting measurement error in dietary exposure assessments: no piece of cake. *Am J Clin Nutr* **112**, 11–12 (2020).
114. McCullough, L. E. & Byrd, D. A. Total Energy Intake: Implications for Epidemiologic Analyses. *Am J Epidemiol* **192**, 1801–1805 (2023).

115. Willett, W. C., Howe, G. R. & Kushi, L. H. Adjustment for total energy intake in epidemiologic studies. *Am J Clin Nutr* **65**, 1220S-1228S; discussion 1229S-1231S (1997).
116. Day, N. E. *et al.* Correlated measurement error--implications for nutritional epidemiology. *Int J Epidemiol* **33**, 1373–1381 (2004).
117. GBD 2021 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators. Global incidence, prevalence, years lived with disability (YLDs), disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs), and healthy life expectancy (HALE) for 371 diseases and injuries in 204 countries and territories and 811 subnational locations, 1990-2021: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *Lancet* **403**, 2133–2161 (2024).
118. Kassem, H. *et al.* Investigation and Assessment of AI's Role in Nutrition-An Updated Narrative Review of the Evidence. *Nutrients* **17**, 190 (2025).
119. Zheng, J., Wang, J., Shen, J. & An, R. Artificial Intelligence Applications to Measure Food and Nutrient Intakes: Scoping Review. *J Med Internet Res* **26**, e54557 (2024).
120. Lo, F. P.-W. *et al.* AI-enabled wearable cameras for assisting dietary assessment in African populations. *npj Digit. Med.* **7**, 356 (2024).
121. Burgess, S., Foley, C. N., Allara, E., Staley, J. R. & Howson, J. M. M. A robust and efficient method for Mendelian randomization with hundreds of genetic variants. *Nat Commun* **11**, 376 (2020).
122. Lai, W., Li, G., Peng, D., Li, N. & Wang, W. Mendelian randomization study reveals the relationship between dietary factors and respiratory diseases. *Sci Rep* **13**, 22601 (2023).
123. Lescinsky, H. *et al.* Health effects associated with consumption of unprocessed red meat: a Burden of Proof study. *Nat Med* **28**, 2075–2082 (2022).
124. Stanaway, J. D. *et al.* Health effects associated with vegetable consumption: a Burden of Proof study. *Nat Med* **28**, 2066–2074 (2022).

125. Page, M. J. *et al.* The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* n71 (2021) doi:10.1136/bmj.n71.
126. Stevens, G. A. *et al.* Guidelines for Accurate and Transparent Health Estimates Reporting: the GATHER statement. *The Lancet* **388**, e19–e23 (2016).
127. Pan, A. *et al.* Red meat consumption and mortality: results from 2 prospective cohort studies. *Arch Intern Med* **172**, 555–563 (2012).
128. Zhang, Y.-B., Jiang, Y.-W., Chen, J.-X., Xia, P.-F. & Pan, A. Association of Consumption of Sugar-Sweetened Beverages or Artificially Sweetened Beverages with Mortality: A Systematic Review and Dose–Response Meta-Analysis of Prospective Cohort Studies. *Advances in Nutrition* **12**, 374–383 (2021).
129. de Souza, R. J. *et al.* Intake of saturated and trans unsaturated fatty acids and risk of all cause mortality, cardiovascular disease, and type 2 diabetes: systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *BMJ* **351**, h3978 (2015).
130. Zheng, P., Barber, R., Sorensen, R. J. D., Murray, C. J. L. & Aravkin, A. Y. Trimmed Constrained Mixed Effects Models: Formulations and Algorithms. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* **30**, 544–556 (2021).

Methods

Overview

This study used the burden of proof methodology to examine the association between processed meat, SSB, and TFA consumption and selected health outcomes. The burden of proof methodology comprises six main steps²⁵: searching for and extracting data from published studies using a standardized approach, estimating the relationship between dietary exposure and relative risk of disease outcome, testing and adjusting for systematic bias arising from differences in known study-design characteristics, quantifying remaining between-study heterogeneity, assessing the evidence for potential publication or reporting bias, and ultimately estimating the burden of proof risk function (BPRF), which is defined as the 5th percentile relative risk curve – inclusive of between-study heterogeneity – that is closest to the null for harmful risks. In the burden of proof methodology, we estimate both the mean risk of the outcome occurring at each level of exposure relative to the risk at the theoretical minimum exposure level (TMREL) and the burden of proof risk function, which provides a conservative interpretation of the risk of a given disease outcome occurring that we summarize by calculating the average BPRF across the 15th to 85th percentiles of exposure observed in the data. Because they represent the data-dense part of the exposure range, the 15th to 85th percentiles are the exposure levels for which the risk curve is most relevant and avoids emphasis on extreme values for our conservatively estimated conservative BPRF metrics. In the burden of proof capstone paper²⁵, Zheng et al tested and found that the correlation between risk-outcome score values derived from alternative ranges of exposure, such as the 10th and 90th percentiles and the 5th and 95th percentiles, and risk-outcome score derived using the 15th and 85th percentiles across 180 risk–outcome pairs was very strong (~0.98). The burden of proof approach allows for a standardized methodology to be applied across multiple risk factors which is relevant for policy or research prioritization. This approach was previously applied to evaluate the association between other dietary exposures, specifically vegetable and red meat consumption, and various health outcomes^{123,124}.

The burden of proof meta-regression methods developed by Zheng and colleagues²⁵ – offers three main advantages over previous risk factor analyses to support policy makers, public health professionals, and individuals interested in minimizing health risk by providing more precisely derived relative risk (RR) estimates, additional information about the shapes of the risk-outcome relationships, and a framework to better capture the consistency of the underlying evidence and make comparisons across risk-outcome pairs. First, to improve rigor and accuracy of RR estimates, burden of proof methods systematically adjust for bias covariates representing known heterogeneity in input study design characteristics, correct for differences in exposure range across input studies, and employ a robust likelihood-based method to detect and trim data outliers. Second, the meta-regression uses a spline ensemble to flexibly model non-linear relationships, allowing the data to determine the shape of the risk-outcome relationship. This avoids conventional assumptions of log-linearity that may amplify risk at higher exposure levels and obscure critical details at lower levels in the presence of a strong threshold effect. Information about the shape of the relationship can be used to inform cost/benefit analyses and policy determinations, including those targeting specific levels of exposure

reduction or providing intake guidelines. Third – complementing RR estimates – burden of proof methods further formally quantify between-study heterogeneity that remains after adjusting for covariates representing known variation across input study characteristics, and incorporate this quantity directly into uncertainty estimates. These are used to derive the BPRF. The BPRF for a given risk-outcome pair is used to compute the risk-outcome score, which is defined as the signed value of the log BPRF, averaged across the 15th to 85th percentiles of exposure (i.e., the range of most likely exposure levels). The risk-outcome score is mapped onto a star-rating system comprising five levels of risk-outcome relationships, with more stars representing a stronger association and/or more consistent evidence. By providing a systematic method to capture the strength or consistency of the input evidence and generate a conservative measure of association, BPRF metrics highlight those risk-outcome relationships most likely to be accurate and reliable and allow for comparisons to other dietary (or non-dietary) risks to inform broader public health or research foci (for instance, low star ratings combining with high exposure or disease prevalence suggest a need for more research).

We estimated relative risks and BPRF and risk-outcome scores for each risk-outcome pair. Due to reporting inconsistencies across the input data, our pooled relative risk estimates are not location-, sex-, or age-specific. We evaluated the association between processed meat, SSB, and TFA consumption and selected chronic diseases among adults. We excluded those studies that evaluated the health effects of these dietary risk factors on adolescents and children.

We followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines through all stages of this study¹²⁵ (**Supplementary Table 1 and Supplementary Table 2**). This study complies with the Guidelines on Accurate and Transparent Health Estimates Reporting (GATHER) recommendations¹²⁶ (**Supplementary Table 3**). The study was approved by the University of Washington Institutional Review Board (Study no. 9060). The systematic review approach for processed meat was registered at PROSPERO (PROSPERO ID = CRD42023457810), and the systematic review approach for sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs) and trans-fat was also registered at PROSPERO (PROSPERO ID = CRD42023495735).

Systematic Review

We conducted systematic reviews to identify studies that present relative measures of association (for example, relative risks [RRs], odds ratios [ORs], or hazard ratios [HRs]) between the dietary exposure of interest and the selected health outcome. Our search strategy had two stages. The first stage was to identify the most recent existing meta-analysis/systematic review for each risk-outcome pair that met the inclusion criteria described below. The first reviewer screened the citations provided by the identified meta-analysis, and the second reviewer checked 100% of the studies excluded by the first reviewer. In the second stage, separate search strings were developed to identify sources in PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science published after the period covered in the most recent PRISMA-compliant meta-analysis identified for each risk-outcome pair of interest. In both stages of the screening, two reviewers are required to exclude a study. Whenever there was a discrepancy happened, discussion and consultation was made with a senior personnel. The first reviewer extracted the data using the data extraction template. The second reviewer checked the

correctness and completeness of the extracted data for all the studies. A detailed description of the search strings and search strategy is presented in the **Supplementary Appendix**.

Our systematic review included prospective cohort, nested case-control, and case-cohort studies that included participants aged 25 or older on average at the time of entry into the cohort. This restriction was applied because findings from this study will be used to calculate estimates of disease burden attributable to these risk factors for future iterations of GBD, which restricts dietary risk-attributable burden estimation adults 25 or older. However, our search did not find any cohort studies conducted among younger adults (under 25 years). Prospective cohort studies entirely based on children, adolescents, pregnant women, or adults younger than 25 on average at the time of entry into the cohort were therefore excluded. The method of assessing dietary intake was required to be either a quantitative 24-hr recall, weight for record, food diary, or food frequency questionnaire. Cross-sectional studies, intervention studies, and cohort studies that did not involve a quantitative assessment of dietary intake were excluded. The sample included in the final analysis had to be free of the outcomes of interest (IHD, type 2 diabetes, colorectal cancer) at the time of entry into the cohort.

Other inclusionary criteria were the use of suitable exposure and outcome definitions, and the reporting of some measure of uncertainty (for example, sample size, standard error, or CIs) and RR (or related measure) for which the exposed and unexposed groups were defined. Where multiple studies provided RR estimates derived from the same cohort, we included only the study that captured the largest sample or the longest follow-up time so as not to include duplicate data. For each study, one reviewer manually extracted data on study name, location, design, population (age, sex, race and sample size), duration of follow-up, exposure definition, exposure assessment method, exposure categories, outcome definition, outcome ascertainment method, and covariates included in the statistical analysis of the study. A second reviewer inspected the extracted data and checked with the first reviewer if there was a discrepancy between the extracted data and what was reported in the paper. All included studies published the data required by our inclusionary criteria, and no unpublished data were obtained for this analysis. For each exposure category, we also collected data on the range of exposure, number of participants, number of events, and the risk estimate and its corresponding uncertainty. The template for the data collection form is provided in **Supplementary Table 4**. The details of the systematic review for each risk-outcome pair are described below.

Processed meat: In the processed meat systematic review, we defined processed meat as any meat preserved by smoking, curing, salting, or addition of chemical preservatives. This aligns with GBD 2021⁵. We defined our outcome as either incidence of, or mortality from, the specified health outcome, excluding studies that included other or non-specific outcome definitions (for example, unspecified cardiovascular disease). As described above, we used search strings to identify the most recent PRISMA-compliant meta-analyses that examined associations between processed meat consumption and type 2 diabetes, IHD, or colorectal cancer. For studies investigating the relationship between processed meat consumption and type 2 diabetes, we searched from June 1, 2022 (the last date of the identified meta-analysis) through September 1, 2023. For studies examining processed meat consumption and IHD, we searched from June 5, 2021 (the last date of the identified meta-analysis) through August 15, 2023. For studies examining processed meat and colorectal cancer, we searched from February 01, 2023 (the last date of the identified meta-analysis) through September

1, 2023. We also searched the Global Health Data Exchange (GHDx) databases. When studies reported effect sizes for colon cancer and rectum cancer separately, we included both effect sizes. However, if studies reported colorectal cancer in addition to effect sizes for colon cancer and rectum cancer, we chose the effect size reported for colorectal cancer.

We standardized the exposure unit to grams (g) of consumption per day. For studies reporting the consumption in servings of processed meat with no other corresponding information about the serving size (13 of 44 studies), we assumed a serving size of 45g per day.

This assumption was based on the study by Pan A et al., 2012¹²⁷. For studies that reported mean consumption rather than ranges of consumption, we used the midpoint between means as the cutoff for intake intervals. For undefined lower bounds, we assumed a consumption level of 0 g per day. For undefined upper bounds when the mean and standard deviation values were not available, we applied the range from the cohort's most adjacent quartile or tertile to estimate the upper bound of consumption, specific to each study cohort. For studies that reported the frequency of consumption per day, week, or month without specifying the serving size, we assumed that the frequency of consumption equated to the number of servings. When the units were presented as grams per kcal, we used the mean energy intake to find absolute consumption (not relative to energy) in grams. If energy intake was not reported, we assumed 2000 kcal as an average energy intake for conversion.

Sugar-sweetened beverages: In this systematic review, we defined SSB exposure as consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages including carbonated beverages, sodas, energy drinks, and fruit drinks, but excluding 100% fruit and vegetable juices. This aligns with GBD⁵. We examined the association of SSB consumption with type 2 diabetes and IHD. We used search strings to identify the most recent PRISMA-compliant meta-analyses that examined these associations. We also conducted an updated search of studies examining SSB consumption and type 2 diabetes by searching in PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science from the last date of the identified meta-analysis (December 1, 2022) to December 20, 2023. Similarly, for the updated search of SSB and IHD, we searched the three databases over the period from the last date of the identified meta-analysis (December 1, 2022) to December 20, 2023. A detailed description of the search strings and search strategy is reported in the **Supplementary Appendix**. For studies reporting the consumption in servings of SSBs without any other corresponding information about the serving size (8/27 studies), we assumed that a serving size is approximately equivalent to 12 ounces (i.e., the most commonly used serving size for SSB)¹²⁸, which is approximately 341 grams. For studies that reported mean consumption rather than ranges of consumption, we used the midpoint between means as the cutoff for intake intervals. For undefined lower bounds, we assumed a consumption level of 0 g per day. For undefined upper bounds when the mean and standard deviation values were not available, we applied the range from the cohort's most adjacent quartile or tertile to estimate the upper bound of consumption, specific to each study cohort. For studies that reported the frequency of consumption per day, week, or month without specifying the serving size, we assumed that the frequency of consumption equated to the number of servings. When the units were presented as grams per kcal, we used the mean energy intake to find total consumption in grams. If energy was not reported, we assumed 2000 kcal as an average energy intake for conversion.

Trans fat: TFA exposure is defined as consumption (in percent of daily energy intake) of trans fats, primarily those that are industrially produced. The outcome of interest for this systematic review was IHD. The identified meta-analysis was a study conducted by de Souza et al.²⁷ The additional updated search covered the period from December 1, 2015 to December 18, 2023. We included only prospective cohort studies and nested case-control studies that examined the relationship of total TFA and industrially produced TFA consumption on IHD. For those studies examining total TFA consumption, we assumed the major contributor to be industrially produced TFAs. We excluded studies that examined the effect of TFAs from ruminant-only sources on IHD because our focus in this systematic review is industrially produced trans fats. Additionally, we excluded studies when the outcome was not specifically IHD (i.e., cardiovascular events). When studies reported measures of association for total IHD events, as well as for non-fatal and fatal IHD events, we used the effect measures based on total IHD events for our main analysis. Intake of TFAs was expressed in % per daily energy intake. For studies which did not report % of energy intake, we converted results into % per daily energy intake using reported intake of TFAs and energy intake. If energy intake was not reported, we assumed 2000 kcal for calculating the % per daily energy intake.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses conducted in this study are described in detail below. We used the burden of proof analytical framework, which includes estimation of the shape of the relationships between the risk and the outcome, testing and adjusting for the bias covariates, quantifying between-studies heterogeneities, evaluating publication bias, and estimating the burden of proof function. No statistical method was used to predetermine the sample size. As all data used in this meta-analysis were from observational studies, no experiments were conducted, and no randomization or blinding took place.

Estimating the risk-outcome relationship

For each risk–outcome pair, we modeled relative risk of the disease outcome occurring as a function of exposure to the risk factor using burden of proof methods, a suite of Bayesian meta-regression tools, which are detailed elsewhere¹³⁰. Burden of proof methods offer several valuable features for evaluating relative risk curves and assessing the robustness of evidence available to support the analyzed risk–outcome associations. These features include, among others: (1) the ability to model non-linear relationships using splines, provided in the analysis framework with automated knot selection and shape constraints; (2) systematic incorporation of covariates related to differences among input study design characteristics, allowing for the mitigation of potential biases; (3) methods to quantify remaining between-study heterogeneity and incorporate it into uncertainty, creating the basis for a single measure that provides a conservative estimate of the magnitude of the risk–outcome association and the strength of the supporting evidence; (4) a mechanism to adjust the parameter for between-study variability to account for the effects of limited data; and (5) a means to evaluate the presence of publication or reporting bias.

In this study, we first modeled the association of each risk–outcome pair with no constraints to assess the nature of the association. Then we applied a constraint based on the shape of the risk curve derived from this initial model. For the analyses involving processed meat and SSBs, we applied a quadratic spline model with an increasing shape constraint (risk increasing with increasing exposure) for each of the outcomes. For the TFA analysis, we applied a cubic spline model with an increasing shape constraint.

Testing and adjusting for biases across input study designs and characteristics

For each study reporting an effect size for the association between consumption and the selected health outcomes, we extracted information about aspects of study design that could potentially bias the reported effect size and coded this information to generate study-level covariates. These study-level covariates included: length of follow-up period (≤ 10 years and > 10 years), precision of the exposure and outcome definitions, study design (i.e., RCT or prospective cohort study), reported measure of association (RRs or ORs), outcome measures (incidence or mortality), number of exposure measurements (single or repeat), method by which outcomes were ascertained (administrative records, self-reports, biomarkers, or physician diagnosis), and level of adjustment for relevant confounders (e.g., age, sex, smoking, education, income, calorie intake, BMI, physical activity, alcohol intake, saturated fat intake, and other dietary factors). We adjusted for these covariates in our meta-regression if they significantly biased our estimated RR function. **See Supplementary Table 7-9** for results from our assessment of study quality for all included studies.

Quantifying remaining between-study heterogeneity

After using the aforementioned study-level covariates to account for known differences in study design characteristics, we used a linear mixed-effects model to quantify the remaining unexplained between-study heterogeneity, as captured by gamma (γ). The remaining between-study heterogeneity captured by γ contributes to the overall assessment of effect size and evidence strength as reflected in the BPRF. The details of the methods for quantifying between-study heterogeneity are described elsewhere²⁵. Uncertainty intervals for estimated relative risks are reported in two forms: 1) exclusive of γ , derived without fully accounting for between-study heterogeneity (thus aligned with conventional uncertainty estimates typically reported in

traditional meta-analyses), and 2) inclusive of γ , which better reflects the degree of consistency across the underlying evidence. In this study, we present relative risk values with uncertainty intervals that include γ unless otherwise specified.

Evaluating the potential for publication and reporting bias

We examined the presence of publication and reporting bias using Egger's regression and by visually inspecting funnel plots. A significant relationship between effect size and standard error suggests bias or methodological differences across studies. Positive Egger's regression results signal potential publication/reporting bias. Although we tested for and reported our findings regarding publication/reporting bias, we followed standard guidelines and did not adjust our risk assessment based on these results.

Estimating the theoretical minimum risk exposure level

The theoretical minimum risk exposure level (TMREL) refers to the exposure level that, among all the theoretically possible values at the population level, minimizes the risk of all associated outcomes combined. For harmful exposures that can theoretically be eliminated, the TMREL is usually set at zero. In our analysis, we applied a TMREL of zero for processed meat, SSBs and TFA.

Estimating the burden of proof risk function (BPRF)

We estimated the BPRF as the function that corresponds to the 5th percentile (for harmful risk factors) of the RR curve, inclusive of γ , that is closest to the null. The BPRF represents a conservative estimate of the risk-outcome association that is consistent with the available data after incorporating between-study heterogeneity. The further the BPRF is from the null, the stronger the estimated association is, both in terms of effect size and/or strength of supporting evidence. We then estimated the risk-outcome score as the mean value of the log-BPRF averaged over the 15th and 85th percentiles of the distribution of exposure observed in the relevant input studies. The risk-outcome score provides a single summary metric of the BPRF that is comparable across both protective and harmful effects²⁵. A higher positive risk-outcome score corresponds to a stronger association, supported by more consistent evidence. We translated the risk-outcome score for each risk-outcome pair into a star rating ranging from one to five stars to reflect our conservative estimate of association strength. Increasing stars – in the case of harmful risk factors – represent increasing evidence of health risk with increased levels of exposure to the risk factor (averaged across the evidence-dense range of exposure levels observed), relative to no exposure. Specifically, the burden of proof framework defines star rating categories as 0% increased risk for one star, 0–15% for two stars, >15–50% for three stars, >50–85% for four stars, and over 85% increased risk for five stars.

Sensitivity analyses

For each risk–outcome pair, we conducted sensitivity analyses that compared the relative risk curves generated with and without trimming the 10% least coherent data points (**Supplemental Results**).

Reporting summary

Further information on research design is available in the Nature Research Reporting Summary linked to this article.

Data availability statement

The findings of this study were based on data from public repositories and published literature, with systematic searches conducted in PubMed (<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>), Embase (<https://www.embase.com>), and Web of Science (<https://www.webofscience.com>) using the search strings provided in the supplementary information. The estimates produced in this study are accessible via the Burden of Proof visualization tool (<https://preview.healthdata.org/burden-of-proof/>). The relevant studies were identified through a systematic literature review and citations for all input studies are listed in the main text as references ²⁷⁻¹⁰³. Study characteristics for all input data used in the analyses are also provided in **Supplementary Table 5**. The template for the data collection form is provided in **Supplementary Table 4**.

Code Availability statement

This study was a secondary analysis of existing data obtained through systematic reviews using meta-analytic methods. The study did not involve primary data collection, randomization, blinding, or determination of sample size. Analyses were carried out using R version 4.0.5, and Python version 3.10.9. All codes used for data processing (https://github.com/ihmeuw-msca/burden-of-proof/tree/main/risks/processed_foods) and to run the Burden of Proof model (<https://github.com/ihmeuw-msca/bopforge>) are publicly available online.

Methods-only references

124. Zheng, P. *et al.* The Burden of Proof studies: assessing the evidence of risk. *Nat Med* **28**, 2038–2044 (2022).
125. Lescinsky, H. *et al.* Health effects associated with consumption of unprocessed red meat: a Burden of Proof study. *Nat Med* **28**, 2075–2082 (2022).
126. Stanaway, J. D. *et al.* Health effects associated with vegetable consumption: a Burden of Proof study. *Nat Med* **28**, 2066–2074 (2022).

127. Page, M. J. *et al.* The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* n71 (2021) doi:10.1136/bmj.n71.
128. Stevens, G. A. *et al.* Guidelines for Accurate and Transparent Health Estimates Reporting: the GATHER statement. *The Lancet* **388**, e19–e23 (2016).
129. Pan, A. *et al.* Red meat consumption and mortality: results from 2 prospective cohort studies. *Arch Intern Med* **172**, 555–563 (2012).
130. Zhang, Y.-B., Jiang, Y.-W., Chen, J.-X., Xia, P.-F. & Pan, A. Association of Consumption of Sugar-Sweetened Beverages or Artificially Sweetened Beverages with Mortality: A Systematic Review and Dose–Response Meta-Analysis of Prospective Cohort Studies. *Advances in Nutrition* **12**, 374–383 (2021).
131. de Souza, R. J. *et al.* Intake of saturated and trans unsaturated fatty acids and risk of all cause mortality, cardiovascular disease, and type 2 diabetes: systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *BMJ* **351**, h3978 (2015).
132. Zheng, P., Barber, R., Sorensen, R. J. D., Murray, C. J. L. & Aravkin, A. Y. Trimmed Constrained Mixed Effects Models: Formulations and Algorithms. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* **30**, 544–556 (2021).

Supplementary Information: supplementary methods, data sources, and results for “Health effects associated with consumption of processed meat, sugar-sweetened beverages, and trans fatty acids: a Burden of Proof study”

This appendix provides detailed information on input data sources and presents supplementary results—particularly sensitivity analysis results—for “Health effects associated with processed meat, sugar-sweetened beverages, and trans fatty acid consumption: a Burden of Proof study.”

Contents

Section 1: Data source identification and assessment	53
Section 1.1: Literature identification and screening.....	53
Section 1.2: Assessing data source eligibility	63
Section 2. PRISMA checklists	65
Supplementary Table 1. PRISMA 2020 checklist.....	65
Supplementary Table 2. PRISMA 2020 abstract checklist	67
Section 3. GATHER checklists	68
Supplementary Table 3. GATHER checklist	68
Section 4: Data source extraction	68
Supplementary Table 4. Causal criteria extraction template.....	68
Section 5: Study characteristics.....	72
Supplementary Table 5. Studies characteristics.....	72
Section 6: Study quality and risk of bias assessment	76
Supplementary Table 6: Bias covariates definitions.....	76
Supplementary Table 7. Quantified bias covariates related to study design, follow-up, exposure and outcome assessment	78
Supplementary Table 8. Quantified bias covariates of major non-dietary intake confounders	81
Supplementary Table 9. Quantified bias covariates for major dietary confounders	83
Section 7: Results from individual studies	85
Supplementary Table 10. Summary results from input studies	85
Section 8. Details on statistical methods	91
Supplementary Table 11. MR-BRT splines and prior specifications	91

Supplementary Table 12. Bias covariates and estimated parameters	92
Section 9: Risk curve details.....	93
Supplementary Table 13. Relative risks of type 2 diabetes and colorectal cancer across exposure range for every 50g/day increased consumption of processed meat derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 1,3)	93
Supplementary Table 14. Relative risks of IHD across exposure range of processed meat derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 2)	93
Supplementary Table 15. Relative risks of type 2 diabetes and IHD across exposure range for every 250g/day increased consumption of SSB derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 4-5)	93
Supplementary Table 16. Relative risks of IHD across exposure range for every percent increased energy consumption of trans fat derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 6).....	94
Section 10: Sensitivity results.....	95
Supplementary Table 17: Non-trimming: Strength of the evidence for the relationship between processed meat, SSBs and TFAs consumption and health outcomes.....	95

Section 1: Data source identification and assessment

The data used for this study can be categorized into the following types: prospective cohort, nested case-control and case-cohort.

Section 1.1: Literature identification and screening

We conducted literature searches to obtain input data from prospective studies evaluating the relationship between processed meat consumption and type 2 diabetes, ischemic heart disease (IHD) and colorectal cancer. Similarly, we conducted a literature search of prospective cohort studies, nested case-control and case-cohort studies to examine the association of sugar sweetened beverages with type 2 diabetes and IHD. We examined the association between trans-fatty acids consumption and IHD using prospective cohort studies, nested case-control and case-cohort studies. Our search strategy had two stages. First, a search string was developed to identify the most recent PRISMA-compliant meta-analyses which examined the effect of each dietary risk factor of interest and each specific health outcome of interest. Then the citations of the selected meta-analysis were searched. The first reviewer screened the citations provided by the identified meta-analysis, and the second reviewer checked 100% of the studies excluded by the first reviewer. In the second stage, separate search strings were developed to identify sources in PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science published after the period covered in the most recent PRISMA-compliant meta-analysis identified for each risk-outcome pair of interest. In both stages of the screening, two reviewers are required to exclude a study. Whenever there was a discrepancy happened, discussion and consultation was made with a senior personnel. The first reviewer extracted the data using the data extraction template. The second reviewer checked the correctness and completeness of the extracted data for all the studies. We also searched the global health data exchange (GHDx) databases. The systematic review approach for processed meat was registered at PROSPERO (PROSPERO ID = CRD42023457810), and the systematic review approach for sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs) and trans-fat was also registered at PROSPERO (PROSPERO ID = CRD42023495735).

1. Processed Meat Systematic Review

a. Processed Meat and Type 2 Diabetes

We developed a PubMed search string to identify the most recent PRISMA complaint meta-analysis on processed meat consumption and type 2 diabetes. The meta-analysis identified that fulfills our criteria of exposure definition (processed meat), outcome definition (Type 2 diabetes). The identified PRISMA complaint meta-analysis was Shi et al 2023. A total of 159 citations of this meta-analysis were identified and screened. From this meta-analysis, we included a total of 14 studies in the final analysis. The last date this meta-analysis covered was June 30, 2022.

Search strings to identify the meta-analysis	Identified meta-analysis
("processed meat*" [tiab] OR "cured meat*" [tiab] OR "deli meat*" [tiab] OR	Shi W, Huang X, Schooling CM, Zhao JV. Red meat consumption, cardiovascular diseases, and

<p>"packaged meat*" [tiab] OR "preserved meat*" [tiab] OR "smoked meat*" [tiab] OR "sausages*" [tiab] OR "hot dogs*" [tiab] OR "bacon*" [tiab] OR "ham*" [tiab] OR "salami*" [tiab] OR "pepperoni*" [tiab] OR "jerky*" [tiab] OR "lunch meat*" [tiab] OR "cold cuts*" [tiab] AND ("Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2" [Mesh] OR "diabetes mellitus type 2" [Title/Abstract] OR "Gestational diabetes" OR "diabetes type 2" [Title/Abstract] OR "type 2 diabetes mellitus" [Title/Abstract] OR "type 2 diabetes" [Title/Abstract] OR "non-insulin dependent diabetes" [Title/Abstract] OR "adult-onset diabetes" [Title/Abstract])) AND ("Systematic Review" [Publication Type] OR "systematic review" [Title/Abstract] OR "Meta-Analysis" [Publication Type] OR "meta-analysis" [Title/Abstract])</p>	<p>diabetes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Eur Heart J. 2023 Jul 21;44(28):2626-2635. doi: 10.1093/eurheartj/ehad336. PMID: 37264855.</p>
---	--

Another search string was developed to identify sources published after the period covered in Shi et al 2023. PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science and searched on September 1, 2023. The searches from the three databases returned 33 total hits, of which only two studies ultimately extracted and included in the model. The exclusion reasons by source count were reported in the PRISMA diagram (**Extended Data Figure 1**). We also searched the global health data exchange database to identify studies not caught from the searching of citation of the selected meta-analysis and the three databases.

Search strings for updated search on Processed Meat and Type 2 Diabetes

a. Pubmed

("processed meat*" [tiab] OR ("processed*meat*" [tiab] OR "cured meat*" [tiab] OR "deli meat*" [tiab] OR "packaged meat*" [tiab] OR "preserved meat*" [tiab] OR "smoked meat*" [tiab] OR "sausage*" [tiab] OR "hot dog*" [tiab] OR "bacon*" [tiab] OR "ham" [tiab] OR "hams" [tiab] OR "salami*" [tiab] OR "pepperoni*" [tiab] OR "jerk*" [tiab] OR "lunch meat*" [tiab] OR "cold cut*" [tiab]) AND ("Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2" [Mesh] OR "diabetes mellitus type 2" [tiab] OR "diabetes mellitus type II" [tiab] OR "diabetes type 2" [tiab] OR "diabetes type II" [tiab] OR "type 2 diabetes mellitus" [tiab] OR "type II diabetes mellitus" [tiab] OR "type 2 diabetes" [tiab] OR "type II diabetes" [tiab] OR "non-insulin dependent diabetes" [tiab] OR "adult-onset diabetes" [tiab])) AND ("cohort" [tiab] OR "prospective*study" [tiab] OR "follow-up" [tiab] OR "longitudinal" [tiab] OR "nested case-control" [tiab] OR "case-cohort" [tiab]) AND (("2022/06/01"[Date - Publication] : "2023/09/01"[Date - Publication])) NOT (Meta-Analysis [Publication Type] OR Systematic Review [Publication Type])

b. Embase

('processed meat*':ti,ab OR processed*meat*':ti,ab OR 'cured meat*':ti,ab OR 'deli meat*':ti,ab OR 'packaged meat*':ti,ab OR 'preserved meat*':ti,ab OR 'smoked meat*':ti,ab OR 'sausage*':ti,ab OR 'hot dog*':ti,ab OR 'bacon*':ti,ab OR 'ham':ti,ab OR 'hams':ti,ab OR 'salami*':ti,ab OR 'pepperoni*':ti,ab OR 'jerk*':ti,ab OR 'lunch meat*':ti,ab OR 'cold cut*':ti,ab) AND ('diabetes mellitus, type 2'/exp OR 'diabetes mellitus type 2':ti,ab OR 'diabetes mellitus type ii':ti,ab OR 'diabetes type 2':ti,ab OR 'diabetes type ii':ti,ab OR 'type 2 diabetes mellitus':ti,ab OR 'type ii diabetes mellitus':ti,ab OR

'type 2 diabetes':ti,ab OR 'type ii diabetes':ti,ab OR 'non-insulin dependent diabetes':ti,ab OR 'adult-onset diabetes':ti,ab) AND (cohort*:ti,ab OR prospective*study:ti,ab OR 'follow up':ti,ab OR longitudinal:ti,ab OR 'nested case-control':ti,ab OR 'case-cohort':ti,ab) NOT ('Meta-Analysis' OR 'Systematic Review') AND [2022-2023]/py AND [embase]/lim NOT [medline]/lim

c. Web of Science

TS = (("processed meat*" OR processed*meat* OR "cured meat*" OR "deli meat*" OR "packaged meat*" OR "preserved meat*" OR "smoked meat*" OR sausage* OR "hot dog*" OR bacon* OR ham OR hams OR salami* OR pepperoni* OR jerk* OR "lunch meat*" OR "cold cut*") AND ("Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2" OR "diabetes mellitus type 2" OR "diabetes mellitus type II" OR "diabetes type 2" OR "diabetes type II" OR "type 2 diabetes mellitus" OR "type II diabetes mellitus" OR "type 2 diabetes" OR "type II diabetes" OR "non-insulin dependent diabetes" OR "adult-onset diabetes") AND (cohort OR prospective*study OR follow-up OR longitudinal OR "nested case-control" OR "case cohort") NOT ("Meta-Analysis" OR "Systematic Review")) AND DOP= (2022-06-01/2023-09-08)

b. Processed meat and ischemic heart diseases

We developed PubMed search strings to identify the most recent PRISMA complaint meta-analysis on processed meat consumption and IHD. The most recent PRISMA complaint meta-analysis that met our definition of exposure (i.e. processed meat) and outcome (i.e., Ischemic heart diseases) was a study published by Papier et al in 2023. From this study meta-analysis, we identified 54 citations, with 11 studies meeting the inclusion criteria to be included in the final analysis.

Search strings to identify the meta-analysis	Identified meta-analysis
("processed meat*" [tiab] OR "cured meat*" [tiab] OR "deli meat*" [tiab] OR "packaged meat*" [tiab] OR "preserved meat*" [tiab] OR "smoked meat*" [tiab] OR "sausages*" [tiab] OR "hot dogs*" [tiab] OR "bacon*" [tiab] OR "ham*" [tiab] OR "salami*" [tiab] OR "pepperoni*" [tiab] OR "jerky*" [tiab] OR "lunch meat*" [tiab] OR "cold cuts*" [tiab] AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" [Mesh] OR "Coronary Artery Disease" [Mesh] OR "IHD" [Mesh] OR "Angina, Stable" [Mesh] OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome" [Mesh] OR "ischemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "ischaemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "coronary artery disease" [tiab] OR "coronary heart disease" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischaemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial infarction" [tiab] OR "angina" [tiab] OR "acute coronary syndrome") [tiab] AND ("Systematic Review" [Publication Type] OR "systematic review" [Title/Abstract] OR "Meta-Analysis" [Publication Type] OR "meta-analysis" [Title/Abstract])	Papier K, Knuppel A, Syam N, Jebb SA, Key TJ. Meat consumption and risk of ischemic heart disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr. 2023;63(3):426-437. doi: 10.1080/10408398.2021.1949575. Epub 2021 Jul 20. PMID: 34284672.

A search string was developed to identify sources published after the period covered in Papier (June 5, 2021, to September 08, 2023). The searches returned 29 total hits. Duplicates between the search results were identified by DOI and removed, then the remaining records were screened by title and abstract for possible retrieval. The full text of

included studies was retrieved and evaluated for extraction. Each full-text exclusion was verified by both reviewers. No discrepancies occurred between the 2 reviewers. Each exclusion reason source count is depicted in the Processed meat-ischemic heart diseases diagram (**Extended Data Figure 2**).

Search strings for updated search on Processed Meat and Ischemic Heart Diseases

i. Pubmed

("processed meat*" [tiab] OR ("processed*meat*" [tiab] OR "cured meat*" [tiab] OR "deli meat*" [tiab] OR "packaged meat*" [tiab] OR "preserved meat*" [tiab] OR "smoked meat*" [tiab] OR "sausage*" [tiab] OR "hot dog*" [tiab] OR "bacon*" [tiab] OR "ham" [tiab] OR "hams" [tiab] OR "salami*" [tiab] OR "pepperoni*" [tiab] OR "jerk*" [tiab] OR "lunch meat*" [tiab] OR "cold cut*" [tiab])

AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" [Mesh] OR "Coronary Artery Disease" [Mesh] OR "Angina, Stable" [Mesh] OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome" [Mesh] OR "ischemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "ischaemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "coronary artery disease" [tiab] OR "coronary heart disease" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischaemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial infarction" [tiab] OR "angina" [tiab] OR "acute coronary syndrome" [tiab])

AND ("cohort" [tiab] OR "prospective*study" [tiab] OR "follow-up" [tiab] OR "longitudinal" [tiab] OR "nested case-control" [tiab] OR "case-cohort" [tiab]) AND (("2021/06/05"[Date - Publication] : "2023/09/08"[Date - Publication])) NOT (Meta-Analysis [Publication Type] OR Systematic Review [Publication Type])

ii. Embase

('processed meat*':ti,ab OR processed*meat*':ti,ab OR 'cured meat*':ti,ab OR 'deli meat*':ti,ab OR 'packaged meat*':ti,ab OR 'preserved meat*':ti,ab OR 'smoked meat*':ti,ab OR sausage*':ti,ab OR 'hot dog*':ti,ab OR bacon*':ti,ab OR ham:ti,ab OR hams:ti,ab OR salami*':ti,ab OR pepperoni*':ti,ab OR jerk*':ti,ab OR 'lunch meat*':ti,ab OR 'cold cut*':ti,ab)

AND ('myocardial ischemia'/exp OR 'coronary artery disease'/exp OR 'angina, stable'/exp OR 'acute coronary syndrome'/exp OR 'ischemic heart disease':ti,ab OR 'ischaemic heart disease':ti,ab OR 'coronary artery disease':ti,ab OR 'coronary heart disease':ti,ab OR 'myocardial ischemia':ti,ab OR 'myocardial ischaemia':ti,ab OR 'myocardial infarction':ti,ab OR angina:ti,ab OR 'acute coronary syndrome':ti,ab)

AND (cohort*':ti,ab OR prospective*study:ti,ab OR 'follow up':ti,ab OR longitudinal:ti,ab OR 'nested case-control':ti,ab OR 'case-cohort':ti,ab) NOT ('Meta-Analysis' OR 'Systematic Review') AND [2021-2023]/py AND [embase]/lim NOT [medline]/lim

iii. Web of Sciences

TS= (("processed meat*" OR processed*meat* OR "cured meat*" OR "deli meat*" OR "packaged meat*" OR "preserved meat*" OR "smoked meat*" OR sausage* OR "hot dog*" OR bacon* OR ham OR hams OR salami* OR pepperoni* OR jerk* OR "lunch meat*" OR "cold cut*"))

AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" OR "Coronary Artery Disease" OR "Angina, Stable" OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome" OR "ischemic heart disease" OR "ischaemic heart disease" OR "coronary artery disease" OR "coronary heart disease" OR "myocardial ischemia" OR "myocardial ischaemia" OR "myocardial infarction" OR angina OR "acute coronary syndrome")

AND (cohort OR prospective*study OR follow-up OR longitudinal OR "nested case-control" OR "case-cohort") NOT ("Meta-Analysis" OR "Systematic Review") AND DOP=(2021-06-05/2023-09-08)

c. Processed meat and colorectal cancer

We developed search strings for processed meat and colorectal cancer to identify the most recent PRISMA complaint meta-analyses that fulfilled our definition of exposure and outcomes.

The identified PRISMA complaint meta-analysis was Di et al 2023. A total of 109 citations were identified in the citations of this meta-analysis and screened. From a total of 109 citations, 17 studies were eligible to be included in the final analysis.

Search strings to identify the meta-analysis	Identified meta-analysis
<p>("processed meat*" [tiab] OR ("processed*meat*" [tiab] OR "cured meat*" [tiab] OR "deli meat*" [tiab] OR "packaged meat*" [tiab] OR "preserved meat*" [tiab] OR "smoked meat*" [tiab] OR "sausage*" [tiab] OR "hot dog*" [tiab] OR "bacon*" [tiab] OR "ham" [tiab] OR "hams" [tiab] OR "salami*" [tiab] OR "pepperoni*" [tiab] OR "jerk*" [tiab] OR "lunch meat*" [tiab] OR "cold cut*" [tiab]) AND ("colorectal cancer" [tiab] OR "colon cancer" [tiab] OR "rectal cancer" [tiab] OR "colorectal neoplasms" [Mesh] OR "colonic neoplasms" [Mesh] OR "rectal neoplasms" [Mesh] OR "colorectal tumor*" [tiab] OR "colon tumor*" [tiab] OR "rectal tumor*" [tiab] OR "colorectal carcinoma" [tiab] OR "colon carcinoma" [tiab] OR "rectal carcinoma" [tiab] OR "colorectal malignan*" [tiab] OR "colon malignan*" [tiab] OR "rectal malignan*" [tiab] OR "digestive*cancer" [tiab]) AND ("Systematic Review" [Publication Type] OR "systematic review" [Title/Abstract] OR "Meta-Analysis" [Publication Type] OR "meta-analysis" [Title/Abstract])</p>	<p>Di Y, Ding L, Gao L, Huang H. Association of meat consumption with the risk of gastrointestinal cancers: a systematic review and meta-analysis. BMC Cancer. 2023 Aug 23;23(1):782. doi: 10.1186/s12885-023-11218-1. PMID: 37612616; PMCID: PMC10463360.</p>

A search string was developed to identify sources published after the period covered in Di et al 2023 study. PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science were searched on September 15, 2023. The search was filtered for publication dates beginning February 01, 2023, the cutoff date for the search in Di et al 2023 study. The searches returned 15 total citations, none of them were meet the inclusion criteria and included in this systematic review. We also searched the global health data exchange database and identified one study that was not caught from the searching of citation of the selected meta-analysis and the three databases. We depicted the data searching and screening process in the PRISMA diagram (**Extended Data Figure 3**).

Search strings for updated search on Processed Meat and Colorectal Cancer

i. Pubmed

("processed meat*" [tiab] OR ("processed*meat*" [tiab] OR "cured meat*" [tiab] OR "deli meat*" [tiab] OR "packaged meat*" [tiab] OR "preserved meat*" [tiab] OR "smoked meat*" [tiab] OR "sausage*" [tiab] OR "hot dog*" [tiab] OR "bacon*" [tiab] OR "ham" [tiab] OR "hams" [tiab] OR "salami*" [tiab] OR "pepperoni*" [tiab] OR "jerk*" [tiab] OR "lunch meat*" [tiab] OR "cold cut*" [tiab])

AND ("colorectal cancer" [tiab] OR "colon cancer" [tiab] OR "rectal cancer" [tiab] OR "colorectal neoplasms" [Mesh] OR "colonic neoplasms" [Mesh] OR "rectal neoplasms" [Mesh] OR "colorectal tumor*" [tiab] OR "colon tumor*" [tiab] OR "rectal tumor*" [tiab] OR "colorectal carcinoma" [tiab] OR "colon carcinoma" [tiab] OR "rectal carcinoma" [tiab] OR "colorectal malignan*" [tiab] OR "colon malignan*" [tiab] OR "rectal malignan*" [tiab] OR "digestive*cancer" [tiab])

AND ("cohort" [tiab] OR "prospective*study" [tiab] OR "follow-up" [tiab] OR "longitudinal" [tiab] OR "nested case-control" [tiab] OR "case-cohort" [tiab]) AND (("2023/02/01"[Date - Publication] : "2023/09/01"[Date - Publication])) NOT (Meta-Analysis [Publication Type] OR Systematic Review [Publication Type])

ii. Embase

('processed meat*':ti,ab OR processed*meat*':ti,ab OR 'cured meat*':ti,ab OR 'deli meat*':ti,ab OR 'packaged meat*':ti,ab OR 'preserved meat*':ti,ab OR 'smoked meat*':ti,ab OR sausage*':ti,ab OR 'hot dog*':ti,ab OR bacon*':ti,ab OR ham:ti,ab OR hams:ti,ab OR salami*':ti,ab OR pepperoni*':ti,ab OR jerk*':ti,ab OR 'lunch meat*':ti,ab OR 'cold cut*':ti,ab)

AND ('colorectal cancer':ti,ab OR 'colon cancer':ti,ab OR 'rectal cancer':ti,ab OR 'colorectal neoplasms'/exp OR 'colonic neoplasms'/exp OR 'rectal neoplasms'/exp OR 'colorectal tumor*':ti,ab OR 'colon tumor*':ti,ab OR 'rectal tumor*':ti,ab OR 'colorectal carcinoma':ti,ab OR 'colon carcinoma':ti,ab OR 'rectal carcinoma':ti,ab OR 'colorectal malignan*':ti,ab OR 'colon malignan*':ti,ab OR 'rectal malignan*':ti,ab OR digestive*cancer:ti,ab)

AND (cohort*':ti,ab OR prospective*study:ti,ab OR 'follow up':ti,ab OR longitudinal:ti,ab OR 'nested case-control':ti,ab OR 'case-cohort':ti,ab) NOT ('Meta-Analysis' OR 'Systematic Review') AND [2023]/py AND [embase]/lim NOT [medline]/lim

iii. Web of Science

TS = (("processed meat*" OR processed*meat* OR "cured meat*" OR "deli meat*" OR "packaged meat*" OR "preserved meat*" OR "smoked meat*" OR sausage* OR "hot dog*" OR bacon* OR ham OR hams OR salami* OR pepperoni* OR jerk* OR "lunch meat*" OR "cold cut*"))

AND ("colorectal cancer" OR "colon cancer" OR "rectal cancer" OR "colorectal neoplasms" OR "colonic neoplasms" OR "rectal neoplasms" OR "colorectal tumor*" OR "colon tumor*" OR "rectal tumor*" OR "colorectal carcinoma" OR "colon carcinoma" OR "rectal carcinoma" OR "colorectal malignan*" OR "colon malignan*" OR "rectal malignan*" OR digestive*cancer)

AND (cohort* OR prospective*study OR follow-up OR longitudinal OR "nested case-control" OR "case-cohort*") NOT (Meta-Analysis OR "Systematic Review") AND DOP= (2023-02-01/2023-09-08)

2. Sugar sweetened Beverages (SSB) systematic review.

a. SSB and type 2 diabetes.

We developed a PubMed search string to identify the most recent PRISMA complaint meta-analysis on sugar sweetened beverages consumption and type 2 diabetes. The meta-analysis identified that fulfills our criteria of exposure definition (SSB), outcome definition (Type 2 diabetes). The identified meta-analysis was and PRISMA complaint was Li et al 2023. A total of 112 citations of this meta-analysis were identified and screened. From this meta-analysis, we included a total of 17 studies in the final analysis. This meta-analysis covered until December 2022.

Search strings to identify the meta-analysis	Identified meta-analysis
("sugar*" [tiab] OR "sweet beverages*" [tiab] OR "sugar beverages*" [tiab] OR "sweetened beverage*" [tiab] OR "soda*" [tiab] OR "sweet drink*" [tiab] OR "sugary drink*" [tiab] OR "non-alcoholic drinks*" [tiab] OR "soft drink*" [tiab] OR "soda-pop*" [tiab] OR "soft drinks*" [tiab] OR "energy drinks*" [tiab] OR "carbonated beverages*" [tiab] OR "fruit drinks*" [tiab] OR "high calorie drinks*" [tiab]) AND ("Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2" [Mesh] OR "diabetes mellitus type 2" [Title/Abstract] OR "Gestational diabetes" OR "diabetes type 2" [Title/Abstract] OR "type 2 diabetes mellitus" [Title/Abstract] OR "type 2 diabetes" [Title/Abstract] OR "non-insulin dependent diabetes" [Title/Abstract] OR "adult-onset diabetes" [Title/Abstract])) AND ("Systematic Review" [Publication Type] OR "systematic review" [Title/Abstract] OR "Meta-Analysis" [Publication Type] OR "meta-analysis" [Title/Abstract])	Li B, Yan N, Jiang H, Cui M, Wu M, Wang L, Mi B, Li Z, Shi J, Fan Y, Azalati MM, Li C, Chen F, Ma M, Wang D, Ma L. Consumption of sugar sweetened beverages, artificially sweetened beverages and fruit juices and risk of type 2 diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and mortality: A meta-analysis. <i>Front Nutr.</i> 2023 Mar 15;10:1019534. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2023.1019534. PMID: 37006931; PMCID: PMC10050372.

Another search string was developed to identify sources published after the period covered in Li et al 2023. PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science and searched on December 20, 2023. The searches from the three databases returned 47 total hits, of which four studies ultimately extracted and included in the model. From GHDX, we identified one study that meet our exclusion criteria not captured by the search strings and the meta-analysis identified. The exclusion reasons by source count were reported in the PRISMA diagram (**Extended Data Figure 4**).

Search strings for updated search on SSB and Type 2 Diabetes

i. Pubmed

("sweet beverages*" [tiab] OR "sugar-sweetened beverages*" [tiab] OR "sweetened beverage*" [tiab] OR "soda*" [tiab] OR "sweet drink*" [tiab] OR "sugary drink*" [tiab] OR "non-alcoholic beverages*" [tiab] OR "soft drink*" [tiab] OR "soda-pop" [tiab] OR "carbonated drinks*" [tiab] OR "energy drinks*" [tiab] OR "carbonated beverages*" [tiab] OR "fruit drinks*" [tiab] OR "high calorie drinks*" [tiab]) AND ("Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2" [Mesh] OR "diabetes mellitus type 2" [tiab] OR "diabetes mellitus type II" [tiab] OR "diabetes type 2" [tiab] OR "diabetes type II" [tiab] OR "type 2 diabetes mellitus" [tiab] OR "type II diabetes mellitus" [tiab] OR "type 2 diabetes" [tiab] OR

"type II diabetes" [tiab] OR "non-insulin dependent diabetes" [tiab] OR "adult-onset diabetes" [tiab])) AND ("cohort" [tiab] OR "prospective*study" [tiab] OR "follow-up" [tiab] OR "longitudinal" [tiab] OR "nested case-control" [tiab] OR "case-cohort"[tiab] AND (("2022/12/01"[Date - Publication] : "2023/12/18"[Date - Publication])) NOT (Meta-Analysis [Publication Type] OR Systematic Review [Publication Type])

ii. **Embase**

('sweet beverages*':ti,ab OR 'sugar-sweetened beverages*':ti,ab OR 'sweetened beverage*':ti,ab OR 'soda*':ti,ab OR 'sweet drink*':ti,ab OR 'sugary drink*':ti,ab OR 'non-alcoholic beverages*':ti,ab OR 'soft drink*':ti,ab OR 'soda-pop*':ti,ab OR 'carbonated drinks*':ti,ab OR 'energy drinks*':ti,ab OR 'carbonated beverages*':ti,ab OR 'fruit drinks*':ti,ab OR 'high calorie drinks*':ti,ab) AND ('diabetes mellitus, type 2'/exp OR 'diabetes mellitus type 2':ti,ab OR 'diabetes mellitus type ii':ti,ab OR 'diabetes type 2':ti,ab OR 'diabetes type ii':ti,ab OR 'type 2 diabetes mellitus':ti,ab OR 'type ii diabetes mellitus':ti,ab OR 'type 2 diabetes':ti,ab OR 'type ii diabetes':ti,ab OR 'non-insulin dependent diabetes':ti,ab OR 'adult-onset diabetes':ti,ab) AND (cohort*':ti,ab OR prospective*study:ti,ab OR 'follow up':ti,ab OR longitudinal:ti,ab OR 'nested case-control':ti,ab OR 'case-cohort':ti,ab) NOT ('Meta-Analysis' OR 'Systematic Review') AND [2022-2023]/py AND [embase]/lim NOT [medline]/lim

iii. **Web of Science**

TS = ("sweet beverages*" OR "sugar-sweetened beverages*" OR "sweetened beverage*" OR soda* OR "sweet drink*" OR "sugary drink*" OR "non-alcoholic beverages*" OR "soft drink*" OR soda-pop* OR "carbonated drinks*" OR "energy drinks*" OR "carbonated beverages*" OR "fruit drinks*" OR "high calorie drinks*") AND ("Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2" OR "diabetes mellitus type 2" OR "diabetes mellitus type II" OR "diabetes type 2" OR "diabetes type II" OR "type 2 diabetes mellitus" OR "type II diabetes mellitus" OR "type 2 diabetes" OR "type II diabetes" OR "non-insulin dependent diabetes" OR "adult-onset diabetes") AND (cohort OR prospective*study OR follow-up OR longitudinal OR "nested case-control" OR "case cohort") NOT ("Meta-Analysis" OR "Systematic Review")) AND DOP= (2022-12-01/2023-12-15)

b. **SSB and ischemic heart diseases**

We developed a PubMed search string to identify the most recent PRISMA complaint meta-analysis on sugar sweetened beverages consumption and ischemic heart diseases. The meta-analysis identified that fulfills our criteria of exposure definition (SSB), outcome definition (ischemic heart diseases). The identified meta-analysis was and PRISMA complaint was Li et al 2023. A total of 112 citations of this meta-analysis were identified and screened. From this meta-analysis, we included a total of 6 studies in the final analysis. This meta-analysis covered until December 2022.

Search strings to identify the meta-analysis	Identified meta-analysis
<p>((("sugar*" [tiab] OR "sweet beverages*" [tiab] OR "sugar-sweetened beverages*" [tiab] OR "sweetened beverage*" [tiab] OR "soda*" [tiab] OR "sweet drink*" [tiab] OR "sugary drink*" [tiab] OR "non-alcoholic beverages*" [tiab] OR "soft drink*" [tiab] OR "soda-pop*" [tiab] OR "carbonated drinks*" [tiab] OR "energy drinks*" [tiab] OR "carbonated beverages*" [tiab] OR "fruit drinks*" [tiab] OR "high calorie drinks*" [tiab]) AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" [Mesh] OR "Coronary Artery Disease" [Mesh] OR "IHD" [Mesh] OR "Angina, Stable" [Mesh] OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome" [Mesh] OR "ischemic heart</p>	<p>Li B, Yan N, Jiang H, Cui M, Wu M, Wang L, Mi B, Li Z, Shi J, Fan Y, Azalati MM, Li C, Chen F, Ma M, Wang D, Ma L. Consumption of sugar sweetened beverages, artificially sweetened beverages and fruit juices and risk of type 2 diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and mortality: A meta-analysis. <i>Front Nutr.</i> 2023 Mar 15;10:1019534. doi: 10.3389/fnut.2023.1019534. PMID: 37006931; PMCID: PMC10050372.</p>

<p>disease" [tiab] OR "ischaemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "coronary artery disease" [tiab] OR "coronary heart disease" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischaemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial infarction" [tiab] OR "angina" [tiab] OR "acute coronary syndrome" [tiab]) AND ("Systematic Review" [Publication Type] OR "systematic review" [Title/Abstract] OR "Meta-Analysis" [Publication Type] OR "meta-analysis" [Title/Abstract] OR "Review" [Publication Type])</p>	
--	--

Another search string was developed to identify sources published after the period covered in Li et al 2023. PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science and searched on December 20, 2023. The searches from the three databases returned 15 total hits. However, none of them meets the inclusion criteria to be included in the final model. We identified one study from GHDX that meets our inclusion criteria. We presented the overall data identification and data screening flow in the PRISMA diagram (**Extended Data Figure 5**).

Search strings for updated search on SSB and Ischemic Heart diseases

i. Pubmed

("sweet beverages*" [tiab] OR "sugar-sweetened beverages*" [tiab] OR "sweetened beverage*" [tiab] OR "soda*" [tiab] OR "sweet drink*" [tiab] OR "sugary drink*" [tiab] OR "non-alcoholic beverages*" [tiab] OR "soft drink*" [tiab] OR "soda-pop" [tiab] OR "carbonated drinks*" [tiab] OR "energy drinks*" [tiab] OR "carbonated beverages*" [tiab] OR "fruit drinks*" [tiab] OR "high calorie drinks*" [tiab]) AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" [Mesh] OR "Coronary Artery Disease" [Mesh] OR "IHD" [Mesh] OR "Angina, Stable" [Mesh] OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome" [Mesh] OR "ischemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "ischaemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "coronary artery disease" [tiab] OR "coronary heart disease" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischaemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial infarction" [tiab] OR "angina" [tiab] OR "acute coronary syndrome" [tiab]) AND ("cohort" [tiab] OR "prospective*study" [tiab] OR "follow-up" [tiab] OR "longitudinal" [tiab] OR "nested case-control" [tiab] OR "case-cohort"[tiab] AND (("2022/12/01"[Date - Publication] : "2023/12/18"[Date - Publication])) NOT (Meta-Analysis [Publication Type] OR Systematic Review [Publication Type])

ii. Embase

('sweet beverages*':ti,ab OR 'sugar-sweetened beverages*':ti,ab OR 'sweetened beverage*':ti,ab OR 'soda*':ti,ab OR 'sweet drink*':ti,ab OR 'sugary drink*':ti,ab OR 'non-alcoholic beverages*':ti,ab OR 'soft drink*':ti,ab OR 'soda-pop*':ti,ab OR 'carbonated drinks*':ti,ab OR 'energy drinks*':ti,ab OR 'carbonated beverages*':ti,ab OR 'fruit drinks*':ti,ab OR 'high calorie drinks*':ti,ab) AND ('myocardial ischemia'/exp OR 'myocardial ischemia' OR 'coronary artery disease'/exp OR 'coronary artery disease' OR 'angina, stable'/exp OR 'angina, stable' OR 'acute coronary syndrome'/exp OR 'acute coronary syndrome' OR 'ischemic heart disease':ti,ab OR 'ischaemic heart disease':ti,ab OR 'coronary artery disease':ti,ab OR 'coronary heart disease':ti,ab OR 'myocardial ischemia':ti,ab OR 'myocardial ischaemia':ti,ab OR 'myocardial infarction':ti,ab OR 'angina':ti,ab OR 'acute coronary syndrome':ti,ab) AND (cohort*':ti,ab OR 'prospective study':ti,ab OR 'follow-up':ti,ab OR 'longitudinal':ti,ab OR 'nested case-control':ti,ab OR 'case-cohort':ti,ab) NOT ('meta-analysis':ti,ab OR 'systematic review':ti,ab) AND [2022-2023]/py AND [embase]/lim NOT [medline]/lim

iii. Web of Sciences

TS= (("sweetened beverages" OR "sugar-sweetened beverages" OR "sweetened beverage" OR soda OR "sweet drink*" OR "sugary drink*" OR "non-alcoholic beverage*" OR "soft drink*" OR "soda pop" OR "carbonated drink*" OR "energy drink*" OR "carbonated beverage*" OR "fruit drink*" OR "high calorie drink*") AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" OR "Coronary Artery Disease" OR "Ischemic Heart Disease" OR "Ischaemic Heart Disease" OR "Coronary Heart Disease" OR "Myocardial Infarction" OR angina OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome") AND (cohort* OR prospective*study OR follow-up OR longitudinal OR "nested case-control" OR "case-cohort*") NOT (Meta-Analysis OR "Systematic Review")) AND DOP= (2022-12-01/2023-12-08)

3. Trans fatty acids systematic review
a. TFAs and ischemic heart diseases

We developed a PubMed search string to identify the most recent PRISMA complaint meta-analysis on trans fatty acids consumption and ischemic heart diseases. The meta-analysis identified that fulfills our criteria of exposure definition (trans fatty acids mainly from industrial sources), outcome definition (ischemic heart disease). The identified meta-analysis was and PRISMA complaint was de Souza et al 2015. A total of 179 citations of this meta-analysis were identified and screened. From this meta-analysis, we included a total of five studies in the final analysis from the identified meta-analysis. The protocol is registered at PROSPERO (PROSPERO ID = CRD42023495735).

Search strings to identify the meta-analysis	Identified meta-analysis
("trans-fat*" [tiab] OR "hydrogenated fats" [tiab] OR "trans fatty acids" [tiab] OR "trans unsaturated fatty acid*s" AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" [Mesh] OR "Coronary Artery Disease" [Mesh] OR "IHD" [Mesh] OR "Angina, Stable" [Mesh] OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome" [Mesh] OR "ischemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "ischaemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "coronary artery disease" [tiab] OR "coronary heart disease" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischaemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial infarction" [tiab] OR "angina" [tiab] OR "acute coronary syndrome") [tiab] AND ("Systematic Review" [Publication Type] OR "systematic review" [Title/Abstract] OR "Meta-Analysis" [Publication Type] OR "meta-analysis" [Title/Abstract])	de Souza RJ, Mente A, Maroleanu A, Cozma AI, Ha V, Kishibe T, Uleryk E, Budyłowski P, Schünemann H, Beyene J, Anand SS. Intake of saturated and trans unsaturated fatty acids and risk of all cause mortality, cardiovascular disease, and type 2 diabetes: systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. <i>BMJ</i> . 2015 Aug 11;351:h3978. doi: 10.1136/bmj.h3978. PMID: 26268692; PMCID: PMC4532752.

Another search string was developed to identify sources published after the period covered in de Souza et al 2015 et al 2015. PubMed, EMBASE, and Web of Science and searched on December 18, 2023. The searches from the three databases returned 92 total hits. None of them were eligible to be included in the final model. We identified one study from the GHDX that meet the inclusion criteria, so that in the final model we included a total of 6 studies (**Extended Data Figure 6**).

Search strings for updated search on Trans fatty acids and ischemic heart disease

i. Pubmed

("trans fat*" [tiab] OR "hydrogenated fats" [tiab] OR "trans fatty acids" [tiab] OR "trans unsaturated fatty acid*s" AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" [Mesh] OR "Coronary Artery Disease" [Mesh] OR "IHD" [Mesh] OR "Angina, Stable" [Mesh] OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome" [Mesh] OR "ischemic heart disease" [tiab] OR "ischaemic heart disease" [tiab] OR

"coronary artery disease" [tiab] OR "coronary heart disease" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial ischaemia" [tiab] OR "myocardial infarction" [tiab] OR "angina" [tiab] OR "acute coronary syndrome") [tiab] AND ("cohort" [tiab] OR "prospective*study" [tiab] OR "follow-up" [tiab] OR "longitudinal" [tiab] OR "nested case-control" [tiab] OR "case-cohort"[tiab] AND (("2015/12/01"[Date - Publication] : "2023/12/18"[Date - Publication])) NOT (Meta-Analysis [Publication Type] OR Systematic Review [Publication Type])

ii. **Embase**

('trans fat*':ti,ab OR 'hydrogenated fats*' ti,ab OR 'trans fatty acids*':ti,ab OR 'trans unsaturated fatty acids*':ti,ab) AND ('myocardial ischemia'/exp OR 'myocardial ischemia' OR 'coronary artery disease'/exp OR 'coronary artery disease' OR 'angina, stable'/exp OR 'angina, stable' OR 'acute coronary syndrome'/exp OR 'acute coronary syndrome' OR 'ischemic heart disease':ti,ab OR 'ischaemic heart disease':ti,ab OR 'coronary artery disease':ti,ab OR 'coronary heart disease':ti,ab OR 'myocardial ischemia':ti,ab OR 'myocardial ischaemia':ti,ab OR 'myocardial infarction':ti,ab OR 'angina':ti,ab OR 'acute coronary syndrome':ti,ab) AND (cohort*:ti,ab OR 'prospective study':ti,ab OR 'follow-up':ti,ab OR 'longitudinal':ti,ab OR 'nested case-control':ti,ab OR 'case-cohort':ti,ab) NOT ('meta-analysis':ti,ab OR 'systematic review':ti,ab) AND [2015-2023]/py AND [embase]/lim NOT [medline]/lim

iii. **Web of Science**

TS = (("trans-fat*" OR "hydrogenated fats*" OR "trans fatty acids*" OR "trans unsaturated fatty acids*") AND ("Myocardial Ischemia" OR "Coronary Artery Disease" OR "Ischemic Heart Disease" OR "Ischaemic Heart Disease" OR "Coronary Heart Disease" OR "Myocardial Infarction" OR "angina" OR "Acute Coronary Syndrome") AND ("cohort*" OR "prospective study" OR "follow-up" OR "longitudinal" OR "nested case-control" OR "case-cohort*")) NOT ("Meta-Analysis" OR "Systematic Review")) AND DOP= (2015-12-01/2023-12-18)

Section 1.2: Assessing data source eligibility

See Extended Data Figures 1-6 for details on identifying, screening, and assessing eligibility for records identified through our search.

Inclusion criteria

1. Exposure of interest: processed meat, SSB and trans-fat exposure aligning with the definition described above.
2. Measurable exposure: reported measure of consumption with grams equivalent, servings equivalent, or other quantification that can be converted into grams per day in both reference and alternate groups. For trans-fat, we used percent of daily energy intake as unit of exposure measurement.
3. Outcome of interest: Type 2 diabetes, Ischemic Heart Diseases, Colorectal cancer
4. Effect size of interest: Reported relative risk, odds ratio, hazard ratio, standardized incidence ratio, risk ratio or other similar relative measures of association of exposure and outcome of interest.
5. Effect size uncertainty: Included a measure of uncertainty for the effect size measure.
6. Study design: Prospective cohort, nested case-control, or case-cohort study
7. Non-duplicate study: Where multiple studies provided relative risk estimates from the same cohort or case-control, we included only one so as not to duplicate data. This decision was made primarily based on which report captured the largest person-time of exposure, but covariates included in relative risk estimation was also considered. We prioritized studies with larger person-time of exposure with more adjusted model.
8. Study population: study population is not defined by comorbidity or other traits that could interact with exposure and affect outcome.

9. Peer review: The full text should be peer reviewed article.
10. Language: The Title/Abstract is in English.

Exclusion criteria

1. Not exposure of interest: Studies that did not report any of the dietary exposures included in this review were not included.
2. Unmeasurable exposure: If studies reported exposures without grams or servings equivalent or other quantitative measures of exposure such as in aggregated “diet scores.” were excluded.
3. No exposure for both reference and alternate groups: Studies that did not quantify the exposure in the reference and alternate group were excluded.
4. No outcome of interest: Studies that reported on all-cause mortality or an outcome outside of the three outcomes of interest were excluded. This includes outcomes lacking specificity, such as cardiovascular disease and insulin sensitivity.
5. No effect size of interest: If studies did not report relative risk, odds ratio, hazard ratio, standardized incidence ratio, or other similar relative measures of association, they were excluded.
6. No effect size uncertainty: Studies that did not include a measure of uncertainty for the effect size measure were not eligible.
7. Wrong study design: Studies that were not a prospective cohort, nested case-control, or case-cohort study were excluded. Pooled cohort studies will be excluded if analysis from individual cohort studies are available.
8. Duplicate study: if a cohort reported in paper was reported in another report captured in our systematic review, and an expert team member ruled that the other report provided better information for our purpose, as outlined in the inclusion criteria above, we considered it as duplicates and remove it.
9. Non-general population: study population defined by comorbidity or other traits that could interact with exposure and affect outcome.
10. No peer review: The full text is not peer reviewed.
11. Language: The Title/Abstract is not in English.

For reports that met the inclusion criteria, data were extracted for the variables listed in **Supplemental Table 4**.

Supplementary Table 1. PRISMA 2020 checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Per the journal's request, the title does not include "systematic review". It is, however, in the title of the methods section, "Systematic reviews"
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	See PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts Checklist below (Supplementary Table 2)
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	"Main" (intro) paragraphs 1–4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	"Main" (intro) paragraph 3
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Criteria summarized in Methods section "systematic review"; full inclusion and exclusion criteria listed in SI section 1.2; reasons for exclusion and number of studies excluded also provided in PRISMA flow diagram for each pair (Extended Data Fig. 1-6)
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Methods section "Systematic Review" paragraph 1; SI section 1.1
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Methods section "Systematic Review": paragraph 1; SI section 1.1
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods section "Systematic Review" paragraph 1,2, 3,
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods section "Systematic Review" paragraph 1
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Methods sections "Systematic Review"
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Methods section "Systematic Review" paragraph 3, 4,5, 6, full list and definitions of all variables are in Supplemental Table 4; study characteristics for each included study are also listed in Supplemental Table 5
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Methods section "Testing and adjusting for biases across input study designs and characteristics"
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Method sections "overview" paragraph 1 and 2, "Estimating the BPRF"
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Methods section "Systematic Review"
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Methods section "Systematic Review"
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Methods sections "Systematic Review," "Estimating the risk-outcome relationship"
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis	Methods sections "Estimating the risk-outcome relationship", "Estimating the theoretical minimum risk

		was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	exposure level,” and “Estimating the BPRF”. Software packages described in “code availability” section of the manuscript
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Methods section “Quantifying remaining between-study heterogeneity”
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Methods section “Sensitivity analyses”; Supplementary information section 10
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Methods for detecting publication or reporting bias found in methods section “Evaluating the potential for publication and reporting bias”
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Methods section “Quantifying remaining between-study heterogeneity”
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	PRISMA flow diagram for each risk-outcome pair (Extended Data Fig. 1-6); first paragraph of each risk-outcome pair results section + the results “overview”
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	N/A
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Supplementary information section 5, Supplemental Table 5 (“study characteristics”)
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Supplementary information section 6, Supplemental Table 7. The definition of each bias covariate is defined in Supplemental Table 6.
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Section 7, Supplemental Table 8
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	First paragraph (summary of characteristics) and last paragraph each risk-outcome pair results section.
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Second paragraph of each risk-outcome pair results section; Fig. 1–3, Table 2
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	All uncertainty intervals presented everywhere in the manuscript and appendices reflect between-study heterogeneity (unless specified otherwise); BPRFs, Risk outcome scores, and star-ratings for each risk-outcome pair also reflect between-study heterogeneity
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Extended data Fig. 7-9
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Last sentence of each risk-outcome pair results section; funnel plots (Fig. 1–3)
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	All estimates are presented with 95% uncertainty intervals. UI values are given alongside all mean estimates in the Results and Discussion sections; all risk curve figures (Fig. 1–3) include shading to depict UI curves (both with and without between-study heterogeneity)
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Discussion paragraphs 1-7
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Discussion paragraphs 8-10
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Discussion paragraph 8-10
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Discussion paragraph 9,11
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	This systematic review was registered, as stated in paragraph 4 of the methods overview
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	This systematic review was registered, as stated in paragraph 4 of the methods overview
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	This systematic review was registered, as stated in paragraph 4 of the methods overview. Exposure definition of TFA is modified as TFA exposure is defined as consumption (in percent of daily energy intake) of trans fats, primarily those that are industrially produced.

Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	"Acknowledgments" section of the manuscript
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	"Competing interests" section of the manuscript
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	"Data availability" and "code availability" sections in the manuscript; data collection form template: Supplemental Table 5

Supplementary Table 2. PRISMA 2020 abstract checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Reported (Yes/No)
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Per the journal's request, the title does not include "systematic review". It is, however, in the title of the methods section, "conducting systematic reviews"
BACKGROUND			
Objectives	2	Provide an explicit statement of the main objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Yes
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	3	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review.	Not in abstract, just main text (given word count limitations by the journal)
Information sources	4	Specify the information sources (e.g. databases, registers) used to identify studies and the date when each was last searched.	Not in abstract, just main text (given word count limitations by the journal)
Risk of bias	5	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies.	Not in abstract, just main text (given word count limitations by the journal)
Synthesis of results	6	Specify the methods used to present and synthesise results.	Yes
RESULTS			
Included studies	7	Give the total number of included studies and participants and summarise relevant characteristics of studies.	Not in abstract, just main text (given word count limitations by the journal)
Synthesis of results	8	Present results for main outcomes, preferably indicating the number of included studies and participants for each. If meta-analysis was done, report the summary estimate and confidence/credible interval. If comparing groups, indicate the direction of the effect (i.e. which group is favoured).	Yes, though number of included studies and participants only reported in the main text
DISCUSSION			
Limitations of evidence	9	Provide a brief summary of the limitations of the evidence included in the review (e.g. study risk of bias, inconsistency and imprecision).	Not in abstract, just main text (given word count limitations by the journal)
Interpretation	10	Provide a general interpretation of the results and important implications.	Yes
OTHER			
Funding	11	Specify the primary source of funding for the review.	Not in abstract, just main text (given word count limitations by the journal)
Registration	12	Provide the register name and registration number.	No

Section 3. GATHER checklists

Supplementary Table 3. GATHER checklist

Item #	Checklist item	Reported on page #
Objectives and funding		
1	Define the indicator(s), populations (including age, sex, and geographic entities), and time period(s) for which estimates were made.	Main text methods “Systematic Review”, paragraph 2
2	List the funding sources for the work.	Main text acknowledgement section
Data Inputs		
For all data inputs from multiple sources that are synthesized as part of the study:		
3	Describe how the data were identified and how the data were accessed.	Main text methods section “Systematic Review”
4	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Identify all ad-hoc exclusions.	Main text methods section “Systematic Review”; reasons for exclusion and number of studies excluded also provided in PRISMA flow diagram (Extended Data Fig. 1–6)
5	Provide information on all included data sources and their main characteristics. For each data source used, report reference information or contact name/institution, population represented, data collection method, year(s) of data collection, sex and age range, diagnostic criteria or measurement method, and sample size, as relevant.	Supplementary information section 5, Supplemental Table 5 (“study characteristics”)
6	Identify and describe any categories of input data that have potentially important biases (e.g., based on characteristics listed in item 5).	Main text methods section “Testing and adjusting for biases across input study designs and characteristics” and “Evaluating the potential for publication and reporting bias”
For data inputs that contribute to the analysis but were not synthesized as part of the study:		
7	Describe and give sources for any other data inputs.	N/A
For all data inputs:		
8	Provide all data inputs in a file format from which data can be efficiently extracted (e.g., a spreadsheet rather than a PDF), including all relevant meta-data listed in item 5. For any data inputs that cannot be shared because of ethical or legal reasons, such as third-party ownership, provide a contact name or the name of the institution that retains the right to the data.	Data inputs in excel format available at https://preview.healthdata.org/burden-of-proof/ . will go live at publication.
Data analysis		
9	Provide a conceptual overview of the data analysis method. A diagram may be helpful.	Introduction paragraph 4; methods “Overview” section
10	Provide a detailed description of all steps of the analysis, including mathematical formulae. This description should cover, as relevant, data cleaning, data pre-processing, data adjustments and weighting of data sources, and mathematical or statistical model(s).	Main text methods
11	Describe how candidate models were evaluated and how the final model(s) were selected.	Main text methods “Estimating the risk-outcome relationship”
12	Provide the results of an evaluation of model performance, if done, as well as the results of any relevant sensitivity analysis.	Main text methods “sensitivity analyses” section; Extended data Fig. 7-9
13	Describe methods for calculating uncertainty of the estimates. State which sources of uncertainty were, and were not, accounted for in the uncertainty analysis.	Main text methods “Quantifying remaining between-study heterogeneity”
14	State how analytic or statistical source code used to generate estimates can be accessed.	Code availability statement in the main text methods “Code Availability statement”
Results and Discussion		
15	Provide published estimates in a file format from which data can be efficiently extracted.	https://preview.healthdata.org/burden-of-proof/ .
16	Report a quantitative measure of the uncertainty of the estimates (e.g. uncertainty intervals).	Uncertainty intervals are given for all findings, including in the text, figures, and tables in the main text and Supplementary Information
17	Interpret results in light of existing evidence. If updating a previous set of estimates, describe the reasons for changes in estimates.	Discussion paragraphs 1-7
18	Discuss limitations of the estimates. Include a discussion of any modelling assumptions or data limitations that affect interpretation of the estimates.	Discussion paragraphs 8-10

Section 4: Data source extraction

For reports that met the inclusion criteria, data were extracted for the variables listed in Supplemental Table 4.

Supplementary Table 4. Causal criteria extraction template

Category	Variable	Definition
Source	seq	
	underlying_nid	Underlying NID: Enter the underlying NID of the study (if applicable). Always talk to a data indexer if you don't know if an underlying NID is needed. They may be used for meta-analyses, certain database sources, and in some other specific cases.
	nid	Found in GHDx, created through the epi form, or created by Data Indexer
	field_citation_value	IHME Zotero format or if source has NID, citation info from GHDx
	file_path	optional; full file path of article; Only needed if source doesn't have NID, to facilitate NID creation.
R-O pair	risk	Risk: Select the risk factor, if not listed here, contact the causal criteria team

	risk_mapping	the relationship between study definition of risk and GBD definition of risk for a particular effect size
	outcome	Outcome: Select the outcome.
	outcome_mapping	the relationship between study definition of outcome and GBD definition of outcome for a particular effect size
Location	location_name	location name (from locations tab). Do a fast double-click in this field to get the drop-down menu, then start typing the location_name. For location_names with special characters, you may need to use the scroll bar.
	location_id	autopopulated from location_name
	rep_geography	Were the study participants representative of the geography? 1=yes, 0=no
	rep_selection_criteria	If rep_geography is 0, please specify the selection criteria of the study that is used in the analysis
	rep_prevalent_disease	Is the study aiming to evaluate the risk or mortality of people who have already developed the outcome? 1=yes 0=no (i.e. yes if for SBP-IHD paper, all participants have IHD at baseline and the paper is looking at mortality due to SBP, no if for SBP-IHD paper the participants have other prevalent diseases)
Study Population	year_start_study	year the study was started. If not specified, leave blank
	year_end_study	year the study was finished (including most recent follow up). If not specified, leave blank
	age_start	ages from 1 and above must be entered as an integer. Ages <1 can be entered as decimal values, e.g., 3 days = 3/365.
	age_end	ages from 1 and above must be entered as an integer. Ages <1 can be entered as decimal values, e.g., 3 days = 3/365.
	age_mean	Mean age
	age_sd	SD of age
	age_issue	0 = no issue flagged; 1 = issue flagged for modeler; always include explanatory notes the note_SR column
	percent_male	what percent of the population is male (0-1), if pop is all female then it would be 0
	sex_issue	sex_issue
Study Design	design	Study design: Specify the design of the study
	study_name	Study Name: Enter the name of the study (e.g., Nurses' Health Study), if provided. Do not enter the title of the article.
Exposure	exp_assess_level	Level of exposure assessment: The exposure was assessed...
	exp_instrument	Exposure assessment instrument: Specify the name of the exposure assessment instrument. For self-reported exposures, please specify the name of the questionnaire e.g., International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ). If more than one instrument specify all
	exp_assess_period	What was the frequency of exposure assessment?
	exp_assess_num	if multiple, specify the number of times that exposure was assessed (excluding baseline)
	exp_method_1	Please specify the method of exposure assessment. If there are more than 1, please add in the next columns labeled "exp_method_2".
	exp_method_2	Please specify the method of exposure assessment. If there are more than 2, please add in the next columns labeled "exp_method_3".
	exp_method_3	Please specify the method of exposure assessment.
	exp_recall_period	This field describes the unit of exposure recall used in data collection ONLY for self-report. Select the correct option from the drop-down menu. If the unit is days, weeks, months, or years, please enter the number in exp_recall_period_value (next column). If the unit is 'lifetime', nothing needs to be entered in exp_recall_period_value. For example, if the study said the recall period was 4 weeks, enter 4 in exp_recall_period_value, and 'weeks' in the field exp_recall_period. If 'other' is selected, please describe in exp_recall_period_other
	exp_recall_period_value	If you entered days, weeks, months, or years in the field 'exp_recall_period', please enter the corresponding integer in this field. For example, if the study said the recall period was 4 weeks, enter 4 in exp_recall_period_value, and 'weeks' in the field exp_recall_period.
	exp_recall_period_other	If 'other' was selected in exp_recall_period, please describe the exposure recall period that the study specified (e.g., recall of exposure from 12 to 18 years).
exp_type	Which form of the exposure was included in relative risk estimation analysis?	
Outcome	outcome_def	Outcome definition: Provide a brief description of the outcome as reported in the study.
	outcome_type	Outcome type: please specify if the outcome definition included incidence of or mortality from a disease endpoint
	outcome_assess_1	Method of outcome assessment: Specify the method of assessment of the study outcome. If more than 1 are appropriate, enter additional methods in the next column labeled "outcome_assess_2"
	outcome_assess_2	Method of outcome assessment: Specify the method of assessment of the study outcome. If more than 2 are appropriate, enter additional methods in the next column labeled "outcome_assess_3"
	outcome_assess_3	Method of outcome assessment: Specify the method of assessment of the study outcome.
Follow up	duration_fup_measure	Type of follow up measure (i.e. mean, median, max, min)
	duration_fup_units	Units of follow up duration
	value_of_duration_fup	Enter the length of participant follow-up.
Confounders	confounders_age	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_sex	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_education	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_income	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_smoking	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_alcohol_use	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_physical_activity	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
confounders_dietary_components	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no	

	confounders_bmi	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_hypertension	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_diabetes	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_hypercholesterolemia	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	cov_vegetable_intake	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	cov_fruits_intake	
	Cov_energy_intake	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	Cov_unprocessedmeat	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	Cov_sodium_intake	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	cov_saturated_fat_intake	if controlled for in the relative risk estimation analysis, mark 1 for yes. Mark 0 for no
	confounders_other	For other confounders that not listed, list here
Effect Size	page_num_effect_size	Page number (where you found effect_size) from literature, or survey question where you found effect size; Use page number(s) of article, not page # of pdf
	effect_size_measure	Effect size measure: Specify the measure of effect size
	effect_size	Effect size estimate: Provide the effect size estimate
	lower	Provide the lower limit of the confidence interval. Enter on a "per 1" basis. (If the CI is reported as a percent, you must convert to a decimal.) These 3 fields must all be filled in if any of them are filled in: lower, upper, uncertainty_type_value.
	upper	Provide the upper limit of the confidence interval. Enter on a "per 1" basis. (If the CI is reported as a percent, you must convert to a decimal.) These 3 fields must all be filled in if any of them are filled in: lower, upper, uncertainty_type_value.
	CI_uncertainty_type_value	This field is required if 'lower' & 'upper' are entered. This column represents the confidence level which is reported at (Eg. 95, 90, 99). These 3 fields must all be filled in if any of them are filled in: lower, upper, uncertainty_type_value.
	nonCI_uncertainty_value	Numerical value of the nonCI_uncertainty_type entered in that column. For example, if SD=5.3, you'd put 5.3 in this column, and choose SD from the drop down menu in nonCI_uncertainty_type.
	nonCI_uncertainty_type	Enter SE or SD if appropriate. For example, if SD=5.3, you'd put 5.3 in nonCI_uncertainty_value, and choose SD from the drop down menu in this column (nonCI_uncertainty_type).
	uncertainty_issue	Mark with a 1 if no uncertainty is reported, if some sort of uncertainty is reported, mark 0
	subgroup_analysis	1 if RR is from main analysis (all participants), 0 if sub-analysis (only males, or among a specific age group, etc.)
	subgroup_analysis_free_text	if a sub-analysis, describe it (i.e. age, sex, etc.)
	effect_size_multi_location	1 if the reported effect size is from a multi-country study and only one effect size has been reported for all locations, otherwise 0
	effect_size_multi_location_specify	which geography level is the RR for
	pooled_cohort	1 if the reported effect size is from a pooled analysis and only pooled effect size has been reported, otherwise 0
dose_response	Does the study support a dose-response relationship between the exposure and the outcome? (1=yes, 0=no)	
dose_response_detail	If "1" was specified in the dose_response field, please specify in this field the type of evidence supporting the dose-response relationship. For example, "statistically significant p value for linear trend".	
Cohorts	cohort_person_years_exp	Please specify the person years of follow up in the exposed group
	cohort_person_years_unexp	Please specify the person years of follow up in the unexposed group
	cohort_person_years_total	Enter the total person-years of follow-up if person-years of follow up in exposed and unexposed not reported
	cohort_number_events_exp	Please specify the number of events in the exposed group
	cohort_number_events_unexp	Please specify the number of events in the unexposed group
	cohort_number_events_total	Enter the total number of events/cases if number of events in exposed and unexposed not reported
	cohort_sample_size_exp	Please specify the number of people in the exposed group if person-years of follow up in exposed not reported
	cohort_sample_size_unexp	Please specify the number of people in the unexposed group if person-years of follow up in unexposed not reported
	cohort_sample_size_total	Please specify the number of people included in the analysis if total person-years of follow up in not reported
	cohort_dropout_rate	Dropout rate : Specify the dropout rate (%) at the end of the study. Enter on a "per 1" basis. For example: 23% is entered as .23.
	cohort_dropout_assess	Specify how dropout rate was defined in the study.
	cohort_exposed_def	exposed group definition: Provide a brief description of the exposed group (i.e., the comparison group) as used in estimation of the relative risk (e.g., never smokers)
	cohort_exp_unit_rr	Exposure unit (for continuous risks): Specify the unit of exposure (e.g., grams/day).

		cohort_exp_level_rr	Exposure level in the exposed group (for continuous risks): Specify the mean/median level of exposure in the exposed group.
		cohort_unexp_def	unexposed group definition: Provide a brief description of the unexposed group (i.e., the comparison group) as used in estimation of the relative risk (e.g., never smokers)
		cohort_unexp_unit_rr	Exposure unit (for continuous risks): Specify the unit of exposure (e.g., grams/day) for the unexposed group
		cohort_unexp_level_rr	Exposure level in the unexposed group (for continuous risks): Specify the mean/median level of exposure in the unexposed group.
		cohort_exp_level_dr	Exposure level in for dose-repose RRs (for continuous risks): If the study reports dose-repose RR, please specify the level of exposure for the reported RR
Case-control		cc_community	Were the controls selected from the community? 1 = yes, 0=no
		cc_cases	Number of cases
		cc_control	Number of controls
		cc_exposed_def	Exposed group definition: Provide a brief description of the exposed group for which the the relative risk is reported (e.g., current smokers)
		cc_exp_unit_rr	Exposure unit (for continuous risks): Specify the unit of exposure (e.g., grams/day).
		cc_exp_level_rr	Exposure level in the exposed group (for continuous risks): Specify the mean/median level of exposure in the exposed group.
		cc_unexposed_def	Unexposed group definition: Provide a brief description of the unexposed group (i.e., the comparison group) as used in estimation of the relative risk (e.g., never smokers)
		cc_unexp_unit_rr	
		cc_unexp_level_rr	Exposure level in the unexposed group (for continuous risks): Specify the mean/median level of exposure in the unexposed group.
		cc_exp_level_dr	Exposure level in for dose-repose RRs (for continuous risks): If the study reports dose-repose RR, please specify the level of exposure for the reported RR
Trials		int_intervention_description	Intervention definition: Provide a brief description of the intervention as reported in the study.
		int_control_description	control definition: Provide a brief description of the control as reported in the study.
		int_intervention_multi_rf	Does this intervention simultaneously target more than one risk? (1=yes, 0=no)
		int_intervention_multi_rf_specify	Specify the risks that are targeted by the interevntion
		int_intervention_level	Level of intervention: The intervention was implemented ...
		int_adhere_assess	Specify how adherence was defined in the study.
		int_adhere_rate_intervention	adherence rate in the intervention group; Enter on a "per 1" basis. For example: 23% is entered as .23.
		int_adhere_rate_control	adherence rate in the control group; Enter on a "per 1" basis. For example: 23% is entered as .23.
		int_dropout_rate_intervention	Dropout rate in the intervention group: Specify the dropout rate (%) at the end of the study. Enter on a "per 1" basis. For example: 23% is entered as .23.
		int_dropout_rate_control	Dropout rate in the control group: Specify the dropout rate (%) at the end of the study. Enter on a "per 1" basis. For example: 23% is entered as .23.
		int_dropout_assess	Specify how dropout rate was defined in the study.
		int_blinding	For interventional studies. Blinding: The trial was ... (select 1)
		int_exp_unit	For trials, specify the unit of exposure (e.g., mmol/l)
		int_baseline_exp_int	For trials, specify the exposure level in the intervention group at baseline
		int_baseline_exp_comp	For trials, specify the exposure level in the comparison group at baseline
		int_fup_exp_int	For trials, specify the exposure level in the intervention group at the end of the follow-up time
		int_fup_exp_comp	For trials, specify the exposure level in the comparison group at the end of follow up time
		int_fup_exp_int_difference	For trials, please specify the difference of exposure level between baseline and follow up time for the intervention group
		int_fup_exp_comp_difference	For trials, please specify the difference of exposure level between baseline and follow up time for the comparison group
		int_person_years_int	Please specify the number of person years of follow up for the intrevntion group
		int_person_years_comp	Please specify the number of person years of follow up in the comparison group
		int_number_events_int	For trials, specify the number of cases in the intervention group at the end of follow up
		int_number_events_comp	For trials, specify the number of cases in the control group at the end of follow up
		int_sample_size_int_group_baseline	For trials, specify the sample size in the intervention group at baseline
		int_sample_size_comparison_group_baseline	For trials, specify the sample size in the comparison group at baseline
		int_sample_size_int_group_follow_up	For trials, specify the sample size in the intervention group at the end of the follow-up time
	int_sample_size_comparison_group_follow_up	For trials, specify the sample size in the comparison group at the end of follow up time	
Other		note_modeler	for modelers only, audience is modeler, not for correspondence
		note_sr	notes related to extraction, including assumptions, data adjustment, problems with source, any other notes that may be relevant, etc.
		extractor	uwnet id of person who extracted the data

Section 5: Study characteristics

In Supplementary Table 5 we provide characteristics for each of the studies identified and used in this meta-analysis.

Supplementary Table 5. Studies characteristics.

Dietary risk factor	outcome	Author	year	Study name	Location	Study design	Sex	Follow up length in years	Age start	Age end	Primary exposure assessment method	Endpoint	Primary outcome ascertainment method	total events	Sample size
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	The Health Professionals Follow-up Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	30	40	75	FFQ	Incidence and mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	4456	43272
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	The Nurses' Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	26	30	55	FFQ	Incidence and mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	3162	84136
Processed meat	IHD	Burke	2007		Australia	prospective cohort	Both	14	15	88	FFQ	Incidence and mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	130	514
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study (ARIC)	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	24	45	64	FFQ	Incidence and mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1147	12066
Processed meat	IHD	Iqbal	2021	Prospective Urban Rural Epidemiology (PURE) Study	Global	prospective cohort	Both	9.5	35	70	FFQ	Incidence	Physician diagnosis	531	31640
Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	pan-European EPIC cohort (European Prospective Investigation Into Cancer and Nutrition)	Global	prospective cohort	Both	12.6	52	61	FFQ	Incidence and mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	7198	409885
Processed meat	IHD	Møller	2021	The Danish National Survey on Diet and Physical Activity	Congo	prospective cohort	Both	9.8	37	75	Food Diary	Incidence and mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	439	8007
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Japan	prospective cohort	Male	18.4	40	79	FFQ	Mortality	Death certificates	301	20466
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Japan	prospective cohort	Female	18.4	40	79	FFQ	Mortality	Death certificates	236	31217
Processed meat	IHD	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	United Kingdom	prospective cohort	Both	8	40	73	FFQ	Incidence and mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	13309	435188
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Japan	prospective cohort	Male	14	45	74	FFQ	Mortality	Death certificates	367	40072
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Japan	prospective cohort	Female	14	45	74	FFQ	Mortality	Death certificates	182	47435
Processed meat	IHD	Whiteman	1999	OXCHECK study	United Kingdom	prospective cohort	Both	9	35	64	FFQ	Mortality	Death certificates	91	9923
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	MDC Study	Sweden	prospective cohort	Both	14	45	74	7-day dietary recall	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	2860	26930
Processed meat	T2DM	Fretts	2012	SHFS study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	8	6.6	63.4	FFQ	Incidence	Biomarker	243	3665
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Nurses' Health study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	40	30	55	FFQ	Incidence, mortality	Biomarker	22761	216695
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Nurses' Health Study II	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	28	25	42	FFQ	Incidence, mortality	Biomarker	22761	216695
Processed meat	T2DM	GU	2023	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	30	40	75	FFQ	Incidence, mortality	Biomarker	22761	216695
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Western Europe	case-cohort	Male	11.7	20	80	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	5751	11174
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Western Europe	case-cohort	Female	11.7	20	80	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	4698	14914
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective study	Japan	prospective cohort	Male	5	40	75	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	681	27425
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based	Japan	prospective cohort	Female	5	40	75	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	497	36424

				Prospective study											
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	The E3N study	France	prospective cohort	Female	13.8	40	65	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1369	66118
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	The E3N study	Germany	prospective cohort	Female	13.8	40	65	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1369	66118
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	The E3N study	Greece	prospective cohort	Female	13.8	40	65	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1369	66118
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	CHNS	China	prospective cohort	Both	9	45	99	24-hour dietary recall	Incidence	Biomarker	1088	16117
Processed meat	T2DM	Mari-Sanchis	2016	SUN cohort	Spain	prospective cohort	Both	8.7	20	90	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	146	18527
Processed meat	T2DM	Montonen	2005	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Finland	prospective cohort	Both	23	40	69	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	383	4304
Processed meat	T2DM	Männistö	2010	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention study	Finland	prospective cohort	Male	12	50	69	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1098	25943
Processed meat	T2DM	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	United Kingdom	prospective cohort	Both	8	40	73	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	9791	447351
Processed meat	T2DM	Son	2019	Korean Genome and Epidemiology Study (KoGES)	Republic of Korea	prospective cohort	Both	10	40	69	FFQ	Incidence	Physician diagnosis	668	8618
Processed meat	T2DM	Song	2004	Women's Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	8.8	45	99	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	1558	37309
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Hawaii	prospective cohort	Male	13.5	45	75	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	4555	36256
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Hawaii	prospective cohort	Female	13.5	45	75	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	4032	39256
Processed meat	T2DM	Villegas	2006	Shanghai Women's Health Study (SWHS)	Shanghai	prospective cohort	Female	4.6	40	70	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	1972	74493
Processed meat	T2DM	van	2012	Rottersdam study	Netherlands	prospective cohort	Both	12.4	55	80.7	FFQ	Incidence	Physician diagnosis	456	4366
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	The Nurses' Health Study (NHS) and The Health Professionals Follow-up Study (HFPS)	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	27	30	75	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1735	87108
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	27	30	75	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	996	47389
Processed meat	CRC	Bostick	1994	Iowa Women's Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	5	55	69	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	212	35216
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Cancer Prevention Study II Nutrition Cohort	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	9	50	74	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	665	69664
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Cancer Prevention Study II Nutrition Cohort	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	9	50	74	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	532	78946
Processed meat	CRC	Cross	2010	NIH-AARP Diet and Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	7.2	50	71	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	2719	300948
Processed meat	CRC	English	2004	Melbourne Collaborative Cohort Study	Australia	prospective cohort	Both	9	40	69	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	451	37112
Processed meat	CRC	Etemadi	2018	NIH-AARP Diet and Health	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	13.8	50	74	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical	6640	407270

				Study (AARP), Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial (PLCO), Agricultural Health Study (AHS)									records or disease registries		
Processed meat	CRC	Flood	2003	Breast Cancer Detection Demonstration Project	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	8.5	18	99	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Self-report	487	45496
Processed meat	CRC	Gilsing	2015	Netherlands Cohort Study (NLCS)	Netherlands	prospective cohort	Both	20.3	55	69	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	437	10210
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	JPHC I; (ii) JPHC II; (iii) JACC; (iv) MIYAGI; (v) OHSAKI; (vi) JPHC-5y; and (vii) TAKAYAMA.	Japan	prospective cohort	Male	15.3857143	35	99	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	3428	107777
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	JPHC I; (ii) JPHC II; (iii) JACC; (iv) MIYAGI; (v) OHSAKI; (vi) JPHC-5y; and (vii) TAKAYAMA.	Japan	prospective cohort	Female	15.3857143	35	99	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	2266	124626
Processed meat	CRC	Knuppel	2020	UK Biobank	United Kingdom	prospective cohort	Both	6.9	37	73	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	3228	474996
Processed meat	CRC	Larsson	2005	Swedish Mammography Cohort	Sweden	prospective cohort	Female	13.9	40	75	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	733	61433
Processed meat	CRC	Lin	2004	Women's Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	8.7	45	99	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Self-report	202	37547
Processed meat	CRC	Mehta	2020	The Sister Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	4.8	35	74	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	216	48704
Processed meat	CRC	Mejborn	2020	The Danish National Survey on Diet and Physical Activity	Denmark	prospective cohort	Both	8.7	15	75	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	127	6282
Processed meat	CRC	Norat	2005	EPIC cohort	Western Europe	prospective cohort	Both	4.8	21	83	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1329	478040
Processed meat	CRC	O'Sullivan	2020	Alberta Tomorrow Project	Canada	prospective cohort	Both	13.23	35	69	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	267	26460
Processed meat	CRC	Ollberding	2012	The Multiethnic Cohort Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	13.6	45	75	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	3404	165717
Processed meat	CRC	Pietinen	1999	Alpha-Tocopherol Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Finland	prospective cohort	Male	8	50	69	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	185	27111
Trans fat	IHD	Laake	2012	Norwegian Counties Study	Norway	prospective cohort	Both	25.8	20	49	FFQ	Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	2383	71464
Trans fat	IHD	Li	2015	Nurses' Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	30	30	55	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	3492	84,628
Trans fat	IHD	Li	2015	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	24	40	75	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	4175	42,908
Trans fat	IHD	Oomen	2001	Zutphen Elderly Study	Netherlands	prospective cohort	Male	10	64	84	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	98	660
Trans fat	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer	Finland	prospective cohort	Male	6.1	50	69	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1399	21930

				Prevention Study												
Trans fat	IHD	Virtanen	2014	The Kuopio Ischemic Heart Disease Risk Factor Study	Finland	prospective cohort	Male	21.4	42	60	FFQ	Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	565	1981	
Trans fat	IHD	Virtanen	2014	The Kuopio Ischemic Heart Disease Risk Factor Study	Finland	prospective cohort	Male	21.4	42	60	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	565	1981	
Trans fat	IHD	Xu	2006	the Strong Heart Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	7.2	47	79	24-hour dietary recall	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	436	2938	
Trans fat	IHD	Xu	2006	the Strong Heart Study	Latin America and Caribbean	prospective cohort	Both	7.2	47	79	24-hour dietary recall	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	436	2938	
Trans fat	IHD	Xu	2006	the Strong Heart Study	Caribbean	prospective cohort	Both	7.2	47	79	24-hour dietary recall	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	436	2938	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Collin	2019	REGARDS Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	10	45	99	FFQ	Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	168	13440	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Japan	prospective cohort	Male	18	40	59	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	360	18874	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Japan	prospective cohort	Female	18	40	59	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	93	20911	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	9.2	45	65	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	269	52238	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	9.2	45	65	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	123	6481	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Keller	2020	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Finland	prospective cohort	Male	6	50	69	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	1399	21141	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Keller	2020	Iowa Women's Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	10	55	69	FFQ	Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	291	29528	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Mullee	2019	European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition	Western Europe	prospective cohort	Both	16.4	18	99	FFQ	Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	3536	451743	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Pacheco	2020	California Teachers Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	20	18	99	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	2677	106178	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Pacheco	2023	NHS, HPFS	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	36	30	75	FFQ	Incidence and Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	8438	105418	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Warfa	2016	Malmö Diet and Cancer Cohort Study	Sweden	prospective cohort	Both	17	44	73	FFQ	Incidence & Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	2493	26190	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	IHD	Yang	2022	Women's Health Initiative	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	17.4	50	79	FFQ	Incident and Mortality	Administrative medical records or disease registries	4695	109034	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Nurses' Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	24	30	55	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	7370	74749	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Health Professionals Follow-Up study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	22	40	75	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	2865	39059	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Dhingra	2007	Framingham Heart Study	Massachusetts	prospective cohort	Both	4	18	99	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or	1426	6154	

														disease registries		
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Japan	prospective cohort	Male	10	40	59	24-hour dietary recall	Incidence	Self-report	484	12137	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Japan	prospective cohort	Female	10	40	59	24-hour dietary recall	Incidence	Self-report	340	15448	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	EPIC-E3N cohort	France	prospective cohort	Female	14	18	99	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	1369	66118	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Gardener	2018	Northern Manhattan Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	11	18	99	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	368	2019	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	CARDIA study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Both	30	18	30	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	680	4719	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Huang	2017	Women's Health Initiative observational study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	8.4	50	79	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	4675	64850	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC-InterAct cohort study	Western Europe	nested case-control	Both	11.7	18	99	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	7116	15374	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Finland	prospective cohort	Both	12	40	60	FFQ	Incidence	Administrative medical records or disease registries	177	4304	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	EPIC-Norfolk study	United Kingdom	prospective cohort	Both	10.8	40	79	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	847	24653	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Odegaard	2010	Singapore Chinese Health Study	Singapore	prospective cohort	Both	5.7	45	74	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	2273	43580	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Black Women's Health Study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	6	21	69	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	2713	43960	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Pan	2012	Nurses' Health Study II	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	18	25	42	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	2718	82902	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Thailand	prospective cohort	Male	8	18	99	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	437	17412	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Thailand	prospective cohort	Female	8	18	99	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	258	21716	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Male	7.5	45	64	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	718	5414	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	United States of America	prospective cohort	Female	7.7	45	64	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	719	6790	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Sakurai	2014	Occupational cohort	Japan	prospective cohort	Male	5.5	35	55	FFQ	Incidence	Biomarker	170	2037	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Siqueira	2023	ELSA-Brasil study	Brazil	prospective cohort	Both	4	35	74	FFQ	Incidence	Biomarker	1604	6124	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Torres-Ibarra	2020	Health Workers Cohort Study	Mexico	prospective cohort	Both	6.7	31	56	FFQ	Incidence	Self-report	109	1445	
Sugar Sweetened Beverages	T2DM	Viana	2023	Cohort of Universities of Minas Gerais (CUME)	Brazil	prospective cohort	Both	3	18	99	FFQ	Incidence	Physician diagnosis	69	2480	

CRC, colorectal cancer; IHD, Ischemic Heart diseases, T2DM, type 2 diabetes

Section 6: Study quality and risk of bias assessment

In this table, we presented the definition of each of the bias covariates included in this systematic review. For each study that met the inclusion criteria, several indicators of bias were assessed during the extraction process. A description of the bias covariates is given in supplementary Table 6. Supplementary Table 7 and Supplementary Table 8 shows the value of each quantified bias covariate. In this presentation of the data, there is one row per individual bias covariate combination for the effect sizes of each study.

Supplementary Table 6: Bias covariates definitions.

Bias covariate	Definitions
cov_adjust ed_0, cov_adjust ed_1, cov_adjust ed_2, cov_adjust ed_3	Cascading dummy variables for adjustment level of the effect sizes (i.e., for which/how many variables the effect sizes were adjusted). There are four adjustment levels, namely, (0) no adjustment, (1) only adjusted for age or sex, (2) adjusted for age and sex, and (3) adjusted for age, sex, smoking, and more than 4 other covariates. If the adjustment level is 0, then cov_adjusted_0 = 1, cov_adjusted_1 = 1, cov_adjusted_2 = 1, and cov_adjusted_3 = 1; if the adjustment level is 1, then cov_adjusted_0 = 0, cov_adjusted_1 = 1, cov_adjusted_2 = 1, cov_adjusted_3 = 1; if the adjustment level is 2, then cov_adjusted_0 = 0, cov_adjusted_1 = 0, cov_adjusted_2 = 0, cov_adjusted_3 = 1; if the adjustment level is 3, then cov_adjusted_0 = 0, cov_adjusted_1 = 0, cov_adjusted_2 = 0, cov_adjusted_3 = 0
cov_rep_prevalent_disease	0 for studies where participants with pre-existing disease states were excluded;

	1 for studies of sub-groups with prevalent disease(s)
cov_rep_geography	for studies where the sample was from a location that was representative of the underlying geography; 1 for studies where the sample was in a location that was not representative of the underlying geography
cov_exposure_study	0 for studies where the exposure was measured multiple times; 1 for studies where the exposure was measured only once
cov_outcome_selfreport	0 for studies where the outcome was measured with self-report and at least one additional measurement technique (e.g., physician diagnosis, administrative medical records); 1 for studies where the outcome was measured only with self-report
cov_outcome_subgroup	0 if the effect size measure was reported for not a subgroup of the outcome; 1 if the effect size measure is reported for a subgroup of the outcome. This applies only to IHD (subgroups include myocardial infarction) and Colorectal cancer (subgroups include colon cancer, rectum cancer).
cov_odds_ratio	0 if the effect size measure was not odds ratio; 1 if the effect size measure was for odds ratio
cov_incidence_only, cov_mortality_only cov_incidence_mortality_together	cascading dummy variables for the endpoint of the effect sizes. There are three types: (1) the endpoint is incidence (2) the end point is mortality only, and (3) the endpoint combines both morbidity and mortality. If the endpoint type is 1, indicating that the effect sizes are exclusive to morbidity, then cov_incidence_only will be set to 1 for studies with effect size on incidence only, and to 0 otherwise. When the effect size used is for mortality, cov_mortality_only will be assigned a value of 1, and 0 in all other cases. If the effect size endpoint encompasses both incidence and mortality, cov_incidence_mortality_together will be marked as 1, and 0 otherwise
cov_bmi	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for body mass index; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for body-mass index
cov_age	0 If the effect sizes were not adjusted for age; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for age
cov_sex	0 If the effect sizes were not adjusted for sex 1 If the effect sizes were sex specific or adjusted for sex
cov_smoking	0 if the effect sizes were not adjusted for smoking; 1 if the effect sizes were adjusted for smoking
Cov_education	0 if the effect sizes were not adjusted for education; 1 if the effect sizes were adjusted for education
cov_diabetes	0 if the effect sizes were not adjusted for diabetes; 1 If the effect were adjusted for diabetes
cov_follow_up	0 if the length of follow up is less than 10 years; 1 if the length of follow-up is 10 years and above
cov_hypertension	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for blood pressure; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for blood pressure
cov_hypercholesterolemia	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for cholesterol (excluding high-density lipoprotein cholesterol); 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for cholesterol (excluding high-density lipoprotein cholesterol)
cov_fruits_intake	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for fruits intake; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted fruits intake
cov_vegetable_intake	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for vegetable intake; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for vegetable intake
Cov_energy_intake	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for energy intake; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for energy intake
Cov_unprocessedmeat	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for unprocessed meat intake; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for unprocessed meat intake
Cov_sodium_intake	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for sodium intake; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted sodium intake
cov_saturated_fat_intake	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for saturated fat intake; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for saturated fat intake
cov_alcohol_use	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for alcohol intake; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for alcohol intake
cov_physical_activity	0 if effect sizes were not adjusted for physical activity; 1 if effect sizes were adjusted for physical activity
Cov_exposure_definitions	0 if the exposure definition matches exactly with the definition matches in specified in the methods 1 if the exposure definition does not match or not reported. This applied for all the three dietary risk factors included in this systematic review. For SSB, we score 0 if sugar is not mentioned clearly as a sweetener (i.e. soft drinks) and 1 if sugar is mentioned clearly as a sweetener or SSB is defined clearly. For trans-fat, we score 0 if the source of trans-fat is not clearly defined and or not from exclusively industrial sources of TFA and 1 is if the TFA source is exclusively from industrial sources. For processed meat we score 0 if the definition for processed meat is not provided, 1 if the definition is clearly reported and aligns with the exposure definition reported in the method section of this paper or PROSPERO protocol.

Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Male	case-cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Female	case-cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	The E3N study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	CHNS	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Mari-Sanchis	2016	SUN cohort	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Montonen	2005	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
Processed meat	T2DM	<i>Männistö</i>	2010	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention study	Male	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Son	2019	Korean Genome and Epidemiology Study (KoGES)	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Song	2004	Women's Health Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Male	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Female	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Villegas	2006	Shanghai Women's Health Study (SWHS)	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	van	2012	Rotterdam study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	Nurses' Health Study	Female	prospective cohort	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	IHD	Burke	2007		Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study (ARIC)	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	IHD	Iqbal	2021	Prospective Urban Rural Epidemiology (PURE) Study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	pan-European EPIC cohort (European Prospective Investigation Into Cancer and Nutrition)	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Processed meat	IHD	Møller	2021	The Danish National Survey on Diet and Physical Activity	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Male	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Female	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0

Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Whiteman	1999	OXCHECK study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Norwegian Counties Study	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Nurses' Health study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
TFA	IHD	Oomen	2001	Zutphen Elderly Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
TFA	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	The Kuopio Ischemic Heart Disease Risk Factor Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
TFA	IHD	Xu	2006	the Strong Heart Study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Nurses' Health Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Health Professionals Follow-Up study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Dhingra	2007	Framingham Heart Study	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Male	prospective cohort	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Female	prospective cohort	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	EPIC-E3N cohort	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Gardener	2018	Northern Manhattan Study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	CARDIA study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Huang	2017	Women health initiative observational study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC-InterAct cohort study	Both	nested case-control	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	EPIC-Norfolk study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Odegaard	2010	Singapore Chinese Health Study	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Black Women's Health Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Black Women's Health Study	Female	prospective cohort	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Pan	2012	Nurses Health study II	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0

SSB	T2DM	Sakurai	2014	Occupational cohort	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Siqueira	2023	ELSA-Brasil study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Torres-Ibarra	2020	Health Workers Cohort Study	Both	prospective cohort	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Viana	2023	Cohort of Universities of Minas Gerais (CUME)	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Collin	2019	REGARDS Study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities' study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities' study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Iowa Women's Health Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
SSB	IHD	Mullee	2019	European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2020	California Teachers Study	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2023	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
SSB	IHD	Warfa	2016	Malmö Diet and Cancer Cohort Study	Both	prospective cohort	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1
SSB	IHD	Yang	2022	Women's Health Initiative	Female	prospective cohort	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

CRC, colorectal cancer; IHD, Ischemic Heart diseases, T2DM, type 2 diabetes

Supplementary Table 8. Quantified bias covariates of major non-dietary intake confounders

Dietary risk	Outcome	author	year	Study name	sex	cov_adj_uste_d_0	cov_adj_uste_d_1	cov_adj_uste_d_2	cov_adj_uste_d_3	cov_adj_uste_d_4	cov_age	cov_sex	cov_educati_on	cov_s_mokin_g	cov_alcohol_use	cov_physical_acti_vity	cov_b_mi	cov_hyp_ertensio_n	cov_diabe_tes	cov_hyp_ercholes_terolemi_a
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	The Nurses' Health Stud, The Health Professionals Follow-up Study (HFPS)	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Bostick	1994	Iowa Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Cancer Prevention Study II Nutrition Cohort	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Cancer Prevention Study II Nutrition Cohort	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Cross	2010	NIH-AARP Diet and Health Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	English	2004	Melbourne Collaborative Cohort Study	Both	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Etemadi	2018	NIH-AARP Diet and Health Study (AARP), Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial (PLCO), Agricultural Health Study (AHS)	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Flood	2003	Breast Cancer Detection Demonstration Project	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Gilsing	2015	Netherlands Cohort Study (NLCS)	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	JPHC I, JPHC II, JACC, MIYAGI, OHSAKI. JPHC-5y, TAKAYAMA	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0

Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	JPHC I, JPHC II, JACC, MIYAGI, OHSAKI, JPHC-5y, TAKAYAMA	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Processed meat	CRC	Knuppel	2020	UK Biobank	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Larsson	2005	Swedish Mammography Cohort	Female	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Lin	2004	Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Mehta	2020	The Sister Study	Female	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Mejborn	2020	The Danish National Survey on Diet and Physical Activity	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Norat	2005	EPIC cohort	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	O'Sullivan	2020	Alberta Tomorrow Project	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Ollberding	2012	The Multiethnic Cohort Study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Processed meat	CRC	Pietinen	1999	Alpha-Tocopherol Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	MDC Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Fretts	2012	SHFS study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Nurses' Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Nurses' Health Study II	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective study	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	The E3N study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	CHNS	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Mari-Sanchis	2016	SUN cohort	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Montonen	2005	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Männistö	2010	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention study	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
Processed meat	T2DM	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Son	2019	Korean Genome and Epidemiology Study (KoGES)	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Song	2004	Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Male	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Female	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Male	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Female	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Villegas	2006	Shanghai Women's Health Study (SWHS)	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	van	2012	Rottersdam study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	Nurses' Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Burke	2007		Both	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study (ARIC)	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Iqbal	2021	Prospective Urban Rural Epidemiology (PURE) Study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	pan-European EPIC cohort (European Prospective Investigation Into Cancer and Nutrition)	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Møller	2021	The Danish National Survey on Diet and Physical Activity	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0

Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
Processed meat	IHD	Whiteman	1999	OXCHECK study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Norwegian Counties Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Nurses' Health study	Female	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
TFA	IHD	Oomen	2001	Zutphen Elderly Study	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
TFA	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	The Kuopio Ischemic Heart Disease Risk Factor Study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
TFA	IHD	Xu	2006	the Strong Heart Study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Nurses' Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Health Professionals Follow-Up study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SSB	T2DM	Dhingra	2007	Framingham Heart Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	EPIC-E3N cohort	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SSB	T2DM	Gardener	2018	Northern Manhattan Study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	CARDIA study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Huang	2017	Women health initiative observational study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
SSB	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC-InterAct cohort study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	EPIC-Norfolk study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Odegaard	2010	Singapore Chinese Health Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Black Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Black Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Pan	2012	Nurses Health study II	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Sakurai	2014	Occupational cohort	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Siqueira	2023	ELSA-Brasil study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Torres-Ibarra	2020	Health Workers Cohort Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0
SSB	T2DM	Viana	2023	Cohort of Universities of Minas Gerais (CUME)	Both	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	IHD	Collin	2019	REGARDS Study	Both	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Male	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities' study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities' study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Iowa Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Mullee	2019	European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2020	California Teachers Study	Female	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2023	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
SSB	IHD	Warfa	2016	Malmö Diet and Cancer Cohort Study	Both	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Yang	2022	Women's Health Initiative	Female	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0

CRC, colorectal cancer; IHD, Ischemic Heart diseases, T2DM, type 2 diabetes

Supplementary Table 9. Quantified bias covariates for major dietary confounders

Dietary risk	outcome	author	year	Study name	sex	cov_energy_intake	cov_unprocessed_meat	cov_fruits_intake	cov_vegetable_intake	cov_sodium_intake	cov_saturated_fat_intake
--------------	---------	--------	------	------------	-----	-------------------	----------------------	-------------------	----------------------	-------------------	--------------------------

Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	The Nurses' Health Study, The Health Professionals Follow-up Study (HFPS)	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Bostick	1994	Iowa Women's Health Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Cancer Prevention Study II Nutrition Cohort	Male	1	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Cancer Prevention Study II Nutrition Cohort	Female	1	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Cross	2010	NIH-AARP Diet and Health Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	English	2004	Melbourne Collaborative Cohort Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Etemadi	2018	NIH-AARP Diet and Health Study (AARP), Prostate, Lung, Colorectal and Ovarian Cancer Screening Trial (PLCO), Agricultural Health Study (AHS)	Both	1	1	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Flood	2003	Breast Cancer Detection Demonstration Project	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Gilting	2015	Netherlands Cohort Study (NLCS)	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	JPHC I, JPHC II, JACC, MIYAGI, OHSAKI. JPHC-5y, TAKAYAMA	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	JPHC I, JPHC II, JACC, MIYAGI, OHSAKI. JPHC-5y, TAKAYAMA	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Knuppel	2020	UK Biobank	Both	0	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Larsson	2005	Swedish Mammography Cohort	Female	1	0	1	1	0	1
Processed meat	CRC	Lin	2004	Women's Health Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Mehta	2020	The Sister Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Mejborn	2020	The Danish National Survey on Diet and Physical Activity	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Norat	2005	EPIC cohort	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	O'Sullivan	2020	Alberta Tomorrow Project	Both	0	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Ollberding	2012	The Multiethnic Cohort Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	CRC	Pietinen	1999	Alpha-Tocopherol Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	0	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	MDC Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Fretts	2012	SHFS study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Nurses' Health Study	Female	1	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Nurses' Health Study II	Female	1	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	1	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC - InterAct study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective study	Male	1	1	0	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective study	Female	1	1	0	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	The E3N study	Female	0	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	CHNS	Both	0	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Mari-Sanchis	2016	SUN cohort	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Montonen	2005	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Männistö	2010	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention study	Male	1	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	Both	0	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Son	2019	Korean Genome and Epidemiology Study (KoGES)	Both	1	0	1	1	1	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Song	2004	Women's Health Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Multiethnic Cohort Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	Villegas	2006	Shanghai Women's Health Study (SWHS)	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	T2DM	van	2012	Rotterdam study	Both	1	1	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	1	1	1	1	0	1
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	Nurses' Health Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Burke	2007		Both	0	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study (ARIC)	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Iqbal	2021	Prospective Urban Rural Epidemiology (PURE) Study	Both	1	1	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	pan-European EPIC cohort (European Prospective Investigation Into Cancer and Nutrition)	Both	1	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Møller	2021	The Danish National Survey on Diet and Physical Activity	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Male	1	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Japan Collaborative Cohort (JACC) Study	Female	1	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Papier	2021	UK Biobank study	Both	0	0	1	1	0	0
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Male	1	1	1	1	1	1
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Japan Public Health Center-based Prospective Study	Female	1	1	1	1	1	1
Processed meat	IHD	Whiteman	1999	OXCHECK study	Both	0	0	0	0	0	0
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Norwegian Counties Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	1

TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Nurses' Health study	Female	1	0	1	1	0	0
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Male	1	0	1	1	0	0
TFA	IHD	Oomen	2001	Zutphen Elderly Study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
TFA	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	The Kuopio Ischemic Heart Disease Risk Factor Study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
TFA	IHD	Xu	2006	the Strong Heart Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Nurses' Health Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Health Professionals Follow-Up study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Dhingra	2007	Framingham Heart Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Male	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Japan Public Health Center study cohort	Female	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	EPIC-E3N cohort	Female	1	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Gardener	2018	Northern Manhattan Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	CARDIA study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Huang	2017	Women health initiative observational study	Female	0	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	InterAct	2013	EPIC-InterAct cohort study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Finnish Mobile Clinic Health Examination Survey	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	EPIC-Norfolk study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Odegaard	2010	Singapore Chinese Health Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Black Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Black Women's Health Study	Female	0	1	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Pan	2012	Nurses Health study II	Female	0	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Male	0	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Thai Cohort Study	Female	0	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	ARIC study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Sakurai	2014	Occupational cohort	Male	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Siqueira	2023	ELSA-Brasil study	Both	1	1	1	1	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Torres-Ibarra	2020	Health Workers Cohort Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	T2DM	Viana	2023	Cohort of Universities of Minas Gerais (CUME)	Both	0	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Collin	2019	REGARDS Study	Both	0	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Male	0	1	1	0	1	0
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Japan Public Health Centre-based study	Female	1	1	1	0	1	0
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities' study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	The atherosclerosis risk in communities' study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention Study	Male	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Iowa Women's Health Study	Female	1	0	0	0	0	1
SSB	IHD	Mullee	2019	European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition	Both	1	1	1	1	0	0
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2020	California Teachers Study	Female	1	0	1	1	0	0
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2023	Health Professionals Follow-up Study	Both	1	0	0	0	0	0
SSB	IHD	Warfa	2016	Malmö Diet and Cancer Cohort Study	Both	1	1	1	1	0	0
SSB	IHD	Yang	2022	Women's Health Initiative	Female	1	0	0	0	0	1

CRC, colorectal cancer; IHD, Ischemic Heart diseases, T2DM, type 2 diabetes

Section 7: Results from individual studies

The health outcome, reference group exposure, alternative group exposure, log effect size, and log effect size SE identified from each report are provided in Supplementary Table 10.

Supplementary Table 10. Summary results from input studies

Dietary risk factor	Outcome	Author	year	Sex	Alternative group exposure	Reference group exposure	Log effect size	Log effect size standard error
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Female	0 - 2 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.26	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Female	2 - 5 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.21	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Female	5 - 8 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.27	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Female	8 - 26 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.25	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Male	0 - 2 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.22	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Male	2 - 5 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.21	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Male	5 - 8 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.34	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Bernstein	2015	Male	8 - 26 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.48	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Bostick	1994	Female	2 - 5 grams	0 - 2 grams	0	0.16
Processed meat	CRC	Bostick	1994	Female	5 - 11 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.07	0.21
Processed meat	CRC	Bostick	1994	Female	11 - 19 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.21	0.29
Processed meat	CRC	Bostick	1994	Female	19 - 26 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.41	0.38
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Male	5 - 11 grams	0 - 5 grams	-0.29	0.16
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Male	11 - 19 grams	0 - 5 grams	0.02	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Male	19 - 27 grams	0 - 5 grams	0.1	0.17
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Male	27 - 49 grams	0 - 5 grams	0.1	0.17
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Female	2 - 5 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.1	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Female	5 - 9 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.05	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Female	9 - 13 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.06	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Chao	2005	Female	13 - 26 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.15	0.16
Processed meat	CRC	Cross	2010	Both	3 - 6 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.04	0.07
Processed meat	CRC	Cross	2010	Both	6 - 10 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.07	0.07
Processed meat	CRC	Cross	2010	Both	10 - 14 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.15	0.07
Processed meat	CRC	Cross	2010	Both	14 - 27 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.15	0.07
Processed meat	CRC	English	2004	Both	10 - 12 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.26	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	English	2004	Both	13 - 25 grams	0 - 10 grams	0	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	English	2004	Both	26 - 38 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.41	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Etemadi	2018	Both	4 - 6 grams	0 - 4 grams	-0.03	0.04
Processed meat	CRC	Etemadi	2018	Both	6 - 9 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.07	0.04
Processed meat	CRC	Etemadi	2018	Both	9 - 12 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.1	0.04
Processed meat	CRC	Etemadi	2018	Both	12 - 19 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.16	0.05
Processed meat	CRC	Flood	2003	Female	1 - 4 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.11	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Flood	2003	Female	4 - 8 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.19	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Flood	2003	Female	8 - 14 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.09	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Flood	2003	Female	14 - 28 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.03	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Gilsing	2015	Both	2 - 7 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.03	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Gilsing	2015	Both	7 - 18 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.12	0.15
Processed meat	CRC	Gilsing	2015	Both	18 - 32 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.22	0.16
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	Male	45 - 112 grams	0 - 45 grams	-0.07	0.04
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	Male	112 - 236 grams	0 - 45 grams	-0.11	0.07
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	Male	236 - 394 grams	0 - 45 grams	0.12	0.11
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	Female	45 - 112 grams	0 - 45 grams	0.06	0.05
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	Female	112 - 236 grams	0 - 45 grams	0.1	0.08
Processed meat	CRC	Islam	2019	Female	236 - 394 grams	0 - 45 grams	0.29	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	Knuppel	2020	Both	10 - 18 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.13	0.08
Processed meat	CRC	Knuppel	2020	Both	18 - 25 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.17	0.08
Processed meat	CRC	Knuppel	2020	Both	25 - 33 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.22	0.08
Processed meat	CRC	Larsson	2005	Female	12 - 21 grams	0 - 12 grams	-0.12	0.25
Processed meat	CRC	Larsson	2005	Female	21 - 31 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.01	0.11
Processed meat	CRC	Larsson	2005	Female	31 - 51 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.07	0.11
Processed meat	CRC	Lin	2004	Female	2 - 4 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.17	0.21
Processed meat	CRC	Lin	2004	Female	4 - 8 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.24	0.21
Processed meat	CRC	Lin	2004	Female	8 - 11 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.05	0.23
Processed meat	CRC	Lin	2004	Female	11 - 29 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.16	0.24
Processed meat	CRC	Mehta	2020	Female	6 - 12 grams	0 - 6 grams	-0.02	0.21
Processed meat	CRC	Mehta	2020	Female	12 - 21 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.02	0.21
Processed meat	CRC	Mehta	2020	Female	21 - 35 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.42	0.21
Processed meat	CRC	Mejborn	2020	Both	35 - 100 grams	0 - 35 grams	0.1	0.2
Processed meat	CRC	Norat	2005	Both	10 - 20 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.1	0.09
Processed meat	CRC	Norat	2005	Both	20 - 40 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.11	0.09

Processed meat	CRC	Norat	2005	Both	40 - 80 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.13	0.1
Processed meat	CRC	Norat	2005	Both	80 - 120 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.35	0.14
Processed meat	CRC	O'Sullivan	2020	Both	11 - 21 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.17	0.16
Processed meat	CRC	O'Sullivan	2020	Both	21 - 43 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.21	0.17
Processed meat	CRC	Ollberding	2012	Both	3 - 6 grams	0 - 3 grams	-0.02	0.06
Processed meat	CRC	Ollberding	2012	Both	6 - 9 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.04	0.06
Processed meat	CRC	Ollberding	2012	Both	9 - 13 grams	0 - 3 grams	0	0.06
Processed meat	CRC	Ollberding	2012	Both	13 - 22 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.06	0.06
Processed meat	CRC	Pietinen	1999	Male	38 - 62 grams	0 - 38 grams	0.41	0.2
Processed meat	CRC	Pietinen	1999	Male	62 - 98 grams	0 - 38 grams	0.1	0.24
Processed meat	CRC	Pietinen	1999	Male	98 - 146 grams	0 - 38 grams	0.18	0.24
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	2 - 6 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.15	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	6 - 11 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.07	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	11 - 17 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.09	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	17 - 34 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.15	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	9 - 22 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.11	0.07
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	22 - 34 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.17	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	34 - 42 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.25	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Ericson	2015	Both	42 - 56 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.14	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Fretts	2012	Both	6 - 12 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.37	0.25
Processed meat	T2DM	Fretts	2012	Both	12 - 19 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.57	0.24
Processed meat	T2DM	Fretts	2012	Both	19 - 28 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.3	0.26
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	9 - 18 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.08	0.02
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	18 - 27 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.1	0.03
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	27 - 36 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.13	0.04
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	36 - 45 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.1	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	45 - 54 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.17	0.08
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	54 - 63 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.17	0.12
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	63 - 72 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.31	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	9 - 18 grams	0 - 9 grams	-0.01	0.03
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	18 - 27 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.05	0.04
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	27 - 36 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.08	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	36 - 45 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.13	0.09
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	45 - 54 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.24	0.13
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	54 - 63 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.04	0.22
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Female	63 - 72 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.33	0.19
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Male	9 - 18 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.1	0.04
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Male	18 - 27 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.2	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Male	27 - 36 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.12	0.07
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Male	36 - 45 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.39	0.08
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Male	45 - 54 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.38	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Male	54 - 63 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.43	0.14
Processed meat	T2DM	Gu	2023	Male	63 - 72 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.43	0.14
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Male	16 - 30 grams	0 - 16 grams	0.08	0.07
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Male	30 - 46 grams	0 - 16 grams	0.03	0.08
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Male	46 - 65 grams	0 - 16 grams	0.19	0.08
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Male	65 - 112 grams	0 - 16 grams	0.29	0.08
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Female	9 - 17 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.07	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Female	17 - 28 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.03	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Female	28 - 41 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.1	0.07
Processed meat	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Female	41 - 74 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.07	0.08
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Male	1 - 4 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.01	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Male	4 - 10 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.07	0.12
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Male	10 - 19 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.14	0.12
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Female	1 - 4 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.03	0.13
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Female	4 - 10 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.1	0.13
Processed meat	T2DM	Kurotani	2013	Female	10 - 17 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.05	0.15
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	Female	9 - 20 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.03	0.1
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	Female	20 - 37 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.14	0.1
Processed meat	T2DM	Lajous	2012	Female	37 - 59 grams	0 - 9 grams	0.26	0.1
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	1 - 4 grams	0 - 1 grams	-1.2	0.28
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	4 - 6 grams	0 - 1 grams	-1.02	0.26

Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	6 - 8 grams	0 - 1 grams	-1.2	0.29
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	8 - 10 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.49	0.21
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	10 - 13 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.84	0.25
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	13 - 18 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.49	0.22
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	18 - 22 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.43	0.24
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	22 - 34 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.21	0.23
Processed meat	T2DM	Liu	2021	Both	34 - 61 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.31	0.2
Processed meat	T2DM	Mari-Sanchis	2016	Both	45 - 90 grams	0 - 45 grams	0.63	0.31
Processed meat	T2DM	Mari-Sanchis	2016	Both	90 - 135 grams	0 - 45 grams	1.12	0.51
Processed meat	T2DM	Montonen	2005	Both	18 - 37 grams	0 - 18 grams	0	0.14
Processed meat	T2DM	Montonen	2005	Both	36 - 68 grams	0 - 18 grams	0.19	0.15
Processed meat	T2DM	Montonen	2005	Both	68 - 100 grams	0 - 18 grams	0.2	0.16
Processed meat	T2DM	Männistö	2010	Male	32 - 51 grams	0 - 32 grams	0.04	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Männistö	2010	Male	51 - 73 grams	0 - 32 grams	0.23	0.1
Processed meat	T2DM	Männistö	2010	Male	73 - 99 grams	0 - 32 grams	0.17	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Männistö	2010	Male	99 - 170 grams	0 - 32 grams	0.31	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Papier	2021	Both	8 - 18 grams	0 - 8 grams	0.07	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Papier	2021	Both	18 - 25 grams	0 - 8 grams	0.14	0.04
Processed meat	T2DM	Papier	2021	Both	25 - 33 grams	0 - 8 grams	0.24	0.04
Processed meat	T2DM	Son	2019	Both	0 - 3 grams	0 - 0 grams	0	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Son	2019	Both	3 - 6 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.07	0.12
Processed meat	T2DM	Song	2004	Female	3 - 13 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.03	0.04
Processed meat	T2DM	Song	2004	Female	13 - 30 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.16	0.08
Processed meat	T2DM	Song	2004	Female	30 - 52 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.32	0.11
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	7 - 14 grams	0 - 7 grams	0.2	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	14 - 20 grams	0 - 7 grams	0.26	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	20 - 30 grams	0 - 7 grams	0.37	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	30 - 40 grams	0 - 7 grams	0.45	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	4 - 8 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.18	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	8 - 12 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.22	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	12 - 19 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.31	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	19 - 26 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.37	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	0 - 1 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.17	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	1 - 2 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.17	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	2 - 4 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.24	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Male	4 - 6 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.26	0.05
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	0 - 0 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.17	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	0 - 1 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.17	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	1 - 3 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.18	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Steinbrecher	2011	Female	3 - 5 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.21	0.06
Processed meat	T2DM	Villegas	2006	Female	22 - 68 grams	0 - 22 grams	0.18	0.07
Processed meat	T2DM	Villegas	2006	Female	68 - 112 grams	0 - 22 grams	0.1	0.07
Processed meat	T2DM	van	2012	Both	0 - 17 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.57	0.2
Processed meat	T2DM	van	2012	Both	17 - 30 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.62	0.2
Processed meat	T2DM	van	2012	Both	30 - 42 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.55	0.2
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	Male	4 - 8 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.02	0.05
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	Male	8 - 13 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.09	0.05
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	Male	13 - 21 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.05	0.05
Processed meat	IHD	Al-Shaar	2020	Male	21 - 39 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.17	0.06
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	Female	1 - 2 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.12	0.06
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	Female	2 - 5 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.02	0.05
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	Female	5 - 8 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.02	0.06
Processed meat	IHD	Bernstein	2010	Female	8 - 26 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.05	0.06
Processed meat	IHD	Burke	2007	Both	6 - 14 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.79	0.38
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Both	2 - 11 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.05	0.1
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Both	11 - 20 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.02	0.1
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Both	20 - 25 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.04	0.1
Processed meat	IHD	Haring	2014	Both	25 - 63 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.04	0.11
Processed meat	IHD	Iqbal	2021	Both	0 - 7 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.03	0.22
Processed meat	IHD	Iqbal	2021	Both	7 - 21 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.15	0.22
Processed meat	IHD	Iqbal	2021	Both	21 - 36 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.53	0.28
Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	Both	6 - 16 grams	0 - 6 grams	-0.02	0.05

Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	Both	16 - 28 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.03	0.05
Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	Both	28 - 42 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.07	0.05
Processed meat	IHD	Key	2019	Both	42 - 74 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.1	0.05
Processed meat	IHD	Møller	2021	Both	19 - 58 grams	0 - 19 grams	-0.12	0.12
Processed meat	IHD	Møller	2021	Both	58 - 97 grams	0 - 19 grams	0.1	0.16
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Male	1 - 2 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.01	0.22
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Male	2 - 4 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.14	0.23
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Male	4 - 8 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.22	0.21
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Male	8 - 18 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.58	0.23
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Female	1 - 2 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.11	0.25
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Female	2 - 3 grams	0 - 1 grams	0.04	0.28
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Female	3 - 6 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.08	0.25
Processed meat	IHD	Nagao	2012	Female	6 - 13 grams	0 - 1 grams	-0.02	0.26
Processed meat	IHD	Papier	2021	Both	10 - 18 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.1	0.04
Processed meat	IHD	Papier	2021	Both	18 - 25 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.13	0.04
Processed meat	IHD	Papier	2021	Both	25 - 33 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.14	0.04
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Male	2 - 4 grams	0 - 2 grams	0.07	0.15
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Male	4 - 6 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.13	0.16
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Male	6 - 10 grams	0 - 2 grams	-0.17	0.18
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Female	3 - 6 grams	0 - 3 grams	-0.16	0.22
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Female	6 - 9 grams	0 - 3 grams	-0.27	0.24
Processed meat	IHD	Saito	2020	Female	9 - 14 grams	0 - 3 grams	-0.05	0.23
Processed meat	IHD	Whiteman	1999	Both	6 - 19 grams	0 - 6 grams	0	0.24
Processed meat	IHD	Whiteman	1999	Both	19 - 45 grams	0 - 6 grams	0.25	0.52
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	0.15-0.65%	0-0.15%	0.05	0.07
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	0.65-1.15%	0-0.15%	0.17	0.08
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	1.15-1.65%	0-0.15%	0.17	0.08
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	1.65-2.15%	0-0.15%	0.21	0.1
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	0.85-1.35%	0-0.85%	0.01	0.06
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	1.35-1.85%	0-0.85%	-0.01	0.07
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	1.85-2.35%	0-0.85%	-0.02	0.09
TFA	IHD	Laake	2012	Both	2.35-2.85%	0-0.85%	0.1	0.11
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Female	1.3-1.6%	0-1.3%	0.08	0.06
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Female	1.6-1.85%	0-1.3%	0.12	0.06
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Female	1.85-2.15%	0-1.3%	0.14	0.07
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Female	2.15-2.9%	0-1.3%	0.18	0.08
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Male	0.85-1.15%	0-1.3%	0.17	0.06
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Male	1.15-1.4%	0-1.3%	0.19	0.06
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Male	1.4-1.6%	0-1.3%	0.2	0.06
TFA	IHD	Li	2015	Male	1.6-2.1%	0-1.3%	0.19	0.07
TFA	IHD	Oomen	2001	Male	3.11-4.86%	0-3.11%	0.29	0.29
TFA	IHD	Oomen	2001	Male	4.86-6.61%	0-3.11%	0.69	0.15
TFA	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Male	0.49-0.59%	0-0.49%	0.1	0.09
TFA	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Male	0.59-0.76%	0-0.49%	-0.03	0.09
TFA	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Male	0.76-1%	0-0.49%	0.07	0.09
TFA	IHD	Pietinen	1997	Male	1-2.69%	0-0.49%	0.13	0.09
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	Male	0.8-1%	0-0.8%	-0.05	0.22
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	Male	1-1.3%	0-0.8%	-0.16	0.25
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	Male	1.3-1.7%	0-0.8%	0.01	0.23
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	Male	0.8-1%	0-0.8%	-0.46	0.17
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	Male	1-1.3%	0-0.8%	-0.03	0.16
TFA	IHD	Virtanen	2014	Male	1.3-1.7%	0-0.8%	-0.06	0.15
TFA	IHD	Xu	2006	Both	1.35-2.2%	0-1.35%	0.16	0.15
TFA	IHD	Xu	2006	Both	2.2-3.25%	0-1.35%	0.12	0.15
TFA	IHD	Xu	2006	Both	3.25-4.55%	0-1.35%	0.06	0.16
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Female	12 - 73 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.08	0.03
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Female	73 - 232 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.17	0.04
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Female	232 - 450 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.25	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Female	12 - 80 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.01	0.03
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Female	80 - 261 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.02	0.04
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Female	261 - 510 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.18	0.09
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Male	12 - 85 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.05	0.05

SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Male	85 - 244 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.17	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Male	244 - 438 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.29	0.1
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Male	12 - 85 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.02	0.05
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Male	64 - 229 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.13	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Bhupathiraju	2013	Male	229 - 481 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.31	0.12
SSB	T2DM	Dhingra	2007	Both	0 - 512 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.19	0.1
SSB	T2DM	Dhingra	2007	Both	512 - 852 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.28	0.13
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Male	97 - 146 grams	0 - 97 grams	-0.15	0.12
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Male	146 - 195 grams	0 - 97 grams	-0.19	0.16
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Male	195 - 341 grams	0 - 97 grams	-0.02	0.15
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Female	97 - 146 grams	0 - 97 grams	0.14	0.14
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Female	146 - 195 grams	0 - 97 grams	0.16	0.21
SSB	T2DM	Eshak	2013	Female	195 - 341 grams	0 - 97 grams	0.58	0.24
SSB	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	Female	0 - 12 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.25	0.1
SSB	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	Female	12 - 23 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.11	0.13
SSB	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	Female	23 - 51 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.2	0.13
SSB	T2DM	Fagherazzi	2013	Female	52 - 79 grams	0 - 3 grams	0.26	0.12
SSB	T2DM	Gardener	2018	Both	11 - 292 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.12	0.18
SSB	T2DM	Gardener	2018	Both	341 - 622 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.14	0.19
SSB	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	Both	34 - 135 grams	0 - 34 grams	-0.02	0.15
SSB	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	Both	135 - 237 grams	0 - 34 grams	-0.03	0.16
SSB	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	Both	237 - 473 grams	0 - 34 grams	-0.04	0.15
SSB	T2DM	Hirahatake	2019	Both	473 - 710 grams	0 - 34 grams	0.24	0.16
SSB	T2DM	Huang	2017	Female	51 - 355 grams	0 - 51 grams	0.08	0.08
SSB	T2DM	Huang	2017	Female	355 - 710 grams	0 - 51 grams	0.17	0.08
SSB	T2DM	Huang	2017	Female	710 - 1065 grams	0 - 51 grams	0.4	0.13
SSB	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Both	10 - 57 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.17	0.14
SSB	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Both	57 - 260 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.07	0.06
SSB	T2DM	InterAct	2013	Both	260 - 591 grams	0 - 10 grams	0.25	0.12
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Both	4 - 14 grams	0 - 4 grams	-0.39	0.26
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Both	14 - 36 grams	0 - 4 grams	-0.05	0.23
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Both	36 - 66 grams	0 - 4 grams	0.44	0.19
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Both	0 - 7 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.16	0.36
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Both	7 - 78 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.22	0.32
SSB	T2DM	Montonen	2007	Both	78 - 208 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.47	0.28
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	0 - 49 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.03	0.1
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	50 - 139 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.02	0.1
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	140 - 3172 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.12	0.09
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	1 - 232 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.19	0.1
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	233 - 881 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.3	0.1
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	882 - 5096 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.17	0.11
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	1 - 74 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.18	0.12
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	75 - 210 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.28	0.11
SSB	T2DM	O'Connor	2015	Both	211 - 2653 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.3	0.11
SSB	T2DM	Odegaard	2010	Both	12 - 37 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.1	0.07
SSB	T2DM	Odegaard	2010	Both	37 - 151 grams	0 - 12 grams	-0.02	0.12
SSB	T2DM	Odegaard	2010	Both	151 - 356 grams	0 - 12 grams	0.29	0.07
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	24 - 122 grams	0 - 24 grams	-0.12	0.05
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	122 - 268 grams	0 - 24 grams	0	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	268 - 414 grams	0 - 24 grams	0.1	0.07
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	414 - 852 grams	0 - 24 grams	0.22	0.08
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	24 - 122 grams	0 - 24 grams	0.08	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	122 - 268 grams	0 - 24 grams	0.08	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	268 - 414 grams	0 - 24 grams	0.16	0.07
SSB	T2DM	Palmer	2008	Female	414 - 852 grams	0 - 24 grams	0.27	0.08
SSB	T2DM	Pan	2012	Female	69 - 137 grams	0 - 69 grams	0.1	0.05
SSB	T2DM	Pan	2012	Female	137 - 171 grams	0 - 69 grams	0.2	0.05
SSB	T2DM	Pan	2012	Female	403 - 600 grams	0 - 69 grams	0.29	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Pan	2012	Female	600 - 797 grams	0 - 69 grams	0.25	0.09
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Male	49 - 292 grams	0 - 49 grams	0	0.1
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Male	341 - 585 grams	0 - 49 grams	0.26	0.22
SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Female	49 - 292 grams	0 - 49 grams	0.47	0.14

SSB	T2DM	Papier	2017	Female	341 - 585 grams	0 - 49 grams	0.88	0.24
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	Male	240 - 264 grams	0 - 240 grams	0.09	0.17
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	Male	264 - 456 grams	0 - 240 grams	0.06	0.12
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	Male	456 - 672 grams	0 - 240 grams	0.02	0.15
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	Female	240 - 264 grams	0 - 240 grams	-0.26	0.16
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	Female	264 - 456 grams	0 - 240 grams	0.05	0.12
SSB	T2DM	Paynter	2006	Female	456 - 672 grams	0 - 240 grams	0.07	0.15
SSB	T2DM	Sakurai	2014	Male	8 - 76 grams	0 - 8 grams	-0.03	0.27
SSB	T2DM	Sakurai	2014	Male	76 - 195 grams	0 - 8 grams	0.1	0.21
SSB	T2DM	Sakurai	2014	Male	195 - 288 grams	0 - 8 grams	0.29	0.3
SSB	T2DM	Siqueira	2023	Both	25 - 100 grams	0 - 25 grams	0.02	0.06
SSB	T2DM	Siqueira	2023	Both	100 - 250 grams	0 - 25 grams	0	0.09
SSB	T2DM	Siqueira	2023	Both	250 - 400 grams	0 - 25 grams	0.21	0.1
SSB	T2DM	Torres-Ibarra	2020	Both	51 - 203 grams	0 - 51 grams	0.1	0.29
SSB	T2DM	Torres-Ibarra	2020	Both	253 - 405 grams	0 - 51 grams	0.47	0.34
SSB	T2DM	Viana	2023	Both	118 - 303 grams	0 - 118 grams	0.49	0.25
SSB	IHD	Collin	2019	Both	21 - 45 grams	0 - 21 grams	0.15	0.22
SSB	IHD	Collin	2019	Both	45 - 424 grams	0 - 21 grams	0.36	0.2
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Male	36 - 71 grams	0 - 36 grams	-0.16	0.13
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Male	107 - 143 grams	0 - 36 grams	-0.16	0.17
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Male	250 - 286 grams	0 - 36 grams	0.04	0.18
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Female	36 - 71 grams	0 - 36 grams	-0.04	0.25
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Female	107 - 143 grams	0 - 36 grams	0.42	0.34
SSB	IHD	Eshak	2012	Female	250 - 286 grams	0 - 36 grams	-0.13	0.55
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Male	0 - 127 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.01	0.03
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Female	0 - 41 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.01	0.02
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Male	0 - 47 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.01	0.01
SSB	IHD	Keller	2020	Female	0 - 30 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.01	0.01
SSB	IHD	Mullee	2019	Both	8 - 33 grams	0 - 8 grams	0.03	0.06
SSB	IHD	Mullee	2019	Both	36 - 214 grams	0 - 8 grams	-0.05	0.06
SSB	IHD	Mullee	2019	Both	250 - 750 grams	0 - 8 grams	0.04	0.09
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2020	Female	0 - 34 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.05	0.05
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2020	Female	34 - 237 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.04	0.06
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2020	Female	237 - 439 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.14	0.11
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2023	Both	11 - 45 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.05	0.03
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2023	Both	98 - 292 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.11	0.03
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2023	Both	341 - 682 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.22	0.06
SSB	IHD	Pacheco	2023	Both	682 - 1023 grams	0 - 11 grams	0.22	0.05
SSB	IHD	Warfa	2016	Both	0 - 50 grams	0 - 0 grams	-0.06	0.06
SSB	IHD	Warfa	2016	Both	50 - 250 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.04	0.05
SSB	IHD	Warfa	2016	Both	250 - 450 grams	0 - 0 grams	0.11	0.07
SSB	IHD	Yang	2022	Female	51 - 355 grams	0 - 51 grams	-0.02	0.04
SSB	IHD	Yang	2022	Female	355 - 1065 grams	0 - 51 grams	0.3	0.08

Section 8. Details on statistical methods

Supplementary Table 11. MR-BRT splines and prior specifications

Risk	Health outcome	Spline degree, number of interior knots	Priors & constraints
Processed meat	Ischemic heart disease	Quadratic, 3 interior knots	Monotonic increasing, right linear tail, Gaussian max derivative prior on the right tail (0, 0.001)
Processed meat	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Quadratic, 3 interior knots	Monotonic increasing, right linear tail, Gaussian max derivative prior on the right tail (0, 0.001)
Processed meat	Colon and rectum cancer	Quadratic, 3 interior knots	Monotonic increasing, right linear tail, Gaussian max derivative prior on the right tail (0, 0.001)

SSB	Ischemic heart disease	Quadratic, 3 interior knots	Monotonic increasing, right linear tail, Gaussian max derivative prior on the right tail (0, 0.001)
SSB	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Quadratic, 3 interior knots	Monotonic increasing, right linear tail, Gaussian max derivative prior on the right tail (0, 0.001)
Trans fat	Ischemic heart disease	cubic, 3 interior knots	monotonic increasing, right linear tail, Gaussian max derivative prior on the right tail (0, 0.001)

Supplementary Table 12. Bias covariates and estimated parameters

Risk	Health outcome	Selected bias covariates	Gamma solution (mean and sd)
Processed meat	Ischemic heart disease	Having multiple exposure assessment	0.00000002(0.14)
Processed meat	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Adjusted for hypertension, Having multiple exposure assessment	0.000000001(0.04)
Processed meat	Colon and rectum cancer	None	0.000000009(0.04)
SSB	Ischemic heart disease	None	0.00000002 (0.04)
SSB	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Adjusted for hypertension, adjusted for hypercholesterolemia, exposure definition	0.009 (0.04)
Trans fat	Ischemic heart disease	None	0.04 (0.06)

Section 9: Risk curve details

Supplementary Table 13-15 shows the relative risk for each risk-outcome pair derived from the relative risk curves presented in the main text (Figures 1-6). The 95% uncertainty intervals (UI), as reported in the main text, incorporate unexplained between-study heterogeneity. We also provided conventional 95% UI of the relative risk, without between-study heterogeneity, for comparison.

Supplementary Table 13. Relative risks of type 2 diabetes and colorectal cancer across exposure range for every 50g/day increased consumption of processed meat derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 1,3)			
	Processed meat consumption (g/day)	RR (95% UI with between-study heterogeneity)	RR (95% UI without between-study heterogeneity)
Type 2 diabetes	50	1.3 (1.12, 1.52)	1.3 (1.22, 1.38)
	100	1.5 (1.2, 1.91)	1.5 (1.37, 1.65)
	150	1.56 (1.22, 2.03)	1.56 (1.41, 1.73)
	200	1.57 (1.22, 2.04)	1.57 (1.41, 1.74)
	250	1.57 (1.22, 2.05)	1.57 (1.41, 1.75)
	300	1.58 (1.22, 2.06)	1.58 (1.42, 1.75)
	350	1.58 (1.23, 2.07)	1.58 (1.42, 1.76)
	400	1.59 (1.23, 2.08)	1.59 (1.42, 1.76)
Colorectal cancer	50	1.26 (1.08, 1.47)	1.27 (1.18, 1.36)
	100	1.32 (1.09, 1.58)	1.32 (1.22, 1.44)
	150	1.32 (1.1, 1.59)	1.32 (1.22, 1.44)
	200	1.33 (1.1, 1.59)	1.33 (1.22, 1.45)
	250	1.33 (1.1, 1.6)	1.33 (1.22, 1.46)
	300	1.34 (1.1, 1.61)	1.34 (1.23, 1.46)
	350	1.34 (1.1, 1.62)	1.34 (1.23, 1.47)
	400	1.35 (1.1, 1.63)	1.35 (1.23, 1.48)

Supplementary Table 14. Relative risks of IHD across exposure range of processed meat derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 2)			
	Processed meat consumption (g/day)	RR (95% UI with between-study heterogeneity)	RR (95% UI without between-study heterogeneity)
Ischemic heart disease	25	1.1 (0.98, 1.22)	1.1 (1.05, 1.14)
	50	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)
	75	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)
	100	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)
	200	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)
	250	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)
	300	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)
	350	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)
	400	1.15 (0.97, 1.36)	1.15 (1.07, 1.22)

Supplementary Table 15. Relative risks of type 2 diabetes and IHD across exposure range for every 250g/day increased consumption of SSB derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 4-5)			
	SSB consumption (g/day)	RR (95% UI with between-study heterogeneity)	RR (95% UI without between-study heterogeneity)
Type 2 diabetes	250	1.2 (1.07, 1.34)	1.2 (1.16, 1.24)
	500	1.28 (1.1, 1.49)	1.28 (1.22, 1.33)
	750	1.38 (1.13, 1.68)	1.38 (1.3, 1.46)
	1000	1.5 (1.17, 1.92)	1.5 (1.39, 1.61)
Ischemic heart disease	250	1.07 (1.03, 1.12)	1.07 (1.05, 1.09)
	500	1.2 (1.07, 1.34)	1.2 (1.14, 1.25)
	750	1.29 (1.1, 1.50)	1.28 (1.2, 1.36)
	1000	1.29 (1.1, 1.51)	1.29 (1.2, 1.37)

Supplementary Table 16. Relative risks of IHD across exposure range for every percent increased energy consumption of trans fat derived from the relative risks presented in the main text (Figure 6)

	Trans fat consumption (% daily energy intake)	RR (95% UI with between-study heterogeneity)	RR (95% UI without between-study heterogeneity)
Ischemic heart disease	1	1.11 (1, 1.24)	1.11 (1.07, 1.15)
	2	1.2 (1, 1.44)	1.2 (1.12, 1.27)
	3	1.26 (1, 1.59)	1.26 (1.16, 1.36)
	4	1.3 (1, 1.68)	1.29 (1.18, 1.41)
	5	1.31 (1, 1.72)	1.31 (1.19, 1.43)
	6	1.31 (1, 1.72)	1.31 (1.19, 1.43)

Section 10: Sensitivity results

Supplementary Table 17: Non-trimming: Strength of the evidence for the relationship between processed meat, SSBs and TFAs consumption and health outcomes

Risk-outcome pair	85th percentile exposure level	Unit of exposure	RR (95% UI with γ)	RR (95% UI without γ)	BPRF	Risk-outcome score	Star rating	Pub. bias	No. of studies	Selected bias covariates
Processed meat-Type 2 diabetes	57	g/day	1.37 (1.18, 1.59)	1.37 (1.28, 1.46)	15%	0.14	★ ★ ★	No	16	Education, smoking, energy intake, vegetable intake, hypertension, length follow-up, having multiple exposures assessment,
Processed meat-colorectal cancer	55	g/day	1.32 (1, 1.74)	1.32 (1.19, 1.46)	2%	0.02	★ ★	No	18	Alcohol intake, physical activity, length follow-up, and type 2 diabetes
Processed meat-IHD	30	g/day	1.11 (0.97, 1.28)	1.11 (1.05, 1.18)	N/A	-0.01	★	No	11	Unprocessed meat intake
SSB-Type 2 diabetes	390	g/day	1.24 (1.09, 1.42)	1.24 (1.19, 1.3)	7%	0.07	★ ★	No	19	Exposure definition
SSB-IHD	365	g/day	1.12 (1.05, 1.21)	1.12 (1.09, 1.16)	3%	0.02	★ ★	No	8	None
Trans-fat -IHD	2.56	Percent of daily energy intake	1.22 (0.76, 1.97)	1.22 (1.07, 1.4)	NA	-0.12	★	No	6	None

The reported relative risk (RR) and its 95% uncertainty interval (UI) reflect the risk an individual who has been exposed to dietary risk factor of interest (i.e. processed meat, SSBs and TFAs consumption) has of developing the outcome of interest relative to that of someone who has not been exposed. We report the 95% UI when not incorporating between-study heterogeneity (γ) – "95% UI without γ " – and when accounting for between-study heterogeneity – "95% UI with γ ." The Burden of Proof Risk Function (BPRF) is calculated for risk-outcome pairs that were found to have significant relationships at an 0.05 level of significance when not incorporating between-study heterogeneity (i.e., the lower bound of the 95% UI without γ does not cross the null RR value of one). The BPRF corresponds to the 5th quantile estimate of relative risk accounting for between-study heterogeneity closest to the null for each risk–outcome pair, and it reflects the most conservative estimate of excess risk associated with dietary risk factors of interest that is consistent with the available data. Negative risk-outcome score indicate that the evidence of the association is very weak and inconsistent. For ease of interpretation, we have transformed the risk-outcome score and BPRF into a star rating (0-5) with a higher rating representing a larger effect with stronger evidence. The selected bias covariates were chosen for inclusion in the model using an algorithm that systematically detects bias covariates that correspond to significant sources of bias in the observations included. If selected, the observations were adjusted to better reflect the gold standard values of the covariate. For more information about the definition of candidate bias covariates, see Supplementary Table 6.

